

A Guide to ATLAS, Vildehaye, and Kamadata

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Version and Change Log

This version of the manual was produced on November 17, 2022.

The software and this manual use some icons made by Freepik from <https://www.flaticon.com>.

November 17, 2022: Added Section 8.5 on SSH tunnels using AWS and marked Section 8.6 on standalone SSH tunnels as obsolete.

June 30, 2022: Added Chapter 11 on computing localizations.

May 1, 2022: Added information about tags with BMP384 pressure+temperature sensors.

April 28, 2022: Added a section on collecting and presenting performance data using Prometheus and Grafana.

April 15, 2022: Added sections on debugging the Java code and on diagnosing memory leaks.

April 15, 2022: `import` statements are no longer needed in configuration files, all references to them removed.

February 25, 2022: Added Section A.8 on production variants of the front-end units.

January 17, 2022: Added Chapter 5 on the ATLAS command-line interface. Also removed the `invalidate` option from the `query` command and replaced it by a separate command.

January 10, 2022: Added dataflow diagrams of key classes to the appendix.

December 29, 2021: Added a section on the hourly consistency enforcer to the appendix.

December 21, 2021: Added information about using low-cost CC1310 modules as tags.

August 12, 2021: Added a section on faster extraction of logging data using a Raspberry Pi, and updated the build instruction for FFTW to eliminate dependency on AVX and AVX2, which caused ATLAS to fail on some laptops.

July 11, 2021: Added documentation of the new `clocksync-strategy` option to `query`.

June 21, 2021: Clarified how the duration of sensor measurements in `SensorConfiguration` is used.

April 26, 2021: Added description of the `AttachInputs` option for localization strategies and JSON output from queries.

April 5, 2021: Added Section 8.9 on ad-hoc receivers controlled by the web app.

February 17, 2021: Split Section 11.7 into 11.7 and 11.8 (setting up and using Vildehaye logging base stations are now in separate sections) and added instructions to 11.7 to assemble a logging base station from modules. Also added a picture of the MOSFET load switch to Chapter 13.

February 16, 2021: Added section 13.6 on the use of low-cost CC1352P modules as tags.

February 3, 2021: Added instructions to remove the FTDI kernel driver and to acquire permissions for using an FTDI dongle to Section 11.3.

September 17, 2020: Many formatting changes. Also replaced the setup command by connect-to and updated the Linux installation instructions to Ubuntu 20.04. Added chapters on software (including how to build the software and the firmware), hardware, and the web application.

February 8, 2020. Added material on WiFi hotspots.

July 16, 2019. Added Section 11.6 on setting up Vildehaye logging base stations.

August 21, 2018. Added Chapter 14 on sensor-logging boards. This pushed the chapter on monitoring and performance problems to become Chapter 15.

July 5, 2018. Added Appendix A and moved the original appendix to B. Appendix A shows when the system can and cannot localize when there is no beacon that all the base stations receive.

September 7, 2017. Added Section 13.4, advanced tag-programming options.

August 28 ,2017. Added database column names to Section 8.4.

August 17, 2017. Added section 8.4 that describes the output formats of queries (currently only of localizations)

July 20, 2017. Invalidation queries now specify the database using the input argument, not the output argument.

July 2, 2017. Calibration files are now stored in the calibration subdirectory of configuration directories and downloaded from there as needed, automatically.

June 27, 2017. Added Section 6.2, which shows how to create a task to run the base station software automatically under Windows (contributed by Christine Beardsworth).

June 26, 2017. Added Section 5.4, Virtual Tags.

June 20, 2017. A new section in Chapter 13 (13.2) explains how to define Vildehaye tags. Improvements to Section 6.7 (running Vildeyahe ad-hoc base stations) explain how to transition tags from configuration to configuration.

June 14, 2017: radioJniLibrary=jni-radio-connection-xxx can be shortened to radio=xxx in ATLAS versions 1017 and up. Also added Chapter 11 (setting up Vildehaye base stations and ATLAS/Vildehaye beacons); deleted the section on programming launchpads to serve as beacons and base stations, because the new Chapter 11 covers the same material. Improved image of the LNA.

Chapter 1

An Overview

This document explains how to install and use ATLAS, Vildehaye, and Kamadata.

ATLAS is a reverse-GPS wildlife tracking system.

Vildehaye is a system of multifunction wildlife telemetry tags that can carry sensors and memory to store sensor data, as well as base stations that can communicate with them.

ATLAS uses Vildehaye tags, but they can also be used without ATLAS.

Kamadata is an interactive program for visualizing and analyzing wildlife tracks. It is used to visualize ATLAS tracking data and ATLAS performance data, but it can also be used to visualize tracking data from other systems.

ATLAS real-time data can also be viewed on a web application that runs on a wide range of devices, from smartphones to laptops and desktops.

Many people contributed to the development of these systems. Contributors from Tel-Aviv University include Sivan Toledo, Tony Weiss, Arie Yeredor, Oren Kishon, Bruria Berger, Ronny Ziss, Ari Lev-Or, Itamar Melamed, Andrei Leshchenko, Shai Mendel, Yaniv Rubinpur, Yazan Badarny, Shai Mendel, Tal Avinari, Assaf Uzan, Orr Spiegel, and Eitam Arnon. Contributors from the Hebrew University include Ran Nathan, Yotam Orchan, Yoav Bartan, Adi Weller-Weiser, Adi Shohat, Lea Aiach, Motti Charter, Sivan Margalit, and Anat Levi. Contributors from the Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ) include Allert Bijleveld, Bas Denissen and Frank van Maarseveen. Other contributors include Nir Sapir and Yoni Vortman.

1.1 ATLAS Systems

ATLAS systems consist of several components:

- *Tags* transmit radio messages. Each tag transmits a unique message or code. Most tags are attached to wild animals, but the system also requires a couple of *beacon* tags at fixed known locations.
- *Infrastructure base stations* detect transmission of tags and beacons and estimate the time of arrival of these transmissions. They send this information to a server. The base stations consist of an antenna, usually an amplifier and filter, a radio, and a computer that processes radio-frequency (RF) samples from the receiver.

Figure 1.1: The main components of an ATLAS system.

- A primary *server* collects detection reports from the base stations; it can also compute localizations (location estimates) and store detections and localizations in a database. A system can also have secondary servers and the localization computations and database storage can be done in them, in addition or instead of in the primary server.
- A *database* (or multiple databases) that stores localizations and detections. The database needs to be a MySQL database (free). For small experiments or temporary setups ATLAS can also use an sqlite database, which requires no installation or administration.
- ATLAS data can be accessed by clients (laptops, desktops, smart phones, and tablets), either using a *web application*, a graphical interactive program called *Kamadata*, or via a command-line tool.

ATLAS systems can also have *ad-hoc* base stations, which do not report to a server, unlike infrastructure base stations. Ad-hoc base stations are portable and are used to test tags and to home-in on tags.

ATLAS systems track a set of tags with known individual characteristics (the code that each tag transmits, for example). ATLAS systems cannot track tags whose characteristics they do not know.

1.2 Vildehaye Systems

Vildehaye systems consist of tags, sensor and memory boards, and base stations, both infrastructure and ad-hoc. A Vildehaye system does not need to have infrastructure base stations, but if it does, it needs a server and a database like an ATLAS system.

Vildevhaye tags can communicate with Vildevhaye base stations. A Vildevhaye base station can consist of a low-cost data radio connected to a computer (possibly a low cost and low power Raspberry Pi), or of a low-cost data radio with an add-on board that allows it to log data to a memory card. The communication between tags and base stations can be bi-directional; tags can send information to base stations, and base stations can send commands to tags and they can acknowledge receipt of data.

Vildevhaye tags can also transmit ATLAS codes. In particular, a tag can transmit only ATLAS codes, only Vildevhaye-type communication, or both.

The range of functionality of Vildevhaye tags is still evolving.

1.3 User Roles and How to Use This Guide

ATLAS and Vildevhaye Systems are used and accessed by people with different objectives and roles. A single person will often serve multiple roles, but it still helps to understand the different roles.

- A **user** tracks animals and sometimes collects sensor data using an ATLAS and/or Vildevhaye system.
- An **administrator** manages the configuration of an ATLAS system, monitors its operation, and ensures that technical faults are corrected.
- An **IT assistant** (information technology assistant) helps users and the administrator install software, manages the database, ensures that it is backed up regularly, and corrects software problems.
- An **RF technician** installs radios and their peripheral equipment, such as antennas, amplifiers, cables, and connectors.
- A **tag preparer** assembles tags and programs them.
- The **group leader** is the investigator in charge of the ATLAS and/or Vildevhaye system.

Users activate tags (in the field or prior to going to the field), deploy them (attach them to animals), manage deployment metadata (that is, keep track of which tag is on which animal and when), views localizations, detections of the tags, and sensor data, and analyze the data. Most users benefit from operating ad-hoc base stations to home-in on animals or tags that detached from animals and to ensure that tags are working properly before deploying them.

The tasks that the **IT assistant** performs are mostly non-critical and not difficult, with the important exception of database administration. Managing a database and ensuring that it performs well and is backed up properly and regularly is a significant responsibility, so it helps to assign this role to an experienced person.

Setting up ATLAS base stations, the job of the **RF technician**, does not require a lot of expertise and the skills are not hard to learn, but this activity is technical and requires at least some learning.

ATLAS and Vildehaye are complex systems that are being developed and maintained by scientists for (other) scientists. It is not a commercial system, and it does have quirks and bugs. The **group leader** and the **administrator** should set their expectations accordingly.

Users should read the chapters on software installation, connecting to ATLAS systems, running queries, using tags, and the section on running ad-hoc base stations (but they need not read the rest of the chapter on running base stations). If an IT assistant installs the software for you, you can read less, but installing the required software on a Windows computer is not complicated; you can do it yourself.

Administrators should read the entire manual. **Group leaders** should at least skim through the entire manual, to understand the range of tasks that members of their groups will need to carry out, and they should discuss planning and staffing with their administrator.

IT assistants should read the entire manual with the exception of chapters on hardware setup. **RF technicians** should read the chapter on setting up base stations, and **tag preparers** should read the chapter on tag preparation.

Everybody who runs ATLAS software should know how to update the software; it changes quickly.

1.4 Openness and Users' Contributions

Vildehaye, Kamadata, and to some extent ATLAS are open systems that persons and groups other than the original developer can expand.

If you are interested in contributing to the technology and expanding its capabilities, we suggest that you start by discussing your plans with the author.

1.5 Software Licensing and Support

Using ATLAS and Vildehaye requires a license and/or the agreement of the developers. Kamadata is distributed as free open-source software and does not require a license.

If you are interested in setting up an ATLAS or Vildehaye system, please discuss your plans with the developers. We grant licensed without a fee, but we ramp up usage in a controlled way that limits the technical support effort required and that allows us to study and improve the technology as more systems are deployed.

We support ATLAS users using a mailing list hosted on Google Groups, <https://groups.google.com/g/atlas-vildehaye-users/>. It is best to send requests for support, as well as suggestions and comments, to the mailing list. The developers monitor it regularly. Users can assist each other and answer queries as well; you are most welcome to answer questions that come up if you know the answers. If you feel that your question has not been addressed reasonably quickly, feel free to write directly to the developers.

After the initial deployment of a system, people within the group running the system can often answer the questions that new users have. But if a question cannot be answered within the group, ask it in the mailing list.

1.6 Data Collection

As part of our efforts to study and improve the technology, we automatically collect data from all ATLAS and Vildehaye systems. That is, data from all ATLAS and Vildehaye systems is sent to the developers.

The data that we collect is limited to technical summaries; it is not at a level of detail that is meaningful in terms of wildlife tracking.

In particular, we collect summaries of which base stations and servers are active and which tags they detect and localize. The temporal resolution of these summaries is one hour or longer.

1.7 Frequencies

ATLAS and Vildehaye are radio systems. Operating radio equipment sometimes requires a license.

We currently produce equipment for one frequency band, the 434 MHz band, in which radios can be operated without a license in most of the world. Some of the equipment can operate outside the license-free band, but not very far; for example, Vildehaye tags work well from about 425 MHz to about 510 MHz. We also have tags that operate on the 868 and 915 MHz bands.

However, both tags and base station equipment can be adapted to other frequencies, from at least 166 MHz (and probably down to 150 MHz) up to 2.4 GHz. For some frequency band (especially other license-free bands) the adaptation is simple and only requires manufacturing the equipment with different components. For other bands, the adaptation requires finding appropriate component values. In all cases, such adaptation requires testing, to ensure the modified tags and base stations perform as they should.

Users and administrators of ATLAS and Vildehaye systems are responsible for ensuring that they operate the equipment legally, whether or not this requires a license.

1.8 Notation

File names and textual input and output to software is printed in this manual in a monospaced font. Long commands that should be entered on a single line in a terminal window or file are broken in this manual. A special arrow marks continuation lines (chunks of text that were broken into separate lines in the manual, but that are really continuations of the previous lines):

```
This text should be entered as a single line, but it is very long so in this
  ↪ manual it is broken; note the special arrow that marks continuation lines.
```

In Linux scripts, long lines can be broken for readability by placing a backslash (\) at the end of the broken line (there must not be any spaces following the backslash):

```
This text should be entered as a single \
line, but it is very long so in this \
manual it is broken; note the special \
arrow that marks continuation lines.
```

In windows batch files (.bat extension), a hat or circumflex symbol marks the end of a broken line:

This text should be entered as a single ^
line, but it is very long so in this ^
manual it is broken; note the special ^
arrow that marks continuation lines.

When commands or input data contains parameters, are sometimes printed in a slanted font, to emphasize that you need to replace the parameters shown with parameters that are appropriate for your situation. Ellipsis (...) designate text that is omitted. In the following example, you are expected to replace *systemname* with the name of a specific ATLAS system, say hula:

```
~/atlas.sh connect-to system=systemname
```

The manual often refers to files and to paths (locations of files). Under Windows, components of paths are separated by backslashes, as in

```
C:\Users\username\.atlas
```

whereas under Linux, components of paths are separated by slashes,

```
/home/username/.atlas
```

1.9 Literature

This section lists some of the technical literature that describes ATLAS and Vildehaye, as well as ecological literature that relies on ATLAS and Vildehaye data. The lists are not necessarily complete.

Overview Articles

Localization Algorithms and Assessments of Accuracy

Post-Processing and Visualization Techniques for ATLAS Localizations

Tags and Tag Batteries

RF Hardware

Signal Design and Signal Processing

Ecology Research Articles that Use ATLAS Tracking

Chapter 2

The ATLAS Web Application

Figure 2.1: Screenshots of the ATLAS web application on a smartphone. The screenshots show the realtime map view with the default Open Street Maps background (left, provided by <https://www.openstreetmap.org>) and with the CartoDB Light background (right, provided by <https://www.carto.com>).

The simplest way to interact with an ATLAS system is through the ATLAS web application at <https://www.cs.tau.ac.il/~stoledo/atlas>. It provides a realtime map of

Figure 2.2: The home screen and the settings screen of the web application.

tag locations, as shown in Figure 2.1, a table showing which basestation receives which tag, and graphs that show the performance of the system. The application works pretty much the same on smartphones, tablets, and laptops and desktops.

From the application’s home screen, shown in Figure 2.2, go to the settings screen and choose a system that you would like to connect to and the particular server that you would like to connect to. When you switch to the map, detections table, or graphs view, the application tries to connect to the server. If this is the first time that you connect to that particular system, the server will ask you to log in. The server identifies and authenticates users using their Google accounts, either personal accounts (e.g., `first.last@gmail.com`) or institutional accounts (e.g., `someuser@mail.tau.ac.il`). The administrator of the ATLAS system that you connect to should add your Google account to a configuration file, `permissions.txt`. The server re-reads this file automatically if it cannot recognize a user, so there is no need to restart the server.

The application runs in a browser and to connect, the browser must identify the ATLAS server. In most cases this happens automatically, so once you log in, the application presents data from the server. If the browser fails to identify the server (or if it cannot reach it, say because the server is down), it shows an error message like the one shown

Figure 2.3: A screen that alerts the user that the application cannot securely connect with the browser, and a screen that the browser shows when the user clicks on the link when the application can reach the server but cannot authenticate it.

in Figure 2.3 (left). If you click on the link provided and if the browser can reach the server but cannot securely identify it, it shows a warning message like the one shown in Figure 2.3 (left). This can happen if the server does not have an appropriate certificate that the browser trusts. If this is indeed the case, you can click on “Advanced”, reach another warning screen like the one shown in Figure 2.4 (left). If you click “Proceed” in this screen, the application will accept the server’s certificate even though it was not able to authenticate it, and will show the message from the server shown in Figure 2.4 (right). Now click on the “back” button of the browser and you should see the application screen you tried to reach. In some cases, after you click “Proceed”, the browser will offer to store the certificate that the server presents; you can ignore the offer (click “Cancel” or refuse to install the certificate).

The detections-table view, shown in Figure 2.5 shows which tag is detected by which base station, and also when each tag was last detected and last localized. Green cells indicate that the tag was detected recently by the base station; the number indicates the signal to noise ratio (SNR); higher numbers indicate better reception. Orange cells

Figure 2.4: A screen allowing the user to connect to a server that the application cannot authenticate, and the web page that the server shows after the user clicks on “Proceed”.

	Last Det	Last Loc	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	10	11	12
		Gain	-19	NaN	-27	-15	-29	-22	-16	-15	-32	-25
972006000003	0s	31s	4.5	2.7	4.3	4.2	3.9	3.8	3.9	4.6	-0.1	
972006000004	0s	31s	4.6	-4.8	-4.1	4.5	4.5	2.1	4.4	-4.6	-2.3	
972006000019	5s	38s		3.2	-16.4	-21.6	3.9		0.4	-4.4		
972006000020	0s	32s			-10.0	-1.6						
972006000026	2s	34s		-4.2	-4.2	0.8	3.2	-11.7	-4.9	-6.6		
972006000027	1s	34s	3.3		0.8	-3.4		-3.6	-20.0	-2.3	-7.4	
972006000028	3s	32s	-6.8		-16.3	-5.5		-19.1	-0.4	-19.9	-12.0	
972006000035	2s	31s	-18.7		-21.3	-12.8		-17.9	-21.9	1.1	-19.3	
972006000036	0s		-19.5							0.2		
972006000047	4s				3.2					-9.4	-0.7	
972006000048	2s				3.2					-9.9	-10.1	
972006000049	3s	35s			2.6		-19.6			-17.3	-16.1	
972006000052	2s	34s					-12.6	2.0		-8.7	-3.0	
972006000062	1s	33s						-5.8		-3.8	-3.3	
972006000090			-17.6		3.9							
972006000152	3s	35s	0.8		-10.7	-14.7			-14.9	-14.4		
972006000153	5s	53s						-1.9			2.6	

Figure 2.5: The detections table view of the web application, this time from a laptop.

Figure 2.6: Graphs showing the coverage (processing performance) of base stations (left) and the level of noise and interference (right).

indicate that the base station is trying to detect the tag but has not detected it recently. Red cells indicate that the base station is not even trying to detect the tag. The red column in the figure, that of base station 2, is probably due to the base station being off line and not reporting at all to the server.

The graphs view shows a series of graphs that allow administrators of ATLAS systems to monitor the performance of the system. They are not particularly helpful for end users. The top one shows the *tracking coverage* of each base station. Coverage of 100% means that the base station succeeds in tracking all the tags that it can hear. If you configure a system to track too many tags, coverage may drop; this is not good and should be corrected using one of several strategies described later in the guide. The dips we see in the graph are probably due to base stations that restarted, so they failed to track tags during the restart period. The next graph shows the *searching coverage*. Here 100% means that the base station is searching for tags that it cannot hear in 100% or the radio samples; 50% means that it only manages to search in 50% of the samples, so on average, once a tag starts transmitting (or gets within reception range), the base station will detect its second transmission. Searching coverage of 50% or even lower is not a significant problem; it only implies that it takes a few transmissions to detect a tag.

The next graphs on this page show the level of noise and interference in different base stations. An ATLAS system can be configured to monitor this metric on several channels, both channels that are in use in the system and channels that are not. These graphs allow you to determine that certain base stations suffer from a local interfering transmitter, that there is strong interference at certain time of the day, and so on.

Chapter 3

Kamadadta

Kamadata is an extensible open-source tool for visualizing and analyzing wildlife tracking data. It was written primarily to enable convenient interaction with data produced by the ATLAS system, but it is perfectly usable for other types of data. ATLAS produces large amounts of data (sometimes millions of localizations per individual at rates of 1-0.1 Hz), so Kamadata is optimized to query, process, and display large numbers of localizations.

We recommend that you watch two short videos showing how to use Kamadata [[KamadataVideo2016](#) [KamadataTransformationsVideo2016](#)] before you start using it. The videos are a bit old, so the user interface is now slightly different, but not by much.

3.1 Installing and Updating Kamadata

On Windows: direct a browser to: <https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/kamadata/get-kamadata.zip>. The server will ask for a username and password, which are `opensource` and `kamadata`. The browser will download a zip file. Extract the contents into a directory in which you want to install Kamadata, say `c:\programs\kamadata`. Open a command shell, `cd` to that directory, and run `update.bat`. This will download Kamadata. You can now run Kamadata by running `kamadata.bat` in the same directory, from the command line (recommended) or by clicking on it. To update to a newer version of Kamadata, simply run `update.bat` again.

On Linux, you can do exactly the same, but download `update.sh`, not `get-kamadata.zip`, and after downloading it, change its permissions to 755 (`chmod 755 update.sh`). The rest is the same. You can also download the `update.sh` script from the command line using a utility called `wget`:

```
wget https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/kamadata/update.sh --http-user=
  ↪  opensource --http-password=kamadata --no-check-certificate
chmod 755
update.sh
./update.sh
```

To run kamadata, just run `./kamadata.sh` in the same directory.

If you report a problem with Kamadata, the developers may ask you to test an experimental version of the software in order to help diagnose the problem or to verify that it has been corrected. To do that, run `update.bat experimental` or `update.sh experimental`. After the testing is concluded, update again (with no arguments) to retrieve a stable version.

3.2 Using Kamadata to Access ATLAS Data

When you use Kamadata to visualize ATLAS data, you will be asked for a number of passwords (and sometimes user names). One is for the keystore file that contains encryption keys that allow Kamadata to connect to ATLAS servers to display real-time data. The user name is `hula-keys` and you should get the password separately.

There are also user names and passwords for the file that contains the list of ATLAS systems and for the configuration files of various atlas systems. Finally, if you connect to ATLAS databases, they require user names and passwords.

The program knows about many ATLAS systems but will only display menu items for systems, databases, and servers for which it is configured. To add systems, databases, and servers, use the *Settings* panel. Changes take effect only after you restart the program. The settings are stored in the `.kamadata` file in your home directory `c:\users\username\.kamadata`:

```
use-atlas-system.hula
use-atlas-database.hula.amazon_db
use-atlas-server.hula.amazon
use-atlas-server.hula.primary
```

Chapter 4

ATLAS Software Installation

ATLAS and Vildehaye share a lot of software components, so the software for base stations and servers of the two systems is distributed together. We use the term *ATLAS software* to refer to software for both systems.

4.1 An Overview of ATLAS Software and Configuration

A computer that runs ATLAS software requires two sets of files. One set of files contains the **software** itself. The second set contains **configuration data** for a particular ATLAS **system**, such as the Hula-valley system, a test setup, etc.

Normally, the computer stores only one set of software files. (It is possible to store multiple copies of the software, for example to store two different versions while upgrading.)

A single computer can store several sets of configuration files in different directories. If there are several sets, they may all configure the software to the same system (for example, to run two ATLAS programs concurrently), or to different systems.

Installing ATLAS involves at least two steps. In the first step, you run a script that downloads the ATLAS software from a web server. In the second step, you run a script that downloads the configuration files for a particular system. If the computer needs to run the ATLAS software continuously and/or to control radio receivers, additional installation steps are required.

ATLAS normally updates the configuration files automatically every time it runs. Therefore, you do not need to download them again manually. ATLAS does not update the software automatically. If you want or need to upgrade to a new version, you must run the software-download script again.

If you only need to view and process ATLAS data, you do not need to install ATLAS; you need to install **Kamadata**, a visual tool that provides access to ATLAS data. Kamadata downloads all the configuration files that are required to access ATLAS data; it may ask you for a user name and/or password for certain configuration files.

4.2 Notes on Linux Installation for Base stations and Servers

If you are installing ATLAS on base stations or servers (in general, computers that run ATLAS around the clock, mostly unattended and possibly at a remote location), please read this section. If you are installing software on a laptop or desktop that you have continuous access to, you can skip this section.

We normally run ATLAS servers and base stations on Ubuntu Linux, usually using a long-time-support (LTS) version, and we recommend that you do the same. If you use another Linux distribution, you may need to adjust the procedures listed below.

We currently only support 64-bit on Intel architectures (on both Windows and Linux), as well as 32-bit ARM architecture on Raspberry Pis (which are too weak for ATLAS base stations). You can run `arch` on Linux to determine the architecture; it needs to respond `x86_64` or `armv7l`.

We also suggest that you name the base station computers `atlas-systemname-01`, `atlas-systemname-` and so on, where `systemname` stands for the name of the ATLAS system (e.g., `hula`). Also, we suggest that you use the same user name (preferably `atlas`) on all the base stations and on ATLAS's server(s); that is, all the base stations should have a user with the same name, and ATLAS programs will run under the identity of this user. These choices will simplify the deployment of the simple VPN that we use to connect to remote base stations, and it will also simplify starting up base stations and servers automatically.

4.3 Install Java

ATLAS and Kamadata are written (mostly) in a programming language called Java. You need to install Java to run the software. A recent version of the open-source Java distribution called `openjdk` is fine. Under Linux (Ubuntu), install using `sudo apt install default-jdk`. Under Windows, download an insaller from <https://openjdk.java.net>.

4.4 Installing ATLAS

Installing ATLAS is required for running the ATLAS base station software (either in an infrastructure base station or in an ad-hoc base station that is used to home in on tags or to check that tags operate before they are deployed), the ATLAS server software, the command-line query tool, and for preparing tags. If you only need to access ATLAS from a graphical user interface, you can use Kamadata and you do not need to install ATLAS.

Decide where to install ATLAS. After the installation, the directory will contain a few files (not too many) and subdirectories. I will assume in the rest of the document that the installation directory is `c:\programs\atlas`. Under Linux, we typically install ATLAS in the home directory `~` or in `~/atlas`.

To download ATLAS, you will need a username and a password. The username is distribution and the password will be provided separately.

Open a command window and `cd` to the installation directory.

Under Linux, download the installation script from <https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/packages/update.sh>, allow the operating system to execute it, and then run it:

```
wget --http-user=distribution --http-password=password https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/
  ↪ projects/atlas/packages/update.sh
chmod 700          allow execution
./update.sh stable execute to download the rest of ATLAS
```

Under Windows, download <https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/packages/getit.zip>, unpack it, and then execute the installation script. In a command shell (cmd.exe) run the following commands:

```
curl https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/packages/getit.zip --user
  ↪ distribution:password --output getit.zip
unzip getit.zip
update.bat stable
```

You can also download `getit.zip` using a browser and you can unpack it using Windows explorer.

If you report a problem with ATLAS, the developers may ask you to test an experimental version of the software in order to help diagnose the problem or to verify that it has been corrected. To do that, run the update script with one argument, `experimental`. After the testing is concluded, update again to a stable version.

You only need to download the script once. If you need to update the software, just run `update.sh stable` or `update.bat stable` script in the same directory.

4.5 Additional Software Components for Running the Base-Station Software: Windows

The base station software in ATLAS needs to communicate with radios and to use signal processing software written in C. This requires the installation of a few more pieces of software. This section lists the additional software components that are required under Windows. The software is available on a Dropbox folder.

Right now, just install the software listed below (for the radios you need to use). We'll see how to test the installations later.

- ~~Install the Visual studio 2013 redistributable package (run `vc_redist_2013_x64.exe`).~~ This is required for running ATLAS base station software with any radio.
- To run ATLAS with any model of USRP radio, install UHD, the driver for these radios. Download and install `uhd_3.15.0.0-release_Winx64_VS2019.exe`. You need to give the option `radio=uhd` to the receiver command to use this version of UHD.
- USRP radios that connect to the computer using a USB cable, like the B200 and the B210, require an additional driver. Download and extract the files from

erllc_uhd_winusb_driver.zip. Now connect the radio and when Windows asks for a driver, tell Windows to use the driver from the directory in which you extracted the zip file.

- To use a USRP model N200 or N210 radio, you need to configure the wired Ethernet connection of the computer to a static IP address 192.168.10.10 with mask 255.255.255.0.

On Windows, you can do this from the Network Connections applet in the Control Panel (or run `ncpa.cpl`), right click on the adapter, properties, select IPv4 and click properties again, select the Alternate Configuration tab, change to *User Configured* (rather than *Automatic*) and fill in the address and the mask. Don't fill in other fields. This will cause Windows to use this IP address when it is connected to the radio, but to keep using normal IP addresses when the computer is connected to an Ethernet switch.

- To use a USB-dongle radio based on the RTL2832 chip (a so-called RTL-SDR USB Dongle), you need to configure the driver for it using a program called `zadig.exe` that you need to download (we tested this with version 2.4). Plug the radio in, run `zadig.exe`, select *list all devices* under *options* and unselect *ignore hubs or composite parents*, then choose `libusb-win32` for the device `RTL2838UHIDIR (Composite Parent)`.

4.6 Additional Software Components for Running the Base-Station Software: Linux

The following instructions were tested on Ubuntu 20.04.

We strongly recommend that you install and enable `ssh`, a mechanism that allows you to connect to a remote base station, as well as a utility called `screen` that allows you to run a program interactively in an `ssh` session and to leave it running after the `ssh` session ends. Run:

```
sudo apt install ssh
sudo systemctl enable --now ssh
sudo systemctl status ssh
sudo apt install screen
```

You may need to disable the built-in fire wall or allow it to pass SSH.

Now use `sudo apt install` to install additional packages:

<code>default-jdk</code>	<i>default-jre is probably sufficient</i>
<code>librtlsdr-dev</code>	<i>librtlsdr0 is probably sufficient</i>
<code>libfftw3-dev</code>	<i>libfftw3-bin is probably sufficient</i>
<code>uhd-host</code>	<i>installs libuhd3.15.0</i>
<code>linux-tools-common</code>	<i>probably not strictly necessary</i>
<code>linux-tools-generic</code>	<i>probably not strictly necessary</i>

As installed, ATLAS will not find the UHD library. To fix that, run

```
sudo ln -s /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libuhd.so.3.15.0 /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/
↳ libuhd.so.3.14.1
```

That's it. You should be all set to download and install ATLAS.

If you plan to use an NVIDIA GPU to perform signal processing in a base station, also install the GPU libraries that are required:

```
sudo apt install nvidia-cuda-toolkit
sudo ubuntu-drivers autoinstall
sudo reboot now
```

To test that the driver is installed and being used:

```
atlas@atlas-12:~$ more /proc/driver/nvidia/version
NVRM version: NVIDIA UNIX x86_64 Kernel Module 450.80.02 Wed Sep 23 01:13:39
↳ UTC 2020
```

Run a test program to see if the radio's firmware is good for the driver's version. If you have an N200 with a GPSDO (a GPS-disciplined oscillator), you can use

```
/usr/lib/uhd/uhd/uhd_utils/query_gpsdo_sensors
```

If the radio's firmware is not appropriate for the version of the driver that you installed, the output of the command will tell you how to upgrade the image. Most likely, it will be something like

```
sudo /usr/local/lib/uhd/uhd_utils/uhd_images_downloader.py
/usr/local/lib/uhd/uhd_utils/usrp_n2xx_simple_net_burner --addr="192.168.10.2"
```

The driver tries to run at a high priority level that is normally not allowed. To allow this, add the following line to `/etc/security/limits.conf`:

```
atlas - rtprio 99
```

(you can start the editor using `sudo gedit /etc/security/limits.conf`; you can obviously use other text editors like *nano* or *emacs* instead of *gedit*.)

To use an RTL-SDR radio, you need to tell Linux to not use it as a television tuner. Add the following line to `/etc/modprobe.d/blacklist.conf`:

```
blacklist dvb_usb_rtl28xxu
```

(You can also remove the TV driver in an ad-hoc manner using the command:

```
sudo rmmod dvb_usb_rtl28xxu
```

However, if you do this rather than blacklisting the TV driver, Linux will reload the TV driver again the next time you plug in the radio).

Vildehaye base stations use a radio connected to the computer with serial port. If you get an error message telling you that you do not have enough permissions to access the serial port, tell Linux to allow your user access to serial ports:

```
sudo usermod -a -G dialout username
```

Chapter 5

The ATLAS Command-Line Interface

Many ATLAS and Vildehaye functions are exposed through a command line interface. The interface allows you to invoke *an ATLAS command* and to give it *options*. You invoke a command by running the `atlas.sh` or `atlas.bat` script. The following examples invoke the `connect-to` command (we'll explain what it does in the next chapter). In Windows, run the following in a shell (`cmd.exe`):

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat connect-to system=hula
```

In Linux, run

```
~/atlas-distribution/atlas.sh connect-to system=hula
```

The `atlas.sh` and `atlas.bat` scripts are stored in the `atlas-distribution` directory that is in the directory in which you ran `update.sh` or `update.bat`. The bold part of the paths above represents the directory in which you ran `update.sh` or `update.bat`. Other than the name of the directory, the path separator (`/` in Linux and `\` in Windows), and the `sh` or `bat` suffix, the commands under Windows and Linux are exactly the same. In the rest of the manual we give only one form of each command, usually the Windows form for interactive commands and the Linux form for commands intended for unattended base stations and servers.

The name of the ATLAS command, here `connect-to`, appears first after the name of the script (there are additional ways to specify the command that we'll cover later). The other strings on the command line are options. Here we have one option, `system`, and we assign a value to it, `hula`. More complex commands require multiple options.

Some options, like `system` here, have a string value, some have a numerical value, some have a boolean value (true or false), and some take multiple string or numerical values, separated by commas. Here is a more complex example:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat query system=hula localize input=  
  → objects:dets.objects output=locs.objects tags=972001000123,972001000234,  
  → 972001000345
```

We invoke the `query` command with five options. Three of them take string values, one takes a list of numbers (`tags`), and one is boolean (`localize`). The value of boolean options is true if they appear with no value or with the value `true` and false if they are missing or appear with the value `false`.

5.1 Getting Feedback and Getting Help

If you misspell a command or give a command that does not exist, you will get an error message:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat no-such-command
...
Command <no-such-command> not recognized
```

If you misspell an option or give a one that the command does not recognize, you will also get an error message:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat connect-to localize
...
Option <localize> not recognized
```

Note that `localize` is not recognized by this command, `connect-to`, even though it is recognized by another command, `query`.

You will also usually get clear error messages if you omit a required option (one that the command cannot function without) or if the format of an option is incorrect:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat coordinates system=hula from-lat-
↳ lon=32,not-a-number
...
Value not-a-number given to option "from-lat-lon" cannot be parsed as a number
```

You can get a list of most of the ATLAS commands using the `help` command¹:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat help
...
atlas-basestation    run an ATLAS receiver (base station); same as "receiver"
connect-to          connect to an ATLAS system
coordinates          transform a lat-lon to metric easting-northing and vice
↳ versa
...
help                prints this help message
invalidate           invalidate a range of hours in the database so they get
↳ recomputed
...
query               query or transform ATLAS data and optionally compute
↳ localizations
receiver            run an ATLAS receiver (base station)
sdcard              format and read a Vildehaye SD card
sensorlog-image     extract sensor data from a Vildehaye NOR flash image file
sensorlog-query     extract sensor data from a database
sensorlog-sensors-conf add the sensors configuration of a tag to vildehaye.sqlite
server              run an ATLAS server
...
vh-program          program a Vildehaye tag, base station, etc
```

You can usually² also get a list of all the options that a given command recognizes:

¹Eventually the list should be complete, but as of January 2022 there are some minor commands that do not appear in this help message.

²Same here, eventually all commands should respond to the `help` option.

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat coordinates help
...
OPTION                EXPLANATION
-----
system                ATLAS system name
from-lat-lon          latitude,longitude (real values)
to-lat-lon            easting,northing   (real values)
```

5.2 Specifying Commands and Options in a file

If you use complex commands repeatedly or you would like to document a particular command, you can specify all or some of the options of a command in a file. You can even specify the command itself in a file. Consider, for example, the following command, which transforms latitude and longitude into easting and northing coordinates in some projected coordinate system:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat coordinates system=hula from-lat-
↳ lon=32.5,35.7
...
266021.580, 711865.473
```

We can prepare a file, say `coordinates-example.csv` with the following contents

```
from-lat-lon,32.5,35.7
system,hula
```

and invoke exactly the same command by running

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat coordinates options=coordinates-
↳ example.csv
```

We can even specify the command in the file. If we add a row specifying the command to the file,

```
command,coordinates
from-lat-lon,32.5,35.7
system,hula
```

then we can invoke the command as follows:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat options=coordinates-example.csv
```

You can edit files with this comma-separated value structure (csv files) with spreadsheet programs like Excel.

If the same option appears multiply times on the command line or in a file (or both), the values get concatenated into a comma-separated list. For example, we also can specify the tags option in the following command

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat query ... tags=972001000123,
↳ 972001000234,972001000345
```

using three separate options

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat query ... tags=972001000123 tags=  
↪ 972001000234 tags=972001000345
```

or in a file with multiple rows that specify the same option,

```
tags,972001000123,972001000234  
tags,972001000345  
...
```

Chapter 6

Connecting to ATLAS Systems

Most ATLAS software interacts with a specific *ATLAS system*, so the software needs a set of configuration files that describe the particular system. Therefore, the first action you need to perform to interact with a new system is to download its configuration files. After the initial download, ATLAS programs update these files automatically.

In addition, there are several configuration files that are common to all ATLAS systems; these need to be downloaded too.

This chapter explains how to connect to an ATLAS system. Along the way, we also explain the basics of invoking ATLAS commands and interpreting their results.

This chapter assumes that the configuration files for the system you want to connect to already exist; it does not cover the initial creating of these files or how to edit them to modify the configuration of a system.

6.1 Connecting to ATLAS Systems and the Basics of ATLAS Commands

ATLAS systems have names. To connect to an ATLAS system called “hula”, run the command¹:

```
~/atlas-distribution/atlas.sh connect-to system=hula
```

or in Windows:

```
c:\users\username\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat connect-to system=hula
```

The `connect-to` command shown above downloads or refreshes two sets of files. Downloading these files require user names and passwords, and the software will ask you for them. The software stores the user name and password required for each file and it does not prompt for them again once you provided them once. (The software may ask again for the same user name and password if they are reused for multiple files or sets of files).

The first set consists of files that are used by all ATLAS systems. These include

¹In earlier versions of ATLAS, the syntax for this command was `setup hula`, not `connect-to system=hula`; it still works.

- `keystore.jks`; this file contains encryption keys that are used to connect to ATLAS servers.
- `catalog.txt`; this file contains a list of ATLAS systems and the locations in which their configuration files are stored.
- Possibly other configuration files that are common to all ATLAS systems.

The output from this command is quite verbose. Let's go through it.

```
C:\Users\username> \files\atlas\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat connect-to system=
  ↪ hula
...
19:09:25 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Running on Android =
  ↪ false
19:09:25 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Trying to load
  ↪ kestore keystore.jks
19:09:25 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Kestore keystore.jks
  ↪ not found
19:09:25 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Trying to load
  ↪ kestore C:\Users\stoledo\.atlas\keystore.jks
19:09:25 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Kestore C:\Users\
  ↪ stoledo\.atlas\keystore.jks not found
Collecting credentials for keystore
User: username      user input
password: password user input
```

In the last two lines, the software asks you for a user name and a password. Note that before the system asks you to provide a username and password, it tells you what resource they are for; in this case, they are for a resource called “keystore”, which stands for the file `keystore.jks`. Let's inspect the rest of the output.

```
19:09:48 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.HttpCacher - trying to cache C:\
  ↪ Users\stoledo\.atlas\keystore.jks
...
19:09:51 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.Certificates - Loaded kestore C:\
  ↪ Users\stoledo\.atlas\keystore.jks
```

Here the system tells you that it is trying to download (cache) the file using the user name and password that you provides; this is successful, as indicated by the last line. Next, the system downloads `catalog.txt` and another file, `vildehaye-setup.txt`. The software knows the user name and password for them, so it does not prompt for a user name and a password.

```
19:09:51 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.HttpCacher - trying to cache C:\
  ↪ Users\stoledo\.atlas\catalog.txt
19:09:51 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.HttpCacher - HTTP last modified Th
u Jan 12 11:19:56 IST 2017
...
19:09:51 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.HttpCacher - trying to cache C:\Us
ers\stoledo\.atlas\vildehaye-setup.txt
19:09:51 [main] INFO tau.atlas.configuration.HttpCacher - HTTP last modified Th
```

```

u Dec 29 13:04:53 IST 2016
...
Collecting credentials for hula-configuration
User: distribution known by the software
password: password user input

```

In the last 3 lines, the system discovered that it knows the user name for the hula system (the user name is “distribution”) but not the password. So it tells you that the user name for the resource “hula-configuration” is “distribution” and asks you for the password. Once the correct password is given, the software downloads the configuration files for the hula system. The output ends with a brief description of the system’s configuration.

```

ATLAS SYSTEM hula props={timeserver=timeserver.iix.net.il, ...}
database: amazon_db at jdbc:mysql:52.48.90.213/atlas,null,null props=null
database: taucs_db at jdbc:mysql:euler-27.cs.tau.ac.il/atlas,null,null ...
server: amazon- primary at 52.48.90.213:6789 db=amazon_db props={...}
server: MYSQLONTEN- primary at pc-sivan-10.cs.tau.ac.il:5555 db=taucs_db ...
server: primary (primary) at atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il:6789 db=none ...
base station: 3 --> atlas-03 (Gonen)
base station: 1 --> atlas-01 (Einan)
base station: 14 --> atlas-14 (Ram)
base station: 10 --> atlas-10 (Keren Naftali)
base station: 7 --> atlas-07 (Gadot)
base station: 8 --> atlas-08 (Manara)
base station: 9 --> atlas-09 (Yanai)
base station: 2 --> atlas-02 (Neot-Mordehai)
base station: 4 --> atlas-04 (Koah)
beacon: 1001000003
beacon: 1001000001
1472 tags:
215, 1, 214, 213, ...

```

This particular system uses two databases (most systems use one), three servers (most use one), nine base stations, two beacons (tags with known locations), and 1472 tags.

If we inspect the contents of the `.atlas` directory now, we see the following files.

```

C:\Users\username> dir .atlas
02/16/2017 07:25 PM <DIR>      .
02/16/2017 07:25 PM <DIR>      ..
02/16/2017 07:17 PM           898 catalog.txt
02/16/2017 07:25 PM <DIR>      hula
02/16/2017 07:09 PM          85,630 keystore.jks
02/16/2017 07:26 PM           551 passwords.txt
02/16/2017 07:09 PM          1,152 vildehayesetups.txt

```

We see the files `keystore.jks`, `catalog.txt`, and `vildehayesetups.txt` that the software downloaded, a `hula` directory into which it downloaded the configuration files of this particular system, and `passwords.txt`, a file that memorizes user names and passwords. If you want to remove user names and passwords, simply remove the appropriate lines in this file. The `hula` directory contains the main configuration file `atlas.txt` and a few more.

ATLAS programs can use configuration files stored in two different locations. One option is to store configuration files in an arbitrary directory and to tell ATLAS to use them. Normally, in this mode the configuration files are stored in the directory in which you run the ATLAS program. The same directory will also contain the ATLAS log files (under the `logs` subdirectory). You normally use this mode to run server and base station programs that run continuously.

The other option is to let ATLAS store the configuration files in the `.atlas` subdirectory of your home directory, using a separate directory for each system. For example, the configuration files of an ATLAS system named *hula* set up by user named *joe* in windows will be stored in `c:\Users\joe\.atlas\hula`. The directory `.atlas` in the home directory will contain a couple of other files that are shared among all systems.

Before we wrap up this section, take a look at the `logs` sub-directory in the directory in which you ran the command. You will see something like

```
C:\Users\username> dir logs
02/16/2017 07:26 PM <DIR>      .
02/16/2017 07:26 PM <DIR>      ..
02/16/2017 07:25 PM           8,709 atlas-1.log
02/16/2017 07:17 PM           9,066 atlas-2.log
02/16/2017 07:25 PM           8,709 atlas-concise-1.log
02/16/2017 07:17 PM           9,066 atlas-concise-2.log
02/16/2017 07:26 PM           9,185 atlas-concise.log
02/16/2017 07:26 PM           9,185 atlas.log
```

The most important file there is `atlas.log`. This is a text file that contains most of the messages that you saw on the screen. You can inspect it with a text editor like notepad. The file `atlas-concise.log` contains only the most important messages; here it is identical to `atlas.log`, but in other cases it might be smaller and easier to inspect. The files with names that end with `-1` and `-2` are older log files that were renamed.

6.1.1 Setting Up Configuration Files for Unattended Programs

We normally run base station and server programs that run continuously on remote computers in a way that uses system configuration files that are not stored in the `.atlas` directory in the home directory of a user, but in the directory in which we run the program. This avoids potential problems that might arise if two ATLAS programs try to update the same configuration file concurrently. This also allows us to modify configuration files locally, for experimentation and troubleshooting.

To set up the configuration files of the *hula* system in a particular directory, say `~/runs/receiver` (the one in which we usually run the base station program), we go to this directory and run the `setup` command and we tell it where to store the configuration files, and what server or base station these files are for²:

```
cd ~/runs/receiver
~/atlas-distribution/atlas.sh connect-to system=hula server=primary
```

or

²The old syntax for this command is `setup hula .;` under the old syntax, you had to create the `local.txt` file yourself. Again, this still works.

```
~/atlas-distribution/atlas.sh connect-to system=hula basestation=972002001
```

This downloads the necessary files to the current directory, and also creates a file named `local.txt` that specify the name or the server or the index of the base station:

Property,serverId,primary

or

Property,basestationId,972002001

Chapter 7

Editing Configuration Files

Administrators (operators) of ATLAS systems need to edit the configuration files of the ATLAS systems that they manage. This chapter explains how to do that. If you are not responsible for administering an ATLAS system, skip it.

7.1 Checking Out and Committing Configuration Files

ATLAS configuration files are managed using a file-versioning system called Subversion (or SVN). This system stores the master copy of the configuration files. Every time an ATLAS command runs, it checks whether this server has new versions of the configuration files. If the ATLAS command finds that it is missing one of the files or has an old copy of one, it downloads the missing or out-of-date files from the server.

Programs that run in unattended mode also check for new configuration files every few minutes. If they discover new files on the server, they read the updated files and behave according to them. In most cases, the software does this by simply stopping, under the assumption that the script that runs them will restart the program, which will then read the updated files.

You cannot copy directly the files on the server. To modify them, you need to *check out* a working copy to your computer using a subversion client, edit the working copy using a text editor on your computer, and then *commit* the modified files back to the server. Checking-out means retrieving a local copy. Committing means uploading a modified local copy back to the server.

To check out and commit files, you will need a subversion client. On Linux, you can use the command-line interface to Subversion, a command called `svn`. On Windows, you can use the graphical TortoiseSVN client. On both systems, you can use a program called Eclipse, which is normally used to develop software, if you add to it an add-on called Subclipse. We normally use the latter setup. To install Subclipse, select *Eclipse Marketplace* from the *Help* menu and search for Subclipse.

Check out the setup for your system. You will need to give subversion the URL from which to check out the files. The URL of the configuration files is stored in `catalog.txt`. For the Hula setup, the URL of the SVN repositories is `https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/atlas-configuration/hula`.

You only need to check out the directory once, not every time you edit the configuration. When you attempt to check out the files, Subversion will also ask you for a user name and password. The user name and password that you used to access the same configuration files from the ATLAS setup command will not work, because they only grant read access, not read-write access. You will need to obtain a read-write user name and password from the person who manages the entire Subversion repository.

Once you have checked out the files, you can go to the directory in which you checked out the files and edit them using a text editor. If you use Eclipse to manage the files, you can use its built-in text editor.

If configuration files contain errors, ATLAS programs that read them usually crash. This is intentional. If we allowed ATLAS programs to run with faulty files, they might misbehave in complex ways that are hard to detect and diagnose. We prefer that the programs stop and report a failure so that the error in the configuration files can be detected and corrected as soon as possible.

This means that before you commit modified configuration files, you should test them. You do this using the `validate` command, which you must run in the directory that contains the local copy of the files:

```
atlas.bat validate
```

or

```
atlas.sh validate
```

If the files are good, the program will print

```
CONFIGURATION TEST PASSED
```

and if they are not, it will print

```
CONFIGURATION TEST FAILED
```

The `validate` command catches many possible errors, but not all. If the test passes, commit the files. Otherwise, correct the errors.

7.2 Additional Techniques for Effective Management of Configuration Files

Because committing new configuration files causes ATLAS programs on servers and remote base stations to restart, you should minimize the number of times you commit files. If you have several changes to make in one or more files, try to make all the changes in the local copy and to then commit all the modified files at once. Do not commit after every small modification.

The rule that ATLAS programs use to decide when to download a new a configuration file is to download whenever the file is missing or the local copy has an older time stamp than the copy on the server. This means that you can edit these files in `.atlas` or in the directory of an unattended program. If you now run an ATLAS program, it will read the local file and will not download a copy that will overwrite it. This can be helpful for

testing changes, for example on just one base station. To cause the software to load a copy from the server, simply delete the locally modified file(s). There is no way to push the modification to the server from copies that ATLAS programs cached (as opposed to local copies checked out by Subversion).

Subversion stores not only the most recent version of each configuration file, but also all the historical versions, which are called *revisions* in Subversion. You can view old revisions, you can revert to old revisions (replace the newest one by an older one), and you can compare revisions. This is helpful when the current version is badly broken. Actions on old revisions are done using your Subversion client.

The caching of configuration files enables ATLAS base stations to start up and receive tags even when they are disconnected from the internet. They upload detection reports to the server when they can reach it through their network connection.

7.3 Key Structures in Configuration Files

An ATLAS system is represented by one configuration file, which we call the *root* file, whose URL is given in `catalog.txt`. This file can refer to additional files, which in turn can refer to even more files. The root file and all of these referred files are read by every ATLAS program that connects to the given system. We normally break the configuration of an ATLAS system to several files that each describe one aspect of the system. We will give examples below.

Some ATLAS programs read additional files from the same configuration-file directory on the server. These additional files are not referred to from the root file. The most important of these files is `track.txt`, which specifies the set of tags that the system should localize.

A configuration file can contain three types of data. One type is description of *system objects*. System objects represent servers, base stations, databases, tags, and so on. Many system objects represent *properties* of other system objects. System objects can be linked in a hierarchical structure, in which objects have *parents*. Normally the child object will specify some part of the parent object or a property of the parent. Let us examine a few simple examples.

```
AtlasSystem,hula
>,Property,projection,EPSG:2039
>,Property,center_x,257000
>,Property,center_y,780000
>,Property,center_z,70
>,Property,fixed_z,70
>,Property,rxAntenna,RX2
>,Property,rxFrequency,433000000
>,Property,rxSamplerate,8333333.333333
>,Property,primary_server,primary
```

The first line in this example, which comes from `atlas.txt` of the hula system, constructs an object that represents the entire ATLAS system. This object has one parameter, the name of the system, here “hula”. Parameters of objects are separated by commas.

The next lines construct property objects that are children of the first object. The child-parent relationship is represented by the greater-than sign, >. Property objects have two parameters, the name of the property and the value of the property. The properties shown here specify the coordinate system that the hula system uses (EPSG:2039), the center of the region in which it is installed, the height value to use when localizing tags in only two dimensions (`fixed_z`, defined here to be 70 meters above sea level), the default configuration of base-stations' receivers, and the name of the primary server, the one to which base stations send detection reports.

The `AtlasSystem` object must be the last object with no parent in the in the root configuration file. It is typically also the only object with no parent in this file.

Let's look at a few more snippets from the main configuration file of a system.

```
>,Database,amazon_db,jdbc:mysql:52.48.90.35/atlas

>,Server,primary,52.48.90.35,4567,null,amazon_db
>,>,Property,localize,true
>,>,Property,recentActivity,true
>,>,Property,hourlyConsistency,true
>,>,Property,backup,false
>,>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true
```

We define here two more objects, which are children of the `AtlasSystem` object. One is a `Database` object, which tells ATLAS how to connect to a database, and the other is a `Server` object, which describes a server and tells it how to operate. The server object has several property children; we know that they are properties of the server and not of the `AtlasSystem` because their lines start with two greater-than signs.

Configuration files contain two more types of data. One consists of names of additional files that are part of the system's configuration. The root file of the hula system ends with two such lines,

```
include tags.txt
include locations.txt
```

Objects in included files become children of the last object with no parent in the file that included them. That is, objects whose definition does not start with a greater-than sign in `tags.txt` and `locations.txt` will be children of the `AtlasSystem` object. By convention, `tags.txt` contains definition of (first-generation and virtual) tags and `locations.txt` contains definitions of objects with a known location, namely base stations and beacons. The structures in these files are described in subsequent chapters.

The ATLAS base station software also reads another configuration file, `track.txt`, that lists tags that the system needs to track and localize. Its structure is usually very simple. Each line in this file specifies one tag that needs to be tracked. For example:

```
TagTracker, 972001000076
```

7.4 Virtual Tags

The ATLAS base station software has mechanisms to measure both the computational load on base stations and the level of radio interference. These mechanisms are imple-

mented as *virtual tags* that are defined in a configuration file, normally in tags.txt.

These mechanisms require importing tau.atlas.tags.*.

Spectrum-sensing tags are used to monitor the level of interference in the radio spectrum. They provide measurements that quantify the level of interference to ATLAS transmissions; their parameters, especially symbol rate, deviation, and length, must match those of real ATLAS transmissions. The first virtual tag below monitors interference in the ATLAS channel centered at 433.92 MHz (the center of the license-free band). It samples the spectrum every 10 s on average (the two tens on the first line) at random times. The load it places on base stations is similar to that of a tag that transmits every 10 s.

```
Tag, 0, 0, 433920, 1, 10, 10, 433920000, 25000
>,PseudoTagAlwaysDetectedSchedule
>,Property, RANDOM_INTERVAL
>,Transmission, STORED, 0, 0, 10, SRSHA1, 8192, 0, 0, 380859, 999756
```

ATLAS systems should normally define at least one more spectrum-sensing tag, for reference. Below we define a spectrum-sensing tag that at 432MHz; it samples part of the spectrum that is completely disjoint from the license-free band and completely disjoint from the spectrum used by ATLAS tags transmitting at 433.92 MHz. The spectrum it samples, roughly from 431 to 433 MHz, is allocated to radio amateurs and is often very quiet or contains short bursts of energy. It is helpful for comparing the level of interference in the (sometimes noisy) license-free band with the level of interference in quieter parts of the spectrum.

Spectrum-sensing tags should only be defined in parts of the spectrum in which the receive chain (antenna, amplifiers, and filters) is effective.

```
Tag, 0, 0, 432000, 1, 10, 10, 432000000, 25000
>,PseudoTagAlwaysDetectedSchedule
>,Property, RANDOM_INTERVAL
>,Transmission, STORED, 0, 0, 10, SRSHA1, 8192, 0, 0, 380859, 999756
```

Computational-load-sensing tags quantify the fraction of tag transmissions that are successfully processed while a tag is being tracked (that is, when the base station knows when its next transmission will occur). They are defined similarly.

```
Tag, 0, 0, 100, 1, 10, 10, 433920000, 25000
>,PseudoTagAlwaysDetectedSchedule
>,Transmission, STORED, 0, 0, 10, SRSHA1, 8192, 0, 0, 380859, 999756
```

For each virtual tag defined like the ones above, the *ATLAS Performance* view in Kama-data and the graphs view in the web application show a graph with one time series for every base station.

7.5 Detection Decimation

ATLAS base stations normally try to process all the transmissions of a given tag, but they can also process only a fraction of the transmissions. This is useful primarily to reduce the workload (and the amount of data gathered) from tags attached to diurnal

animals at night, and to reduce the workload from nocturnal animals during the day. The rationale is that during times of inactivity, the location rates can drop without reducing the amount of ecologically significant information.

This is done using commands in `track.txt`. The commands follow the command to track a particular tag, and they tell base stations what fraction of the transmissions to process. For example, by adding the lines in red to `track.txt`, we decimate the transmissions of tag 972002000950:

```
...
TagTracker, 1, 4, 108
>,DetectionsDecimator,7,0,Infinity,OfficialSunset,-3600,OfficialSunrise,3600
>,DetectionsDecimator,5,0,Infinity,OfficialSunrise,+3600,OfficialSunset,-3600
```

The first number after the command (7 and 5 in these commands) tell ATLAS what fraction of the transmissions to process. Here we tell ATLAS to process 1 transmission in 7 during the night and 1 in 5 during the day. The next two fields tell ATLAS on what dates the command should be active. Here they are active from 1970 onward. The next four fields define the start and end times of the decimation command. The first line starts one hour (3600 seconds) before sunset and ends one hour after sunrise.

Sunset and sunrise are astronomical events. ATLAS uses a library that can determine the time of four variants of these events, called the *official*, *astronomical*, *nautical*, and *civil* sunset and sunrise. You can look up the definition of these times in Wikipedia.

Chapter 8

Running the Software in Base Stations

8.1 Running the Software in Infrastructure Base stations

In infrastructure base stations, the ATLAS base station program is run using the receiver command with no additional arguments. The fact that the command is invoked with no arguments tells ATLAS that the program runs in unattended mode. It must be executed in a directory with configuration files for some ATLAS system and with a local.txt file that declares the base stations's name. The base station must be defined in the ATLAS system, usually in locations.txt.

To test the setup of such a base station, go to that directory, which we assume is `~/runs/receiver`, and run the receiver command:

```
cd ~/runs/receiver
~/atlas-distribution/atlas.sh receiver
```

When you run the receiver command with radios whose performance improve when you provide a calibration file, the command will check if the configuration file exists (in `~/uhd/cal` on Linux or `%APPDATA%\uhd\cal` on Windows), and if not, will attempt to download it from the calibration subdirectory of the configuration directory of the system on the SVN server. If the calibration file is missing, cannot be downloaded, or has just been downloaded, the software will stop. If it has just downloaded the file, just run it again.

If you press control-C or if the program crashes, the program simply stops. This is not a good behavior in an unattended base station; we want the program to restart if it stops or crashes. To run the program repeatedly even if it crashes, run:

```
~/atlas-distribution/atlas-loop.sh receiver
```

If you now kill the program with control-C, it will restart 10 seconds later.

We want the software to start automatically on infrastructure base stations; we do not want to log in and start it manually. To do that, we tell the operating system to start the program when it finishes booting up, by placing a command like the following one in `/etc/rc.local` (you will need root or sudo privileges to edit this file).

```

/sbin/start-stop-daemon
  --start --background \
  --startas /bin/bash \
  --pidfile /tmp/atlas-receiver-shell.pid --make-pidfile \
  --chuid atlas --chdir /home/atlas/runs/receiver \
  -- \
  /home/atlas/atlas-distribution/atlas-loop.sh receiver

```

Backslashes in Linux script indicate that the logical line (command) does not end here but continues with whatever text is on the next line. So logically, this entire code snippet constitutes one line. On Ubuntu 16.04 and later, the operating system does not automatically run `/etc/rc.local` at startup. To tell it to do so, run the command:

```
systemctl enable rc-local.service
```

The `rc.local` file must include two more lines that configure the Linux kernel to communicate with N200 radios effectively:

```

sysctl -w net.core.rmem_max=50000000
sysctl -w net.core.wmem_max=1048576

```

These commands, along with a few others that are useful in the `rc.local` of base stations, are stored in a template for the `rc.local` file in the `atlas-distribution` directory.

On some computers, the wired Ethernet card has problems communicating reliably with N200 radios. This can sometimes be corrected using the following command in `rc.local` (this should have no harmful effect on computers without this problem):

```
printf '%s\n' 'setpci -s 02:00.0 CAP_EXP+10.b=40' | at now + 2min
```

The command `at`, which we use here to run a command two minutes in the future, that we use here is not automatically available on Ubuntu 16.04 and up (it used to be installed automatically). To install it, run:

```
sudo apt install at
```

Starting up Vildehaye base stations is very similar, but the command is `vh-basestation` command, not `receiver`.

8.2 Automatically Running the Software under Windows

Christine Beardsworth contributed the following step-by-step instructions for creating a task in Windows that will run the base station software automatically. The procedure was developed on Windows 7, but seems to also work on Windows 10.

- Search for and launch the Task Scheduler application.
- Click *Create Task...* on the panel on the right.

Figure 8.1: Defining the action of a Windows task.

- Under the **General** tab, choose a name for your task and check **Run whether user is logged on or not**. Note that using this second option means that there will be no console window (command prompt) prompt to show you what is going on. The task will be hidden so look at the atlas log files to check that it is working. You can also check the box **Do not store password**.
- Under the **Triggers** tab, click **New...** and select **Begin the task on start up** and Click **OK**.
- Under the **Actions** tab, click **New...**, select **Start a program** under **Action**. You can specify the atlas-loop.bat script as the program to run (use its full absolute path), the appropriate argument (e.g., receiver for ATLAS base stations and vh-basestation for Vildehaye base stations), and the directory in which you set up the ATLAS or Vildehaye system for **Start in**.
- Under the **Conditions** tab, you may want to uncheck “Start the task only if the computer is on AC power” (if you want the software to start even if a laptop is powered by its battery).
- Under **Settings** uncheck the box **Stop the task if it runs longer than...** and check the box **Allow task to be run on demand** (this is for testing).
- Click **OK**.
- You can test the task by selecting in the center panel and clicking **Run** in the right-hand side panel. Check the log file. You can then stop it, and restart the computer to test that the task really starts when the computer starts.

Figure 8.2: The Windows Task Scheduler.

8.3 Configuring Base stations

The simplest configuration of a base station in a system includes two objects, one for the base station and another to define its location over a span of time.

```
BaseStation,8,dummy,atlas-08 (Manara)
>,TimedLocation,251270,788928,890,2013-Jun-10 09:00 UTC,Infinity
```

The first line defines the base stations's number (8) and name. The second argument (dummy) is no longer used and its value is ignored. The second line defines a location (easting 251270, northing 788928, 890 above sea level) and a span of time. Dates and times must be formatted exactly as shown here, or as the number of seconds since 1970. The Infinity means that this location is valid indefinitely. The coordinates are Cartesian and metric in the system's projection. It is also possible to specify positions using GPS latitude and longitude. The format is 34.905859@WGS84,31.776450@WGS84 using fractional degrees. If the base station moves, you can add additional TimedLocation objects to record the various positions.

It is important to specify locations accurately. Errors in locations of base stations and beacons generate errors in localizations of tags. The specified location should be that of the receiving antenna of the base station.

Base station objects can have more kinds of children. Here are a few.

```
>,Property,radioJniLibrary,jni-radio-connection-uhd
>,Property,radioHint,serial=EAR04ZABT
>,Property,radioSerial,EAR04ZABT
>,Property,rxAntenna,RX2
>,Property,rxFrequency,434000000
>,Property,rxSamplerate,8000000
```

The first line tells the software which driver to use to connect to the radio. The driver shown here is the default one, so you do not normally need to specify it, but if the radio uses another driver, you need to specify the driver. You can also use a shorthand notation for this property:

```
>,Property,radio,uhd
```

The second line tells the radio driver which radio to open. This is useful if more than one radio is connected to one computer. The next three lines select an antenna port in the radio, the center frequency, and the sampling rate. These lines are also not normally required; when they are not defined here, the radio uses the corresponding default parameters of the system. Specifying them for a given base station is useful mostly if it uses a different radio than the other base stations (e.g., a B200 rather than an N200).

If you need to run a radio that benefits from calibration files (e.g., an N200) but you do not have them, add the `noRadioCalibrationFile` property, to allow the receiver command to run even though the calibration files are missing.

To use a signal processing library that can take advantage of NVIDIA GPUs, add the property:

```
>,Property,dspLibrary,cuda
```

To tell the signal processing library (the one that uses CPU cores, not a GPU) how many cores to use, add the property:

```
>,Property,dspThreas,number
```

8.4 Configuring Remote Base stations to Start Up Automatically after Power Outages

Most computers are configured to stay turned off when AC power is restored after a power outage. This is inappropriate for remote base stations and for servers; we want these computers to start up automatically after a power outage.

Configure the BIOS of the computer to start up automatically after a power outage. Test this by unplugging the computer from AC power and then replugging it. The computer should reboot automatically and it should connect to the internet and start the ATLAS program. If there is a problem, fix it and retest. It is easy when it is in your lab of office and difficult when it is already in the field.

8.5 Setting Up SSH Tunnels through AWS to Enable Logging in to Remote Base stations

You need a way to log on to remote base stations using `ssh` (secure shell) in order to resolve problems and to update their ATLAS software.

Remote base stations are often connected to the internet in a way that does not allow you to log into them even if you know their IP address. They may be behind a firewall or a router or switch that uses NAT.

Figure 8.3: Reverse-tunnel SSH mechanism. The cyan arrows represent MQTT connections, and the orange and gray arrows represent SSH connections.

We provide a simple and secure mechanism to do that. The mechanism allows you to open an SSH (terminal) connection from your laptop or desktop to the base station. The mechanism incurs some costs to a cloud-computing platform, but it appears that these costs are minor so for now I will bear them.

This mechanism, illustrated in Figure 8.3, runs a program on the remote computer (say a base station that) listens for a command from a controlling computer, say your

laptop, to allow incoming connections. You will have a corresponding program on your laptop to instruct the remote computer to start or stop allowing incoming connections. When the remote computer receives a command to allow connections, it opens an SSH connection called a reverse tunnel to a server in the cloud (more specifically, in the Amazon Web Services or AWS cloud). The tunnel is identified on the cloud server by a port number, which is chosen randomly and reported back to your computer. When the program you ran to start the tunnel receives the notification that the tunnel has been created and the port number it uses, it creates a small script called `tunnel.bat` or `tunnel.sh` on your computer. You just run it to connect to the remote computer. After you disconnect, you give a command to stop allowing incoming connections. This frees up the port number and other resources on the cloud server.

To use this mechanism, you need to set up the base station with appropriate security keys and with the program that listens for remote commands, and you need to make sure it runs all the time. In particular, both the base station and the controlling computer (a laptop or desktop) require a *private key* file and a *certificate* in order to send and receive messages through a cloud protocol called MQTT. The key and the certificate are specific to a particular base station and to the control connection of a particular ATLAS system. You need to keep the key files secret. The SSH connections require separate key files. Both base stations and control computers need a *private identity file* to connect to the cloud server. The controlling computer needs a private identity file that is used to connect to all the remote computers of a particular ATLAS system. The remote computer needs the public key file associated with the private identity file in order to recognize legitimate connection requests.

Let us assume that you need to add a base station number 972001333 to the hula ATLAS system, as well as a controlling laptop, and that the user name on both computers is atlas. You need to ask me (an email is fine) to generate a zip file containing all the files required to set up both the remote computer and the controlling computer. There are two ways to generate the unique key associated with each computer: a simple but not very secure way, and a very secure way. We'll start with the simpler way.

A simple (and not completely secure) way to set up SSH tunnels. If you want the installation to be simple, ask me for zip files containing the private keys. The two files will be called `atlas-hula-972001333.zip` and `atlas-hula-controller.zip`. Transfer them to the two computer and unzip them up in some directory in the remote computer, say the home directory. The first will create a sub-directory called `tunnel` and the other a sub-directory called `tunnel-controller`, in both cases with all the required files. Change to that directory and run a command that installs the SSH keys; this command gives some of these files proper permissions and it may also modify `~/.ssh/authorized_keys`, to allow incoming connections. On the base station the commands are:

```
atlas@hula333:~$ unzip atlas-hula-972001333.zip
atlas@hula333:~$ cd tunnel
atlas@hula333:~/tunnel$ java -jar sivantoleado-iot.jar install-keys
```

On the controlling computer the commands are:

```
C:\Users\atlas> unzip atlas-hula-controller.zip
```

```
C:\Users\atlas> cd tunnel-controller
C:\Users\atlas\tunnel-controller> java -jar sivantoledo-iot.jar install-keys
```

Now run on the remote computer the script called `loop.sh`. It is best to run it from `/etc/rc.local` so that it runs every time the remote computer boots. Here we run it from the command line for testing:

```
atlas@hula333:~/tunnel$ ./loop.sh
MQTT starting...
MQTT connecting...
MQTT connected
MQTT subscribing to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/control
MQTT subscribed to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/control
```

Now you can tell the controlling computer to instruct the remote computer to set up an SSH tunnel. You need to specify which base station should establish the tunnel, the user name that you will use to connect to the remote computer, and the SSH secret key file that identifies this user:

```
C:\Users\atlas\tunnel-controller> java -jar sivantoledo-iot.jar connect 972001333
  ↪ atlas id_atlas_hula
MQTT connecting...
MQTT connected
MQTT subscribing to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/state
MQTT subscribed to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/state
>>> atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/control: connect
<<< atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/state: connected|port=39173
!!! remote state consistent, exiting
```

Now simply run the tunnel script; it should establish an SSH connection between the controlling computer and the remote computer.

When you no longer need the tunnel, please disconnect it to free up the port number and other resources:

```
C:\Users\atlas\tunnel-controller> java -jar sivantoledo-iot.jar disconnect
  ↪ 972001333
MQTT connecting...
MQTT connected
MQTT subscribing to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/state
MQTT subscribed to atlas/hula/972001333/tunnel/state
>>> atlas/hula/972001333ry/tunnel/control: disconnect
<<< atlas/hula/primary/tunnel/state: disconnected
!!! remote state consistent, exiting
[detached from 5441.tunnel]
```

You can establish and terminate many SSH connections to the remote computer using the tunnel script before you disconnect.

A more secure way to set up SSH tunnels. A more secure way to set up the SSH tunnels infrastructure is to generate the MQTT secret key on the remote computer itself. This way, this key is never sent between computers so the chances of it being stolen or being leaked are smaller.

To use this method, you need to install the `openssl` package on the remote computer. Start by asking me for a zip file that *does not contain a secret key*. Now unzip the file on the remote computer and then run the request script:

```
atlas@hula333:~$ unzip atlas-hula-972001333.zip
atlas@hula333:~$ cd tunnel
atlas@hula333:~/tunnel$ ./request.sh
```

This generates two files: the secret key file, in this case `atlas-hula-972001333.key`, and a *certificate signing request* file, in this case `atlas-hula-972001333.csr`.

Send me back the `csr` file, which I will use to generate a certificate file and to register it on AWS. I will send you back the certificate (or a new zip containing it), `atlas-hula-972001333.cert.pem`. Put it in the `tunnel` directory (or the `tunnel-controller` directory) and proceed as before.

SSH Keys. The zip files that I distribute contain a secret-key SSH file that allows the remote computer to establish the reverse-SSH tunnel to the server on the cloud. This file is called `id_tunnel`.

The zip files for remote computers also include two public-key SSH files that are copied into `~/.ssh/authorized_keys`. These allow authorized users to connect to the remote computer through SSH, including through the tunnel. One file, `id_atlas_common.pub`, is common to all ATLAS systems and it allows me to easily connect to remote ATLAS computers in order to provide technical assistance. If you do not want or need this functionality, you can delete or rename this file before running `install-keys`. The other file is common to a particular ATLAS system and is intended to allow the controller computer of this system to connect to remote computers.

In the future we may distribute and install SSH keys through the MQTT connection, but right now we use static files that are part of the zip files.

8.6 ~~Setting Up a Simple VPN to Enable Logging in to Remote Base stations~~

~~You need a way to log on to remote base stations using ssh (secure shell) in order to resolve problems and to update their ATLAS software.~~

~~Remote base stations are often connected to the internet in a way that does not allow you to log into them even if you know their IP address. They may be behind a firewall or a router or switch that uses NAT.~~

~~In some cases, it may be possible to configure the switch, router, or firewall to allow ssh access to the base stations, but we have found this to be unreliable, and it is not always possible. The reliability problem stems from the fact that other people may re-configure the router or firewall and remove your forwarding rules. Also, the router or firewall may belong to an Internet provider that does not allow such configuration.~~

~~We normally resolve this by setting up a very simple VPN (virtual private network) that allows ssh access to the base stations. We do this using a mechanism called *ssh reverse tunnel*.~~

In the reverse tunnel mechanism, the base station runs a script that opens an ssh connection to a server with a public ssh address. The ssh connection is configured with a reverse tunnel, which means that on the server side, the connection binds to a TCP port. When an ssh client on the server connects to this port, the tunnel forwards the traffic in this connection to the remote base station.

For the mechanism to work, the remote base station must be able to establish an ssh connection to the server without supplying a password. This requires a pair of matching keys (a public key and a private key). If you do not already have them, generate a pair. *Do not supply a passphrase* (leave it empty).

```
atlas@server:~$ ssh-keygen
Generating public/private rsa key pair.
Enter file in which to save the key (/home/atlas/.ssh/id_rsa):
Enter passphrase (empty for no passphrase):
Enter same passphrase again:
Your identification has been saved in /home/atlas/.ssh/id_rsa.
Your public key has been saved in /home/atlas/.ssh/id_rsa.pub.
The key fingerprint is:
b3:2e:92:09:6d:70:73:52:a5:51:d7:77:b1:ac:bf:a2 atlas@server
```

If we now try to open ssh connections, the ssh client will attempt to use the private key (`id_rsa`) to authenticate you, but if the other side is not configured to accept this key, it will still ask for your password.

```
atlas@server:~$ ssh localhost
The authenticity of host 'localhost (127.0.0.1)' can't be established.
ECDSA key fingerprint is ab:cc:6f:0e:09:10:bb:17:b0:1f:4a:19:1e:6e:b4:f9.
Are you sure you want to continue connecting (yes/no)? yes
Warning: Permanently added 'localhost' (ECDSA) to the list of known hosts.
atlas@localhost's password: password
Welcome to Ubuntu 14.04.4 LTS (GNU/Linux 3.13.0-83-generic x86_64)
...
atlas@server:~$
```

As you can see, the server asked for a password. The ssh client also verified that we really know what server we are connecting to, and stored our reply. If we inspect the content of the directory `~/.ssh` that contains our ssh keys and configuration, we see three files:

```
atlas@server:~$ ls -l ~/.ssh
total 12
-rw----- 1 stoledo stoledo 1679 Feb 17 15:33 id_rsa
-rw-r--r-- 1 stoledo stoledo  401 Feb 17 15:33 id_rsa.pub
-rw-r--r-- 1 stoledo stoledo 3762 Feb 17 15:34 known_hosts
```

Note that the permissions of the private key are read-write for the owner only. If this is not the case, the file is not be used. To allow logging in using the private key and without typing your password, append the public key to `.ssh/authorized_keys`:

```
atlas@server:~$ cat .ssh/id_rsa.pub >> .ssh/authorized_keys
```

If you ssh to localhost now, the connection will be established without asking for your password. If the server still asks for your password, the ssh server program might not be configured to allow access using keys only; set the following parameters to yes in `/etc/ssh/sshd_config`:

```
...
RSAAuthentication yes
PubkeyAuthentication yes
...
```

Now log in to the base station, install the ssh server software, and copy all of these files from the server.

```
atlas@basestation:~$ sudo apt-get install openssh-server
atlas@basestation:~$ scp -r atlas@server:.ssh .
```

Now try to log in using ssh from the base station to the server. The connection should be established without asking you for a password.

If you now issue an ssh connection command that opens a reverse tunnel, you should be able to log in from the server back to the base station through the tunnel. On the base station, the command is:

```
atlas@basestation:~$ ssh -o ServerAliveInterval=60 \
  -4 -N -x \
  -R 63105:localhost:22
```

When you now connect to port 63105 on the server, you should reach the base station:

```
atlas@server:~$ ssh p 63105 localhost
Welcome to Ubuntu 14.04.4 LTS (GNU/Linux 3.13.0-83-generic x86_64)
...
atlas@basestation:~$
```

The atlas-distribution directory contains a script that sets up the tunnel automatically. It uses a port number that is 631xx where xx is the suffix of the host name of the base station. If you use this setup, to connect to a base station called atlas-hula-06 you will need to connect to port 63106. Our template for `/etc/rc.local` invokes this script.

We have been using this setup for several years with no significant difficulties. It appears that sometimes tunnels get stuck in a state that does not allow logging in through them. In this case, killing all the processes of the user that is used for these connections and waiting for the base station to re-establish the connection always works (we use `kill -9 -1` to kill all the processes of the user atlas).

Another potential issue is that the server might allocate the port numbers that we use for other processes. This is not very likely to happen, but if it does, you can configure a kernel parameter on the server that tell it not to allocate automatically port numbers above some number, say 60000.

8.7 Setting up Cellular Connections

When a base station starts up it needs to connect to the Internet. If it uses WiFi or wired Ethernet connections, this is easy to set up. But our experience has been that starting up cellular connections automatically in Ubuntu is not trivial. (Because of that, a WiFi connection to a WiFi cellular hot spot is a good solution; see Section below.

Start by plugging in the cellular modem and configure the network using the Ubuntu menus (Ubuntu uses the term *broadband* to refer to cellular connections).

Once the connection is working, mark it as available to all users and mark it so that it starts up automatically. Also, select “auto login” for the user who runs the ATLAS software. The automatic login starts up the network. Reboot and test that the computer connects to the cellular network automatically.

Before we discovered that “auto login” is required, we used a more complex mechanism to start the network, listed below.

Once the connection is working, configure `/etc/rc.local` to invoke a script that will connect the base station to the Internet. There are templates in `atlas-distribution` for this.

In general, we encountered two problems that our script solves. One is that the USB cellular modems that we use have two USB modes, a modem mode (the one we want the modem to be in, obviously) and a separate storage (disk-on-key) mode which allows the Windows driver of the modem to be distributed in the modem itself. There are two mechanisms to transition the modem from storage mode to modem mode. One is to tell the operating system to disconnect from the storage device (using the `eject` command); some USB modems respond to this by reconnecting as a modem. The other is to send a command to the modem; the `usb_modeswitch` utility in Ubuntu knows how to do this to some modems. You will need to try to get one of these to work with your modems. If you can, try to purchase modems that never go into disk-on-key mode; this eliminates this problem altogether.

The other problem that existed at least until Ubuntu 14.04 is that the cellular network would not start up automatically even if you configure it to do that in the *edit connections* panel. To resolve this, our start up script invokes a command that tells the networking infrastructure in Ubuntu to start up the cellular connection. For Ubuntu 16.04 and later, this command is called `nmcli`, and you start up the network from a script using a command like:

```
/usr/bin/nmcli \  
  con up "Pelephone 3G" \  
  passwd-file /home/atlas/pass3g.txt
```

The last argument is the name of a file that contains the password to connect to the network, which you provide interactively when you start up the connection from a menu.

8.8 Running ATLAS Ad-Hoc Base stations

An ad-hoc base station is a base station that does not report to a server. Instead, the software reports detections of tags to a graphical user interface. They have several purposes:

- To verify that tags transmit, in the lab when they are prepared or in the field prior to deployment.
- To test a radio or a computer before it is deployed in an infrastructure base station.
- To find the direction to a tag using a directional antenna, usually to home-in on the tag to find it (and perhaps the animal to which it is attached); this is easier using a variant setup described in Section 8.9.
- To configure tags via radio; this is possible only using Vildehaye base stations, not using ATLAS base stations; see Section 8.10.

You run ad-hoc base stations using the same commands that are used to run infrastructure base stations (receiver and vh-basestation), but with arguments that tell the base stations what to do, because this information is not present in the configuration files of a system.

This section describes how to run ad-hoc ATLAS base stations; the next one focuses on Vildehaye base stations.

To run an ATLAS receiver with an RTL-SDR receiver, use the command:

```
atlas.bat receiver system=hula radio=rtlsdr
```

The first argument tells the software which driver to use to connect to the radio. You can also specify the driver using alternative syntax that specifies the library more fully:

```
radioJniLibrary=jni-radio-connection-rtlsdr
```

You can specify the center frequency with `rxFrequency=433500000`, but you can also do that from the graphical use interface.

To use a USRP radio (we usually use B200 radios in ad-hoc base stations, but you can also use N200s, especially for testing), replace the second argument with `radio=uhd`. USRP radios can also operate with several sampling rates, so it is helpful to specify the rate you want. For B200s, the rate should be an integer divisor of 8000000, so you can use `rxSamplerate=2000000` or `rxSamplerate=4000000`. If you use a radio with a GPS-disciplined oscillator and the GPS is not locked, use the argument `useGpsClock=false`, otherwise the program will complain that the GPS is not locked and will stop. Running without a GPS lock does not provide accurate enough arrival times for localization, but does not cause any other problem.

The program opens a window like the one shown in Figure 8.4.

The bottom center panel presents a list of tags that the ATLAS system knows about. If you select one of them, the software will start scanning for its transmissions and if the tag can be detected, you will start seeing detections in the left panel. You can select more than one tag and the software should track all of them.

Figure 8.4: The user interface of an ATLAS ad-hoc base station.

The bottom right panel allows you to tune the radio to different frequencies and sampling rates (the range of sampling rates that the software supports is limited; not every value will work).

It takes a few seconds to changes to the frequency/sampling rate and the set of tags that are being tracked; be patient.

The bottom left panel shows a table of tags that the software has has detected. If you select one of the tags, its detections will be shown in the top row of numbers, which give the signal strength (RSSI) of every detection along with the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the headroom (how much stronger the tag could have been without overloading the receiver at the particular gain setting that the program is in), and the gain of the receiver. The gain is normally adjusted automatically but you can lock it by checking the gain box.

Detections are also presented aurally with a beep whose volume and pitch indicate the RSSI. As you turn a directional antenna towards and away from the tag, you should be able to easily hear differences in signal strength and determine the approximate direction to the tag.

The audible RSSI indications are relative to the RSSI of the strongest detection of the tag. When the current detection is stronger than all the recent ones, you will hear a double beep and the range of volume and pitch will readjust. If the headroom is zero, meaning the tag's transmissions are very strong, you will hear a beep with a changing pitch that indicates that the precise RSSI cannot be determined because the receiver is overloaded.

If you run the software using the receiver command and you give a `radio` or `radioJniLibrary` argument, the radio needs to be connected to the computer on which you are running the software, perhaps a laptop. This is not always convenient, so we provide another way to run an ad-hoc ATLAS base station. You can connect the radio to a Raspberry Pi (models 2 or 3; this will not work on first-generation Raspberry Pis). The Raspberry Pi is configured to run a barebones ATLAS receiver program that does not use the configuration files of any particular atlas system. The command to do this is `remote-radio`:

```
atlas.sh remote-radio radio=rtlsdr rxFrequency=433500000
```

Assuming that the Pi is not connected to a keyboard and a display, you need to run this command from `/etc/rc.local` and to invoke `atlas-loop.sh`, not `atlas.sh`.

This command connects to the radio and advertizes its presence over the local networks to which the computer running it (the Pi) is connected. If your laptop is connected to the same network, say a WiFi network, and you run the receiver command without a radio or jniRadioLibrary argument, it will attempt to connect to the radio on the Pi and to use it instead.

If you are using a laptop to interact with the base station, the Pi does not help much, but in the future we will also support the use of Android phones and tablets as interfaces to the base station using the same mechanism.

There are several ways to configure the Pi and the laptop or phone to form a local network. The one we propose is to configure a WiFi network connection on the Pi that is set up as a hotspot (this is possible in Ubuntu 16.04 and up). This network connection should be configured to start up automatically. When the Pi is running, you should be able to connect to this network from your laptop or phone.

8.9 ATLAS Ad-Hoc Base Stations with a Web App Interface

To find a tag in the field by repeatedly estimating the location to it, it is easier to run the ad-hoc base station software on a small computer with no keyboard or monitor (this is referred to as a *headless* configuration) and to use a smartphone as the user interface. The software running on the smartphone is simply the web app described in Chapter 2.

The rest of the discussion assumes that the base station is running on a Raspberry Pi and that the web app is running on a smart phone. We also assume that the WiFi hotspot feature (tethering) is active on the smart phone, exposing a WiFi hot spot called *atlas-tether* and that the Pi is configured to automatically connect to this hot spot. During testing, it's best to connect a keyboard and a monitor to the Raspberry Pi. When running headless, it is best to connect a small OLED display that the base station uses to display its IP address and its status, as shown in Figure 8.5. We describe the physical connections later. In the absence of an OLED display, you can determine the IP address of the Raspberry Pi using a network scanning application like *Network Analyzer Pro*.

To allow the web app to access and control the base station, run the base station without a system parameter; e.g.,

```
atlas-loop.sh receiver radio=rtlsdr rxGain=0
```

To run headless, run this command from `/etc/rc.local`, as in infrastructure base stations. The web app can also shut down the Raspberry Pi, and if you want to use this feature, run the software from `/etc/rc.local` under the user *root*, not under the user *atlas* (that is, without the `chuid` option).

We also have a Raspberry Pi image that is already set up to run the ATLAS receiver software. To install it, download the image file, run the Raspberry Pi Imager program (it is available for Windows, Linux, and macOS), choose *custom* in the operating-system menu, select the image file you downloaded, and write the SD card. The image should work with cards of 8 GB and up. The URL for the image file is <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ldgA1ukGIyY6GfJA0gkwgz5-hzLDEJgr/view?usp=sharing>.

Figure 8.5: A headless Raspberry Pi with an OLED display showing its IP address and the status of the base station software (left), and the *Network Analyzer Pro* smartphone application showing the IP address of a tethered Raspberry Pi.

Because the base station software is run without any system option, it does not connect to any system and does not need to update the configuration files of any system. This implies that you do not need to update the Raspberry Pi or to connect it to the Internet (except if you need to update the ATLAS software).

To connect to the base station, run the web app and select the radar-like icon in the top bar. Go to the radio panel and enter the IP address of the Raspberry Pi, as shown in Figure 8.6. You may see a screen saying that the browser has trouble connecting to the service, perhaps a security issue. Click on the link and allow the browser to connect. You will see a message from the radio's embedded web server. Click *back* you should see the web app connected to the radio, with the frequency and sampling rate set, as shown in the rightmost screenshot in Figure 8.6. The *SET* button allows you to change the frequency or sampling rate, the *RESTART* button to restart the base station software (not the entire Raspberry Pi), and the *SHUTDOWN* button allows you to cleanly shut down the Raspberry Pi before you disconnect it from power.

Now go to the Detections panel and enter a tag number, as shown in Figure 8.7. The number shows up in red if the web app does not recognize it, or in green if it does. Once the number is recognized (give it a second or two to check) and shown in green, you can add it to the list of tracked tags. It will be added to the list on top, with a red square denoting that it was not detected recently. Once it is detected, the square changes to green and will show the last detection's RSSI. Tag that you add are muted, but if you unmute a tag, the web app will beep when the tag is received with a beep that indicates

Figure 8.6: Connecting to a radio on a Raspberry Pi.

Figure 8.7: Adding a tag to be tracked by an ad-hoc base station in the web app.

the RSSI. To reset the scale of the audible indications, click on the down-pointing arrow icon.

When entering tag numbers that are defined in the system that is currently selected in the web app (in the Settings screen), you can enter only the last 6 digits of the tag number, omitting leading zeros. So to enter tag number 972001007144, you can enter just 7144, as shown in Figure 8.7. The full number 972001007144 also works, of course. To enter the number of a tag defined in another system (that you were connected to previously in the same browser), enter the full number.

The web app gets the information required to detect tags from ATLAS servers. To detect a tag defined in the hula system, say, you need to connect at some point to a server of the system (select the system from the Settings panel, etc). The web app caches this information in the browser indefinitely, so it does not need to be connected to the server to detect tags.

The web app is defined as a so-called *Progressive Web App*, which means that the browser should offer you to install it locally, on your computer or phone. This allows you to use it as an ad-hoc base station even in locations with no Internet access.

The OLED display must be have an SSD1306 controller chip and it must be possible to attach it to the Raspberry Pi using an I2C interface. Connect the 3.3V pin of the OLED display to pin 1 of the Pi, GND to pin 6 (or 20 or several others, but 6 is convenient), SCL to pin 5, and SDA to pin 3. You can get these OLED display from many sellers on ebay and similar online marketplaces, as well as from Adafruit and Sparkfun.

You also need to enable I2C communication in the Raspberry Pi through the `raspi-config` command (under *interfacing*).

8.10 Running Vildehaye Ad-Hoc Base Stations

Running ad-hoc Vildehaye base stations is similar. The radio is simply a tag connected to the computer or the phone using a USB-to-serial bridge. The only argument to the `vh-basestation` command is typically the identity of the serial port, for example:

```
atlas.bat vh-basestation serialPort=COM8
```

In Windows, you can also specify the serial port using a part of the string that describes the serial port in the Windows Device Manager. For example:

```
atlas.bat vh-basestation serialPort=App@Windows
```

The command opens a graphical user interface, shown in Figure 8.4, that is similar to the one used in ATLAS ad-hoc base stations. The top panel only shows RSSI values; the radio does not provide SNR, headroom, and gain information. The bottom left panel still shows a table of detections. The bottom center panel shows a list of *radio setups* that you can choose (only one at a time). A radio setup defines a frequency, data rate, and other parameters of the transmission of tags.

In the table of tag detections on the left, column 1 shows the tag number (here 972002000095), column 2 shows an *intent*, which we explain below, column 3 shows the current configuration of the tag (here 1), and column 4 shows the RSSI of the last detection.

Figure 8.8: A Vildehaye ad-hoc base station running on a laptop. On the left we see a detection of the tag, and on the right the menu of wake-up intents that can be used to transition the tag to a new configuration.

The *intent* defines the interaction of the base station with the tag. When the tag is first detected, this column is blank. If you click on it, a small window opens. Here we selected WU1 (wake-up-1) from the menu. Wake-up intents try to move the tag to the selected configuration; wake-up 1 tries to move the tag to configuration 1. Here the configuration is already 1, so the base station will not respond to the tag. When we just powered up the tag, it was in configuration 0. We selected intent WU1; The next time the tag transmitted its identification number and indicated that it is in configuration 0, the base station transmitted a wake-up command to the tag. This caused it to transition to configuration 1, and in this case, to start transmitting an ATLAS code every second. You can transition the tag back to configuration 0 using the WU1 intent.

Chapter 9

Servers

9.1 The Functions and Types of Servers

ATLAS systems run a server program to perform the following functions:

- The server collects reports from base stations. Most of the reports are of detections of tags, but there are additional types of reports, such as reports that a base station is searching for a tag but not hearing it.
- The server computes localizations of tags from detection reports by 3 or more base stations.
- The server stores both detection reports and localizations in a database for later retrieval and analysis.
- The server passes the reports and localizations to client programs for real-time display, and potentially to other servers (the uses of this will be clarified below).
- The server informs base stations that do not hear a particular tag when it is transmitting, if other base stations do hear it. This helps base stations detect tags with weak signals. We refer to these notifications as *assists*.

Servers should be running most of the time, but it is not critical that they run all the time. When a server is not running, base stations accumulate reports in a file. Base stations also store these reports when they are not connected to the Internet and cannot therefore reach the server. When the connection between the base station and the server is reestablished, the base station uploads all the reports it has accumulated. Similarly, if a server is configured to send data to a *downstream* server and the downstream server is down or not reachable, the upstream server will accumulate all the data destined for the downstream server in a file and will upload it when the connection is reestablished.

Every ATLAS system has one *primary server*, the one to which base stations send reports. When this server is down, it does not send assist notifications to base stations; this may reduce the number of detections and hence the number and/or quality of localizations. This is the only permanent effect of a server being down in an ATLAS system.

A simple ATLAS system can use a single server that performs all the functions listed above. A more complex system can use multiple servers, on the same computer or

on multiple computers, to share the load among them. For example, we can set up a primary server that only collects reports and a downstream server that computes localizations, stores data in a database, and sends reports and localizations to real-time clients. This way, the primary server can continue to send assists to base stations even when the database and main server are down for backup.

9.2 Running and Configuring Servers

To run a server, set up configuration files in a directory (we usually use `~/runs/server` on computers that run a single server program), specify the name of the server in `local.txt`, and run it using the server command with no arguments.

If the server stores data in a database, it will need the user name and password to access the database. If these are not already stored in `~/atlas/passwords.txt`, it will prompt for them. You can use the `login-db` command once to perform just this step (database authentication); this is useful because the prompt for the user name and/or password can be hard to notice when the server program is starting up.

Servers that compute localizations and store data in a database require a large amount of memory (we had problems on a computer with 4 GB of RAM). The best way to avoid this is to run servers on computers with at least 8 GB of RAM, preferably 16 GB or more. The other remedy is to tell Java how to use memory; there are arguments to the Java Virtual Machine (JVM, the software that runs Java programs like ATLAS servers) that specify this. If you place such arguments in a file called `javaargs.txt` in the directory in which you run the server, the `atlas.sh` script will read this file and will supply the arguments to Java. The argument that is potentially the most useful is the one that tells Java how much memory to use: `-Xmx7g` tells Java to use 7 GB of RAM, for example. Our experience has been that Java does not follow this instruction exactly, but that it can be helpful in controlling the amount of memory that the server uses.

The problem that we experienced on the computer with the small memory was not that the server crashed, but that it spent almost all of its time in managing memory (more technically, performing garbage collection). Because of this, it was not processing information as expected. If you suspect that this is happening in your ATLAS server, run it on a machine with more memory or try to use arguments to Java to mitigate the problem.

Let us examine the configuration of the server in a simple ATLAS system, one line at a time. The `primary_server` property of the ATLAS system tells base stations to which (named) server they need send reports:

```
>,Property,primary_server,primary
```

A Database object in an ATLAS system gives the URL of a database, its name in the system (here `tau_db`), and the user name in the database system. We do not provide here the password; the software will prompt for it and will store it in `~/atlas/passwords.txt`, a safer place.

```
>,Database,tau_db,jdbc:mysql:mysqlsrv.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo,stoledo
```

Now come the definition of the Server object itself. The following line defines a server named `primary`, specifies the Internet address of the computer it runs on, the port it

listens to, its upstream server (here `null`, which means that there is no upstream server, this being the primary server that is fed by base stations, and the database it stores data in, here `tau_db`).

```
>,Server,primary,euler-27.cs.tau.ac.il,6780,null,tau_db
```

The next few lines specify properties of the server. The first two specify that it should compute localizations and that they should include covariance matrices.

```
>,>,Property,localize,true
>,>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true
```

The next two lines specify that the server should store data in a database and that this is not a special type of ATLAS database that is used to store backups only.

```
>,>,Property,noDataBase,false
>,>,Property,backup,false
```

The next line states that the database should store in the database the most recent localizations and detections of every tag. This is optional but speeds up certain queries considerably. This data can also be used by a web interface to the system.

```
>,>,Property,recentActivity,true
```

Finally, the following line states that when information from a base station arrives late, the server should recompute the relevant localizations. This recomputation is done in granularity of one hour, hence the name of this property.

```
>,>,Property,hourlyConsistency,true
```

9.3 The Database

ATLAS uses a MySQL database. Databases like MySQL are different than simple files. They rely on a server program that is usually the only software that accesses the underlying files directly; ATLAS software stores and retrieves data through this server program.

The database server does not need to run on the same computer as the ATLAS server program, but it can.

Databases like MySQL must usually be actively managed. Backing them up require attention and some expertise. In particular, simply copying the database files while the database is running does not work (we know; we did this for a while only to discover that all the backup files were corrupt and that the data could not be reconstructed from them). To back up the data you need to either stop the database server program or to use special backup procedures.

The data stored in an ATLAS database is the result of significant efforts to observe wild animals. It is your responsibility to ensure that the data is stored and backed up properly. Invest the necessary resources, especially if you have invested a lot in collecting the data in the first place.

Here are a few suggestions as to how to manage this database responsibly:

- If your department or group employs a database administrator (DBA), let this person set up and manage the ATLAS database. DBAs are (hopefully) experienced and they are trained to value the data they are responsible and to ensure its permanence.
- If your department does not employ a DBA, consider setting up the database as a cloud service. Services like Amazon RDS offer turn-key MySQL service that is run by professional DBAs and that is backed up regularly. Using such a service is more expensive per GB/month than managing the database yourself (some estimates are that the cost is about 40% higher than setting up a self-managed MySQL server on Amazon EC2), but you get professional database administration along with the storage.
- Make sure you know the backup policy (every day, every week, etc) and its implications (if the data is backed up every night, you will lose up to 24 h worth of data if the disks of the database server fail).
- Insist that backup files are tested, at least occasionally, by setting up a database from them and comparing its content to that of the live database.

If you set up the database yourself, install MySQL on a computer. Create a new database and create two users that can access this database. One should be able to read and write data and the other only to read. The read-write user is used by the ATLAS server and by the database administrator. The read-only user should be used by ATLAS users who only need to retrieve data from the database.

Create the tables and indices that ATLAS uses with the SQL script `create.sql` in `atlas-distribution/`

For experiments or short-term deployments of ATLAS systems, you can also use a database called SQLite. This database system stores all the data in a single file that does not require a separate database server program. SQLite is reliable, but its performance can be a bit erratic when the database is large, and it does not have good support for concurrent accesses to the database. This means that you should not run queries while the ATLAS server program is using the database, and that you should not use the hourly-consistency mechanism of ATLAS, since to the database it looks like a second user.

9.4 Internet Access

ATLAS server programs should run on a computer that base stations can reach through the Internet (this is only required for the primary server), that downstream servers (if any) can reach, and that real-time clients can reach. If the server computer is connected to the Internet through a firewall or router that uses NAT, you will need to configure the firewall or router to allow access to the server through a port. Any port number will work; just configure correctly it in `atlas.txt`.

9.5 Running Servers Continuously

ATLAS servers need to run most of the time. You can start them up from `/etc/rc.local` in the same way that you start up base-station software.

Another mechanism that we used successfully on servers in machine rooms is the `screen` utility. Servers in data centers or machine rooms, whether run by a cloud provider or by an academic IT organization, often run continuously for months or years without stopping or crashing. The `screen` utility in Linux allows you to run a program in a virtual shell, to disconnect from it (control-A then D, or automatically when the network connection is broken), and to reconnect later (run `screen -r`). The software continues to run even when you are disconnected. You can set up several `screen` sessions on the same computer (use `screen -S name` to start up named sessions and `screen -r name` to connect to later). Run `sudo apt install screen` to install in Ubuntu.

9.6 Data Mules (Uploading Data from Unconnected Base Stations)

[This feature has not been tested in a long time; beware.]

A base station that cannot connect to the primary server of its system accumulates data in a file. If the connection to the server is restored after a few hours or a few days, the base station will upload the data from the file.

If a connection to the server cannot be established or cannot be restored, the data must be uploaded in some other way. ATLAS provides a mechanism called a *data mule server* for uploading the data.

A data mule server is a computer running an ATLAS server that is configured to move data from base stations to the primary server. To configure a server as a data mule, simply give it the `serverId data-mule`. Data mule servers should not be defined in `atlas.txt`.

To mule (upload data), the computer running the data mule server must be connected to the same local network as the base station. An easy way to do this is to define the base station as a WiFi access point and to configure the data-mule server to connect to it. Once the two computers are connected to the same network, the data-mule server advertizes itself on the network, the base station discovers the advertisements and starts uploading the data to the data mule server. The uploaded data is forwarded to the primary server if the data mule server is connected to the internet. If the data mule server cannot reach the primary server either, the data will be stored on it until it can reach the primary server.

The base station reports to the data mule server how much data it still needs to upload. You can use these reports to decide when to disconnect the base station from the data mule.

Chapter 10

Running Command-Line Queries

The *query* command to atlas.bat (or atlas.sh in Linux) retrieves detections, localizations, and GPS localizations (of base stations, not of ATLAS tags) and can process them in various ways, including computing localizations.

The command takes several groups of options. One single-option group specifies the ATLAS system; it is mandatory. The syntax is *system=name*. Two other mandatory groups specify the input data source (database) and the output file.

The input is specified using the following rules. The first one is the recommended form; the name of the database is normally specified in the atlas.txt configuration file. Here are a few examples.

```
input=atlas:amazon_db
input=jdbc:mysql:'db.uni.edu'/'atlas','user','password'
input=jdbc:sqlite:filename.sqlite
input=objects:filename.objects
```

The last form uses serialized java objects created as the output of a previous query using the output:objects syntax.

The output is specified using the following rules.

```
output=jdbc:mysql:'db.uni.edu'/'atlas','user','password'
output=jdbc:sqlite:filename.sqlite
output=objects:filename.objects serialized java objects
output=printer text printouts to standard output
output=printer:filename.txt text file
output=json:filename.json JSON file
output=server:atlas-server.uni.edu:6789 dangeous, do not use!
```

Storing the output into an SQLite database is often the best options, since these files can be read very quickly in a wide range of programming environments, including R and Matlab. Output of localizations into a text file is suitable for further processing in Matlab. JSON files can be easily digested by virtually any programming environment, such as Matlab, Python, and R. Technically, the JSON file contains one array containing the output elements of the query. The server option uploads data to an ATLAS server. It is intended for uploading backup files into the database that the server is connected to or for uploading recomputed localizations. Use this option with extreme care because it

modifies the database that the server uses. The server name and port number arguments to this option are optional.

You can specify the name of a *Movebank study* whose data you would like to query. When you do that, the program queries all the data associated with the study, so you do not need to specify tags and a time range:

```
movebank-study=hula-passerines
```

If you do not specify a Movebank study, you must specify a *time range* for the query:

```
from=2020-feb-10-00-00
to=2020-feb-10-23-59
```

Either way, you must tell the program what to retrieve. Normally, the data that the query retrieves is written into the output file, but one (important) option tells the program to read detections and to output localizations:

```
detections
localizations
gps_localizations  GPS localizations of basestations
vh_detections      detections of Vildehaye data packets
localize           compute and output localizations
```

10.1 Examples of Simple Queries

Let's go through some simple examples that simply retrieve data from a database.

The first example retrieves localizations (*what=l*) associated with a Movebank study and prints them out on the standard output (screen).

```
c:\programs\atlas\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat query localizations movebank-study
↪ ="ATLAS hula Grus grus"  input=atlas:amazon_db output=printer
```

The next example retrieves one hour's worth of detections from the morning of December 17 2015 (data from exactly 05:00 will be included; data from exactly 06:00 will not).

```
c:\programs\atlas\atlas-distribution\atlas.sh query detections from=2015-Dec
↪ -17-05-00 to=2015-Dec-17-06-00 input=atlas:amazon_db output=printer
```

Options that filter data further (beyond just the time range) include:

```
basestations=id1,id2,id3  include only these base stations
tags=id1,id2              retrieves data for these tags
min-snr=lowerbound        detections filtered by SNR above a threshold
min-headroom=lowerbound   only detections with headroom above a threshold
```

10.2 Queries that Compute Localizations

The `localize` option tells ATLAS to compute (or recompute) localizations. The detections that are read from the database and that are used to compute the localizations will not be sent to the output file, only the computed localizations.

Since ATLAS uses detections of beacons when it computes localizations, the query must include beacons, not just mobile tags. That is, if you use the `tags=` syntax to restrict the tags that are queried, include in the list of tags all the active beacons, as well as the mobile tags that you want the query to localize.

Several options that we have already mentioned are helpful in localization queries. For example, by limiting the base stations you can explore how localizations would degrade if some base stations are removed from the system. Similarly, you can use options that limit the SNR and headroom to filter out noisy detections (SNR) or detections that were affected by strong interference (the headroom option).

Several additional options tell ATLAS exactly how to compute localizations.

<code>localize</code>	<i>an instruction to compute localizations</i>
<code>beacon-ref-other</code>	<i>beacons are not used as self time references, the default</i>
<code>beacon-ref-self</code>	<i>beacons are used as self time references</i>
<code>beacon-delay=n</code>	<i>uses beacon detections n seconds away for clock</i>
\rightarrow <code>synchronization</code>	
<code>cr-factor=c</code>	<i>Cramer–Rao multiplicative constant is c; default is usually fine</i>
<code>clocksync-strategy=string</code>	<i>algorithm; see below</i>
<code>localization-strategy=string</code>	<i>algorithm; see below</i>

The `beacon-ref-other` and `beacon-ref-self` options tell ATLAS how to compute localizations of beacons, if at all. Normally, a `localize` query does not compute localizations of beacons. If you want to compute them, you should normally add the `beacon-ref-other` option; it tells ATLAS to compute localizations of beacon x using detections of another beacon, say y , to synchronize the clocks. This is similar to the way mobile tags are localized and therefore can give an indication of the accuracy of the system. The alternative, `beacon-ref-self`, allows detections of beacon x to be used to synchronize the clocks when localizing the same beacon x . This gives unrealistically-accurate localization and is usually useless.

The clock synchronization strategy string (`clocksync-strategy`) tells ATLAS how to synchronize the clocks of the base stations. If it is missing, ATLAS performs the clock synchronization as part of every localization, as described in [atlas-accuracy]. How it is done exactly in this case depends on the localization strategy string, described below. If the option is present, ATLAS uses one of the following clock synchronization strategies:

- **Periodic** (the default); ATLAS estimates the rate and offset of each clock periodically (currently every 10 s) and uses the offset and rates to correct the time stamps of tag detections.
- **Multiple**; ATLAS collects beacon detections from before and after each tag transmission and uses them to synchronize the clocks for this single tag transmission.

These are the same beacons detections that are used when the clock synchronization and localization are performed jointly.

- `Single`; this is similar to `Multiple`, but uses a single beacon transmission to synchronize the clock offsets. Rates are not estimated.

The localization strategy string controls whether localizations are computed in 3D (if possible) or in 2D, how beacons are used to synchronize clocks, and whether the algorithm corrects for clock-rate errors. If the string contains `2D` the algorithm will compute locations in 2D; if it contains `3D` it will compute 3D locations. The different algorithms are `Simplified`, `Single` (or `SingleBeacon`), and `Multiple` or `MultipleBeacons`. The latter ones are slower but potentially more accurate. The beacon-delay parameter has a strong influence on the performance of `MultipleBeacons` runs (larger delays makes the algorithm slower). To correct for clock-rate errors, include in the string `Rates`. Sample strings are `3D-Simplified`, `2D-MultipleBeacons-Rates`, and `3D-SingleBeacon`. To delay computing localizations in a prefix of a track until we find a transmission that was detected by at least 4 base stations, add the word `DelayN3` to the localization strategy string.

In January 2022 we added a better way to compute the covariance matrix of localizations. To use the new method, include the word `GNCov` in the covariance string. The old method sometimes produced covariance matrices with entries close to zero when the actual uncertainty was high; the new method seems not to suffer from this problem, but other than that, it seems to produce similar covariance matrices. Using this option is highly recommended.

If you include the string `AttachInputs` in the strategy string, the each output localization will also include the inputs (detections grouped by tag or beacon transmission) that where used to compute the localization. This is useful when the output file format is Java objects or JSON objects.

The `cramer-rao-estimator` option is an instruction to compute (estimate) how SNR affects the variance of arrival-time estimates. It is not intended for users but for configuring ATLAS systems for new hardware or new transmission parameters. The option requires another parameter, which sets the limit for time differences between pairs of detections that are used by the estimator, in seconds:

```
max-time-diff=n
```

10.3 Invalidation Queries¹

~~The `invalidate` option marks a time range in a database as a time range whose localizations and statistics need to be recomputed. This option is intended to be used only by ATLAS administrators, not by users. It allows the administrator to replace localizations in a database by localizations that were computed using a different algorithm.~~

~~The recomputation is done by an ATLAS server connected to the database, not by the query program; the query only marks a time range for subsequent recomputation by~~

¹This option was removed from query and replaced by a separate command, `invalidate`.

the server. This option is special in that it only takes a to, from, and output arguments; there is no need to specify an output data source. The input must be an SQL database, and the invalidation will occur in that database.

10.4 Output Formats

For large queries, the best output format is an sqlite database file. It has the same table structure as the main ATLAS database and can be queried efficiently. It is possible to query it directly from Matlab, and it is also possible to create such files in Matlab.

For exploration, a format called JSON is useful. You specify it with

```
output=json:filename.json
```

The format of text output files (output=printer:filename.txt argument) is as follows. Localizations are specified by rows (lines) like the following one:

```
1004000660 1448506605.673 6 433546509 2 6 258139.3 778331.0 70.0 NaN NaN NaN 3.2
  ↪ 1.33e-13 1.017e+01 -1.077e+00 0.000e+00 0.000e+00 5.529e+00 0.000e+00
  ↪ 0.000e+00 0.000e+00 0.000e+00
```

The columns are

1. tag number (TAG field in the LOCALIZATIONS table in the database)
2. time (in seconds since the beginning of 1970, UTC, TIME field in the database)
3. number of detections that this localization is based on (NBS)
4. frequency in Hz (FREQ)
5. dimensionality of the localization problem (DIM, here 2D); distance computations are always done in 3D, but in 2D localizations, the height is assumed and not estimated
6. The number of constraints that were used in the estimation (NCONSTRAINTS). In the simple algorithm, this is the same as the number of detections; in more complex algorithms, it is higher
7. Easting estimated location (in the projection that the system uses; X in the database)
8. Northing estimation location (Y)
9. Height above sea level (Z)
10. Easting error (known only for beacons, not in the database)
11. Northing error
12. Height error

13. Norm of the residual (PENALTY); this is a measure of the extent to which the arrival-time estimates at the receivers do not agree with the estimated localtion; it is expressed in meters
14. The norm of the gradient of the optimization problem (GRADNRM); it should be close to zero (more precisely, to the precision of the arithmetic which is about 10^{-16}); if it is large, it means that the localization algorithm failed
15. The next 9 numbers are the variance-covariance matrix in the following order: var(x), cov(x,y), cov(x,z), cov(y,x), var(y), cov(y,z), cov(z,x), cov(z,y), var(z); the names of the columns are self explanatory (VARX, COVXY, etc)

Chapter 11

Computing Localizations

This chapter explains the basics of location estimation, how ATLAS estimates the location of tags, and how to control the localization algorithms in ATLAS.

11.1 The Core Ideas using a Simplified Example

Localizations that ATLAS computes consist not only of spatial coordinates, but also of a set of values that help users assess the reliability of the localization. To understand the meaning of these values, it helps to explain a bit about the process in which ATLAS computes localizations.

We start with a highly simplified imaginary setup, in which localizations have only one dimension (say position along a long straight road) and in which localizations are computed from distance measurements. Consider a tag in location $\hat{\ell}$ along the road. The little circle above the ℓ signifies that this is the true position, not an estimate, and the red color signifies that we do not know the location; $\hat{\ell}$ is an unknown that we want to estimate.

Suppose that we can somehow measure the distance along the road between the tag and base stations; only the distance, not the direction. Suppose that we measure the distance from base station 1 at a known location ρ_1 to be 1000 ± 3 m. That is, the measured distance is 1000 m, we know that the measurement is not exact, and we estimate its standard deviation to be 3 m. We colored the expression for the location of the base station in green since we know it. We express this as an equation, or constraint,

$$d_1 = |\rho_1 - \hat{\ell}| + \epsilon_1,$$

where $d_1 = 1000$ is the first measured distance and ϵ_1 represents the measurement error, which we take to be a random variable with zero mean and standard deviation of $\sigma_1 = 3$.

If we only have this one measurement, as shown in Figure 11.1A, we know that the tag is either near $\rho_1 + 1000$ or near $\rho_1 - 1000$. The measurement is *ambiguous*, in the sense that the tag could be in one of two locations that are far from each other. Suppose that we make 2 more measurements from base station one, 1002 ± 4 and 999 ± 2 . The system of constraints is clearly still ambiguous (Figure 11.1B). If we add a measurement from

Figure 11.1: Distance measurements along a line. The figure shows three scenarios, ranging from one to three measurements. The red triangle represents the location \hat{l} of the tag, green triangles the locations ρ_1, ρ_2, ρ_3 of base stations, and gray rectangles the standard deviations $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ of measurements.

Figure 11.2: The objective function (top) for the problem location estimation problem shown on the bottom.

a second base station (Figure 11.1C), we can resolve approximately the location of the tag.

ATLAS, like many other localization systems, estimates the unknown location of the tag by minimizing a function that measures the level of disagreement between the actual measurements and the measurements that we expect to make given a possible location. If ATLAS had to solve our simplified problem, it would have produced an estimate $\hat{\ell}$ of ℓ by minimizing

$$\sum_i \left(\frac{|\rho_i - \ell| - d_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 .$$

This expression, called the *objective function*, is a function of a hypothetical location ℓ . For every possible ℓ , we get a value, called a *penalty*, of the objective function. The function is a sum of squares of the disagreements between predicted measurements, the values $|\rho_i - \ell|$, and the actual measurements, the d_i s. An algorithm searches for the value of ℓ that minimizes the penalty; this is returned as the location estimate, $\hat{\ell}$. The penalty function for our distances-based problem is shown in Figure 11.2.

Figure 11.2 shows two important features of the objective function. First, its value is meaningful. If the measurements were error-free, $\epsilon_i = 0$, then the value of the function at the true location ℓ would be zero. A non-zero but small value indicates that the minimum almost satisfies the constraints. This is often an indication of an accurate estimate. ATLAS reports the value of a penalty function with every localization, in the PENALTY field in the database. The penalty that is reported is not the sum of squares, which is a bit hard to interpret, but rather the maximum disagreement, without weighting (so the units are meters). On our simple localization problem, the reported penalty would be

$$\max_i ||\rho_i - \ell| - d_i| .$$

A large reported penalty means that the localization is inconsistent with at least one of the constraints that were used to compute it. If that constraint had a large standard deviation, the localization might still be accurate. A small value indicates that the localization is consistent with the constraints; it might not be close to the tag (for example, if the constraints are ambiguous).

The second feature is the *gradient* of the objective function at the reported solution. The gradient is the vector of derivatives of the penalty function with respect to the coordinates of the solution. In the one dimensional case that we use in this section to illustrate the concepts, the gradient is simply the derivative of the function at the reported localization. At a minimum of the objective function, the gradient is always zero. If it is not zero, the value of the function drops when you move from the reported location in some specific direction. If the value drops, we are not at a minimum. ATLAS also reports a value, GRADNRM, called the *norm* of the gradient that tells you how large the gradient is at the reported location. This value should normally be very close to zero. If it is not, it means that ATLAS was not able to find a minimum of the objective function.

ATLAS also attaches to every localization a *covariance matrix*, an estimate of the level of uncertainty associated with the localization.

The measurements that we use to localize tags can sometimes be inaccurate, and the inaccuracy is not always reflected in the estimated standard deviation. Figure 11.3

Figure 11.3: An outlier and its effect on the objective function and its minimum. The objective function is shown in orange. The objective function from Figure 11.2, without the outlier, is shown in blue for reference.

shows such a measurement, called an *outlier*. If the measurement is inaccurate but its estimated standard deviation is large enough, it does not have a large effect on the accuracy of the localization. But in cases like the one shown in the figure, outliers tend to have a large influence on the objective function and its minimum, leading to inaccurate localizations. ATLAS can sometimes identify outlier measurements and ignore them.

11.2 Time of Arrival Localization

The constraints that ATLAS uses are more complicated than the ones shown above. If ATLAS base stations had perfect clocks, the constraints would be

$$t_i = \tau + \frac{1}{c} \|\rho_i - \hat{\ell}\|_2 + \epsilon_1,$$

where τ is the time in which the ping left the tag, t_i is the measured time when the ping reached base station i at location ρ_i , c is the speed of radio propagation (speed of light), and ϵ_1 represents the error in the measurement of t_i . The expression $\|\cdot\|_2$ represents the Euclidean distance. Here ρ_i and $\hat{\ell}$ are vectors in 3 dimensions. ATLAS needs to estimate $\hat{\ell}$, the location of the tag, but it also estimate τ . In most cases, ATLAS estimates only the easting and northing coordinates of $\hat{\ell}$; it uses either a fixed altitude value, or the elevation of the terrain, for the third coordinate. We refer to such localizations as *2-dimensional* or *assumed-height* localizations. ATLAS must have time-of-arrival

measurements at 3 base stations in order to produce a 2D localization (and a useless estimate of τ). ATLAS can estimate all 3 coordinates of the location of a tag, but the placement of base stations usually leads to poor accuracy of the estimated altitude.

However, the clocks in ATLAS base stations are not perfect, so the constraints that ATLAS uses to estimate locations have another term (sometimes two more),

$$t_i = \tau + \frac{1}{c} \|\rho_i - \hat{\ell}\|_2 + o_i + \epsilon_1, \quad (11.1)$$

where o_i is the clock offset of base station i . To help estimate the clock offsets, ATLAS uses *beacons*, transmitters at known fixed positions. A ping from a beacon at position ρ_b adds a constraint of the form

$$t_b = \tau_b + \frac{1}{c} \|\rho_i - \rho_b\|_2 + o_i + \epsilon_b. \quad (11.2)$$

ATLAS can estimate the locations and clock offsets either *jointly*, where a single objective function is used to estimate both the o_i s and $\hat{\ell}$ (and the times of departure, τ and τ_b), or separately. When estimating them separately, ATLAS first estimates the o_i s from constraints of the form (11.2) and then substitutes the estimated values in constraints of the form (11.1). Either way, ATLAS can also estimate the clock rates, not only the clock offsets.

When ATLAS estimates a location and a set of clock offsets jointly, it uses constraints that correspond to one ping of the tag and to one or more pings of one or more beacons. Using constraints from multiple beacon pings leads to more accurate estimates of the o_i s, and this in turn can improve the accuracy of the estimate of $\hat{\ell}$. However, the more constraints are used in each objective function, the higher the likelihood that one of them is an outlier. So sometimes using a single or just a few beacon pings is better.

11.3 Three Contexts in which ATLAS Computes Localizations

ATLAS computes localizations in three different contexts: at real-time, in a delayed-processing mode called the *hourly consistency enforcer* (or just *enforcer* for short), and when users run queries with the `localize` option. ATLAS servers implement the first two contexts, the real-time context and the enforcer context. The software that runs in these three contexts is exactly the same, but it usually makes sense to compute real-time localizations a little differently. Also, when users run localization queries, they can experiment with various options to try to get more localizations and/or more accurate localizations.

The real-time and query contexts are self explanatory, but the hourly-consistency enforcer requires an explanation. Whenever an ATLAS server writes a detection to the database, it also marks the hour in which the detection occurred as requiring re-computation of the localization. Every minute or so, the server checks if there are hours requiring re-computation and if detections have not been added to them the past few minutes. If detections have been added, the server waits for the stream of detections to end. If there are hours that qualify, the server re-computes the localizations from that hour.

This serves two purposes. First, this causes a re-computation of all the localizations shortly after each round hour ends. The re-computation can use algorithms that are less suitable for real-time processing. Second, the re-computation ensures that all the available data has been used to compute localizations, even if data from some base stations arrives after a delay of hours or days. The hourly consistency enforcer runs only if the `hourlyConsistency` property of the server is set to `true`.

The settings that control how ATLAS computes real-time localizations in the server are normally specified as properties of the server in `atlas.txt`. Here are definitions that tell the server to compute real-time localizations, to run the hourly consistency enforcer, and to compute real-time localizations in 2 dimensions (to assume the altitude of tags rather than to estimate it).

```
>,Server,primary,atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il,6789,null,null
>,>,...
>,>,Property,localize,true      tells the server to localize in real time
>,>,Property,hourlyConsistency,true tells the server to run the enforcer
>,>,...
>,>,Property,localization.dimension,TWO
>,>,...
```

The parameters that control how localizations are computed in the enforcer are properties of the database:

```
>,Database,tau_db,jdbc:mysql:mysql.cs.tau.ac.il:5900/atlas
>,>,...
>,>,Property,localizeBulkDedup,true recommended; enforcer accesses the database
    ↪ efficiently
>,>,...
>,>,Property,localization.dimension,TWO
>,>,...
```

In a query, the dimension parameter is specified as

```
atlas.bat query localize localization.dimension=TWO ...
```

or in a CSV options file,

```
...
localization.dimension,TWO
...
```

11.4 Recommended and Alternate Settings

This section lists and explains the main parameters that affect how ATLAS estimates locations. We explain here both the recommended values for important parameters and the default values. The recommended and default values sometimes differ, to ensure consistent behavior of ATLAS systems. That is, when we discover that the default value of a parameter is not optimal, we recommend that users set it to another value explicitly, so that systems in which the value has not been changed do not change their behavior when the software is updated. For conciseness, we use the CSV-file notation.

By default, ATLAS estimates tag locations and the base stations' clock parameters jointly, so the first line below is optional.

```
clocksync.strategy,JOINT
clocksync.beaconDelaySeconds,4
```

The beacon-delay parameter controls the maximum time difference between the tag's ping and the pings of beacons that are considered for clock-parameter estimation. The recommended value of around 4; the default is much longer (because it was originally thought that a longer time window will give better results; we maintain the default so that ATLAS systems continue to behave consistently until their parameters are modified explicitly). Separate estimation is currently not recommended, but you can experiment with it by setting the `clocksync.strategy` parameter to `PERIODIC` or one of the other options given in the help message.

In the default joint setting, we recommend the use of an outlier detection and removal technique introduced to ATLAS in summer of 2022, specified by

```
localization.robust,true
```

Setting this value to `false` (the default) leads to the use of algorithm that ATLAS has been using originally. ATLAS has two outlier detection and removal algorithms. The default one is

```
localization.hypothesisSelection,CONSENSUS
```

The alternative setting, `CLUSTERING`, is currently not recommended. These algorithms are controlled by a few parameters; we recommend that you leave them at their default values

```
localization.outlierStdDevThreshold   for CONSENSUS
localization.outlierDistanceThreshold for CONSENSUS
localization.dbscanEps                 for CLUSTERING
```

When using an outlier detection and removal, we recommend that you also set

```
localization.constraintCountIsTagDetections,true
```

This parameter changes the meaning of the `NCONSTRAINTS` field in the database so that it reflects the number of base stations that received the ping from the tag. By comparing this value to the `NBS` field, which counts the number of base stations that detected the tag and were not rejected as outliers, you can tell whether outliers have been rejected from a particular localization. If this is set to `false`, the field simply counts the number of constraints that make up the objective function.

In the joint clock-synchronization setting, ATLAS usually uses one beacon transmission to estimate the parameters of the clocks of each localization problem. To use all the beacon transmissions within the beacon-delay window, specify

```
localization.jointClocksync,MULTIPLE_BEACONS
```

The value `SINGLE_BEACON` is the default for the new robust method and the value `SIMPLIFIED` (which behaves similarly) is the default for the older method.

In summer 2022 we added a new algorithm to estimate the covariance of localizations; the older method sometimes underestimated the variance. The Gauss-Newton approximation is now recommended but is not the default. To select it (you should), specify

```
localization.covarianceApproximation,GAUSS_NEWTON
```

The *tracker* is an object that tracks the location of a tag over time. It is used in the outlier-rejection algorithms to disambiguate ambiguous localization problems, and it is used in older algorithms as an initial guess for the search for the minimum of the objective function. Until summer 2022, the tracker used simply the last localization of the tag, but we replaced this with a robust Kalman filter. To select this new and recommended approach, use

```
localization.tracker,KALMAN_STATIONARY
```

The behavior of the Kalman-filter tracker can be controlled using two parameters, shown below with their default values.

```
localization.trackerEvSDMetersPerSec,0.1
localization.trackerEvSDUBMeters,750
```

Both control the standard deviation of the constraints that state that the tag does not move much. The first is the likely speed of the tag, in meters per second. The second is the maximum standard deviation of these constraints.

ATLAS normally estimates only the easting and northing coordinates of tags (*x* and *y* values). To request estimation of the altitude too, specify

```
localization.dimension,THREE
```

To estimate in two dimensions but with the altitude set to the elevation of the terrain, you can specify a digital elevation map (DEM). This improves localizations, especially in hilly regions. It is meaningless in flat areas. The syntax is:

```
localization.dem,yourregion.tif
```

ATLAS can usually tell if a localization problem is ambiguous (the objective function has more than one minimum close to zero). If the tracker has a reliable (but not necessarily accurate) estimate of the tag's location, ATLAS chooses the location that makes more sense given the previous localizations. If the tracker does not have a reliable location estimate, ATLAS can either choose one of the possible locations (usually one out of two), or it can delay the localization process. When the tag is localized unambiguously later, ATLAS goes back to resolve the ambiguous locations. It is best to delay ambiguous localizations in the query and enforcer contexts, but not in the real-time context,

```
localization.delayAmbiguous,true false for real-time localizations
```

ATLAS can also estimate the location of beacons. This seems silly, because we know where they are, but this serves as a good indicator of the health of an ATLAS system. You can tell ATLAS to localize beacons using

```
localization.beacons,WITH_OTHERS or SKIP to not localize
```

A third option for this value, `WITH_SELF`, computes localizations, but using the beacon itself to estimate clock parameters; this results in unrealistically-accurate localizations, so it has no real value other than testing.

The parameter

```
localization.gridsearchEnabled
```

is only relevant for the older localization algorithms (robust set to false); it skips a computationally expensive method to try to find the minimum of the objective function. It is usually best to set it to false.

11.5 Obsolete Parameters

The following parameters have been used in older versions of ATLAS and are no longer used. Most of them have been replaced by more structured parameters.

```
localization.strategy
beaconSkip
dem_geographic_geotiff
```

11.6 Recommended Settings

Here are recommendations for how to define a server and its database in `atlas.txt`.

```
>,Database,my_db,jdbc:mysql:'mysql.university.edu/atlas'
# how the enforcer insert localizations in the
>,>,Property,localizeBulkDedup,true
>,>,Property,grouping,TIMESTAMP
>,>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true
>,>,Property,localization.beacons,WITH_OTHERS
>,>,Property,localization.dimension,TWO
>,>,Property,localization.jointClocksync,SINGLE_BEACON
>,>,Property,localization.beaconDelaySeconds,4,
>,>,Property,localization.robust,TRUE
>,>,Property,localization.constraintCountIsTagDetections,TRUE
>,>,Property,localization.tracker,KALMAN_STATIONARY
>,>,Property,localization.covarianceApproximation,GAUSS_NEWTON
>,>,Property,localization.dem,n32_e035_1arc_v3.tif
>,>,Property,localization.outlierStdDevThreshold,0.1
>,>,Property,localization.trackerEvSDMetersPerSec,0.1
>,>,Property,localization.outlierDistanceThreshold,100
# delay ambiguous localizations in the enforcer
>,>,Property,localization.delayAmbiguous,TRUE

>,Server,primary,atlas-server.university.edu,6789,null,my_db
>,>,Property,id,972035090
# port for Prometheus metrics
>,>,Property,httpPort,1234
```

```
>>,Property,noDataBase,false
>>,Property,backup,false
>>,Property,localize,true
>>,Property,recentActivity,true
>>,Property,hourlyConsistency,true
# localization properties from here on
>>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true
>>,Property,localization.beacons,WITH_OTHERS
>>,Property,localization.dimension,TWO
>>,Property,localization.jointClocksync,SINGLE_BEACON
>>,Property,localization.beaconDelaySeconds,4,
>>,Property,localization.robust,TRUE
>>,Property,localization.constraintCountIsTagDetections,TRUE
>>,Property,localization.tracker,KALMAN_STATIONARY
>>,Property,localization.delayAmbiguous,TRUE
>>,Property,localization.covarianceApproximation,GAUSS_NEWTON
>>,Property,localization.dem,n32_e035_1arc_v3.tif
>>,Property,localization.outlierStdDevThreshold,0.1
>>,Property,localization.trackerEvSDMetersPerSec,0.1
>>,Property,localization.outlierDistanceThreshold,100
# do not delay ambiguous localizations in real time
>>,Property,localization.delayAmbiguous,FALSE
```

Chapter 12

Hardware Setup for ATLAS Base Stations

This chapter describes the components of infrastructure base stations and how to prepare and set them up.

An infrastructure base station consists of:

- A UHF antenna for the frequency band of the ATLAS system. So far we have only built systems for the 434 MHz band, so the equipment we list below is for this band. The antenna should be as high as possible, at the top of a mast or a tower.
- A low-noise amplifier (LNA) close to the antenna. Because this amplifier must be close to the antenna, it is also called sometimes a masthead amplifier. Its role is to amplify weak signals from tags before they get attenuated by the long cable run going down to the receiver. The LNA is connected to the antenna by a short piece of coaxial cable (coax).
- A *front-end unit* that provides power to the LNA, filters the signals coming from it, possibly amplifying them, and protects the receiver from signals strong enough to damage it.
- A *sampling receiver* (sometimes referred to as a software-defined radio or SDR) that digitizes the signal from the antenna and sends it to the computer. To perform time-of-arrival localization, the receiver must have an accurate and stable clock. We use clocks called GPS-disciplined oscillators (GPSDOs) that include a GPS receiver and require an external GPS antenna.
- A computer that performs all the signal processing required to identify signals from tags and to estimate their arrival times and that sends detection reports to an ATLAS server. We use normal desktop-type computers, possibly in a small form factor.
- An internet connection to allow the computer to send reports to the server and to update the configuration of the ATLAS system.

The rest of this section lists these components, explains how to set them up (other than software installation), and provides a checklist for new deployments.

12.1 UHF Antennas

We mostly use vertical collinear antennas that are omnidirectional in the azimuth plane and have gain towards the horizon in the elevation plane. Their gain depends on their physical size. The antenna itself is completely enclosed in a fiberglass tube.

We mostly use a model called TQJ-400C made by Kenbotong communications. It is about 1.8m high and has a gain of 7.8dBi. We order it with short piece of coax (about 0.5m) attached to it and terminated by an N-type plug.

The Diamond X50N is a good equivalent that appears to be more widely available and is also a bit less expensive (about 100 USD). It is about the same size. It comes with an N-type female socket, which requires preparing a short coax with N-type male connectors on both ends to attach the antenna to the LNA.

We also used two other types of antennas. One is the 436CP16 by M2 Antenna Systems, a 16-element cross Yagi. This is a directional antenna in both planes, so it is only appropriate for bases stations that are away from the main coverage area of the ATLAS system. It is circularly polarized. It costs about 250 USD.

The other is the EB-432/RK70CM, also by M2 Antenna Systems, which is an egg-beater antenna. It is omnidirectional and has circular polarization in some directions and linear in others. We installed it sideways with the RK70CM radials so that it covers roughly 180 degrees with circular polarization. It costs about 240 USD.

Figure 12.1: An N-type male connector.

12.2 Masthead LNA

We use the L434LNACN from Down East Microwave¹, which costs 85 USD.

This amplifier has about 17dB of gain and noise figure below 1dB. We order it with two N-type female sockets (it can be ordered with other connectors). It requires 5V or more at about 100mA, with DC fed through the output coax.

The part number (L434LNACN) represents a special item built specifically for ATLAS systems. The product that this LNA is based on requires 7.5V or higher, is tuned for a slightly different frequency (432MHz rather than 434MHz), and is usually fed by a separate cable; its price is the same. Make sure that you order the correct part number and specify that you need the LNA to work down

Figure 12.2: L434LNACN mast-head preamplifier from Down East Microwave.

¹<http://www.downeastmicrowave.com>

Figure 12.3: A USRP N200 radio with the cover removed. The GPSDO is the circuit board on the top right.

to 5V, to be powered through the output coax connector, and to come with two N-type connectors.

12.3 The Radio

ATLAS base stations use USRP N200 or USRP B200 radios, made by Ettus Research². The N200 radio has slightly higher performance is is substantially more expensive than the B200. The N200 connects to the computer using an Ethernet cable and the B200 through a USB cable.

The N200, shown in Figure 12.3, is part of a modular system of radios, and in particular it requires an RF board. We order it with the WBX-40 daughter board and with a GPSDO (a GPS disciplined Oscillator). The radio costs about 1800 USD, the WBX 570 USD, and the GPSDO another 900 USD.

Each N200 radio will therefore come in 3 packages: the N200, the WBX, and the GPSDO. You will need to do the following steps to assemble the radio:

- Open the N200's enclosure.

²<https://www.ettus.com>

- Install the GPSDO in the radio according to the instruction sheet that comes with it. This involves attaching 3 coax cables and 2 twisted-cable assemblies, and **moving two jumpers on the N200's motherboard**.
- Plug in and screw down the WBX, and connect one of the RF cables that come with the WBX between the RX2 connector on the WBX and the front panel (or the front-end unit; see below). You do not need to use the other cable. Installing the GPSDO first is easier than the other way around.

The radio should come with a 6V power adapter and with an Ethernet cable.

To use a B200 with ATLAS, you again needs to add to it a GPSDO. There are two to choose from, one with a TCXO (temperature-compensated crystal oscillator) and the other with an OCXO (oven-controlled crystal oscillator, which means that temperature variations are not only compensated for, but actively minimized). The TCXO costs less and allows the B200 to be powered by the USB connection; it is less stable than the OCXO but is normally sufficient for ATLAS. If you order the OCXO, you will need an external power supply that you also need to order.

ATLAS can also use two-channel variants of these radios, the N210 and B210. They are more expensive and do not bring any benefit to ATLAS. Ettus also makes physically-smaller variants of the B200, but we have not tried them.

12.4 GPS Antenna

The GPS receiver in the GPSDO inside the N200 or B200 needs an active (amplified) GPS antenna. The GPS antenna connector on the back of the N200 and B200 is an SMA connector. The N200 provides 3V for the antenna and the B200 provides 5V.

The best place to locate the GPS antenna is near the base of the UHF antenna. This placement will allow you to use GPS fixes collected by the software to determine the precise position of the UHF antenna. The accuracy of this position affects the accuracy of ATLAS localizations. This is likely to require a long cable.

If you place the GPS antenna close to the radio, you will need to adjust for the distance and height differences when you specify the location of the UHF antenna.

Ettus sells a suitable magnetic patch antenna with a 5m cable terminated with a matching SMA connector for 60 USD. Digikey sells similar antennas for much less, as well as a range of higher-performance antennas. (For ATLAS the performance of the GPS antenna is not particularly important, but it is useful to buy antennas that can withstand the elements).

12.5 The Front-End Unit

We use custom front-end units that connect between the radio and the LNA [MelemedToledoFrontEnd]. The units we describe in this section are second generation units. Section A.8 discusses production variants. For documentation of the first-generation units, see [UHFFrontEnd].

The units have three functions:

1. An RF filter keeps interfering out-of-band signals out of the receiver, allowing it to perform better.
2. An RF limiter protects both this filter and the receiver from signals strong enough to damage it.
3. A DC limiter and a bias tee provide DC power to the LNA while limiting the current that it can draw. The current limit allows users to connect to the front-end unit either an LNA or an antenna, even if the antenna shorts at DC.

Figure 12.4: The front-end unit (second generation, revision 1).

The units come as mostly-assembled circuit boards. The user needs to attach the RF connectors (SMA male and female), the DC wires, and the housing of the DC connectors, and a resistor between the positive DC input and the Enable input (between the positive and negative DC inputs)³. We use wires that already have contacts attached to the end that fits into the connector housing. The pull-up resistor should be around 10k, but the exact value is not critical. We will probably have it assembled it as part of the board in future revisions of the unit.

The cost of the circuit boards depend on the quantity that is ordered. In quantities of 10, the units cost about 41 USD each; in quantities of 200, less than 10 USD. The connectors must be purchased separately, according to the details below.

The units are designed to fit into the N200 radio, for convenience. The DC input connector attaches to a mating connector on the N200 motherboard. If you use a B200, the unit will need to be fitted outside the radio.

The *enable* signal on the front-end board control DC supply through the coax connector. When pulled high (connected directly or through a resistor to the positive supply), the unit provides power to the LNA. When pulled low (to ground, which is also the negative supply), it does not. If you use the unit in ad-hoc base stations, you can connect the enable signal to a switch that enables or disables DC power towards the antenna and/or LNA.

If you connect an antenna that presents a DC short, the front-end will consume about 150mA and will get warm. If it gets too warm, it shuts down. No harm should occur from shorting the antenna connector.

If you are using the units on radios other than the N200, you will need to supply power from a separate power supply. The units can work with any DC voltage up to 6.5V. More than this will damage them.

The following table lists the connectors and wires that attach to the front-end's board. The total cost for these parts in small quantities is about 10 USD. There are many potential replacements to these components. The boards are available for purchase from CircuitHub at

https://circuitHub.com/projects/sivan_toledo/filter-bias-limiters

³The resistor is no longer necessary (starting at revision 2 of the board, which includes it).

Figure 12.5: The front-end unit installed in an N200

Item	Mfg & Part Number	Digikey Part Number
SMA plug (board edge)	Linx CONSMA013.066	CONSMA013.062-ND
SMA jack (board edge)	Molex 0732512120	WM5536-ND
Black wire with contact	Molex 0008500113-08-B2	0008500113-08-B2-ND
Red wire with contact	Molex 0008500113-08-R2	0008500113-08-R2-ND
Connector Housing	Molex 22-01-3027	WM2000-ND
Resistor	Any, 10k	(not necessary for revision 2)

12.6 Computer

The ability of ATLAS base stations to track a large number of tags and to detect tags quickly depends on a capable processor. We normally use computer with an 8GB and Intel Core i7 processors, with 4 cores in full-size desktop and with 2 cores in small-form-factor computers.

N200 radios are connected to the computer using a wired 1 Gb/s Ethernet connection. The radios are sensitive to the performance of the Ethernet network interface in the computer. Some Ethernet chips that function normally when connected to a router or switch cause problems when connected to N200 radios.

One way to address this, at least in desktops with expansion slots (PCI or ePCI), is to add an Ethernet card to the computer if the built-in Ethernet connection causes problems to the radio. These cards are typically inexpensive. This is one good reason to choose computers with reasonably large form factors. If you opt for a small form factor, try to select one with an expansion slot that can be used for an extra Ethernet card.

The other way to address this issue is to test the radio with a computer of exactly the same model of the computer that you plan to purchase.

hotspots. This setup, developed by Michal Handel and Yotam Orchan, allows the computer in the base station to use a WiFi connection (to the hotspot), not a cellular connection, and this removes the need to have a driver for the modem.

In Harod, the WiFi hotspots are powered by a USB socket that is powered by an always-on AC adapter, but the computer is connected through a WiFi-controlled smart socket. This allows system operators to turn off power to the computer (to perform a hard reset if it gets stuck); the WiFi hotspot that relays the power-off and power-on commands to the smart socket remains on because it is connected to AC power directly, not through the smart socket. The smart socket that they use actually includes an always-on USB socket that is used to power the hotspot (Assaf Uzan came up with this setup). The application that they use to control the smart sockets is called eWeLink.

Figure 12.6: Smart sockets that allow you to remotely power cycle the computer.

12.8 Cables, Connectors, and Miscellaneous Items

You also need the following miscellaneous items for each basestations.

- We use LMR-400 coax cable for the run between the LNA and the front-end unit. This is a 1cm diameter cable, fairly stiff, and very durable. You can use the same cable for the short cable between the UHF antenna and the LNA, if the antenna does not come with an attached cable.
- 4 N-type male plug connectors designed for LMR-400, or 2 if the antenna comes with an attached cable with a plug. You will attach the connectors to the long cable run in the field, after you cut the cable to length.
- Heat-shrink tubing to weatherproof the attachment point of the connectors.
- Instruction sheet for the connectors.
- 75cm of LMR-195 or RG-58 coax cable, for a flexible transition piece between the stiff LMR-400 and the radio.
- N-type female connector and SMA-male plug designed for RG-58 or LMR-195 (the same connectors should fit both types of cable). You can prepare this 75cm jumper in the lab or buy them ready made at Digikey and elsewhere.
- If you use a GPS antenna that comes without a cable, you need a coax with appropriate connectors (SMA male plug on the radio side, and whatever matches the antenna connector on the other side).
- U clamps to attach the UHF antenna to the mast (usually comes with the antenna).

- A weatherproof box for the LNA with U clamps to attach it to the mast.
- AC mains splitter or power strip. During normal operations you need two AC outlets, one for the computer and one for the radio. You need at least one more outlet to allow a monitor to be connected to the computer, in case you need to diagnose Internet connections problems that prevent remote network connections.

12.9 Tools

We use the following tools when setting up base stations.

- A set of tools to prepare and crimp LMR-400 connectors. We use the CST-400 preparation tool from Times Microwave (the manufacturer of the LMR-400), which costs about 110 USD. The crimp tool costs another 50 USD or so.
- A hobby knife for preparing RG-58 cable.
- A crimper for RG-58. Depending on the model, the same crimper can be used on both LMR-400 and RG-58/LMR-195. As explained above, you can get by without preparing any RG-58 cable assemblies by buying them ready made.
- Heat gun for heat-shrink tubing.
- A computer monitor, AC cable and DVI or VGA cable, and a keyboard and a mouse.
- A multimeter .
- Hand tools (wrenches, screwdrivers, etc).

Figure 12.7: Smart sockets that allow you to remotely power cycle the computer.

12.10 Setting Up New N200 Radios

Connect the radio to its power supply and to the computer.

Verify that the computer can find and talk with the radio by running

```
~/uhd/host/build/utils/uhd_find_devices
```

It should find the new radio with address 192.168.10.2.

Check that the firmware on the radio is appropriate for the version of the UHD driver by running

```
~/uhd/host/build/utils/query_gpsdo_sensors
```

If the firmware is up to date, the program will report GPS location and time. If not, it will complain and will tell you to (1) download new firmware files and (2) upload them to the radio. It will tell you what commands to run to accomplish these tasks. (When using UHD 3.8.5 on Ubuntu 16.04, we found that it was necessary to install in

Ubuntu the `python_cheetah` package to successfully run the commands that the driver suggests.)

Once `query_gpsdo_sensors` run, calibrate the radio. Run the three commands

```
uhd_cal_rx_iq_balance
```

```
uhd_cal_tx_dc_offset
```

```
uhd_cal_tx_iq_balance
```

(they are in the same location as the previous programs). **You must run the calibration with no antenna or amplifier attached.** The GPS antenna can remain connected in the back; it does not affect the calibration process.

These commands create 3 files in `~/uhd/cal`. The files have names that end with `serial.csv` where `serial` is the serial number of the radio (more specifically, of the daughter board). Commit these files to the calibration directory in the configuration directory of the system you plan to use the radio in (on the SVN server storing the configuration files for the system).

If you use our second-generation filters that fit within the radio, install them now between the front panel and the coax cable that goes to the RX2 input. Connect its power cable to the unused connector on the motherboard. **You must do this after calibration, not before.**

12.11 Summary Table

The following table lists the main equipment required for an infrastructure base station and its approximate cost.

Item	Model	Approx USD
UHF Antenna	X50N	100
GPS Antenna	Tallysman TW4020	27
LNA	L434LNACN	85
Front-End	Custom	50
Radio	N200+WBX+GPSDO	3270
Computer	Core i7, 8GB	700
Cellular Modem	USB Dongle (or WiFi hot spot)	50
4 N-Type Connectors	Amphenol crimp-crimp	30
N-Type to SMA Jumper	Taoglass ready-made assembly	17
Coax Cable	LMR-400	4/m
Approximate total cost for main components		4329+coax

12.12 Ad-Hoc ATLAS Base Stations

Ad-hoc base stations allow users to test tags in the lab or in the field and to find the direction to tags. Ad-hoc base stations do not report to a server. Section ?? explains how to run an ad-hoc base station.

While you can use an N200 or B200 in an ad-hoc base station, there is a much cheaper and more convenient alternative. We have found that inexpensive radios based on

the RTL2832 chip (so-called *RTL-SDR dongles*) work well. They are widely available on eBay and Amazon. The least expensive ones come with inconvenient antenna connector called MCX. We recommend that you buy one with an SMA connector; they usually also come with better oscillators. Even high-end dongles only cost 20 to 30 USD. Some of these come with a remote control; it is useless unless you plan to watch TV with the dongle.

For testing tags in the lab, small monopole antennas with an SMA connector are convenient. They are available on Digikey and similar distributors for about 8 to 15 USD, or you can buy a bundle of an RTL-SDR with such an antenna.

For direction finding, you need a directional antenna. We normally use a 3-element, 5-element, or 7-element Yagi antennas made by Arrow Antennas⁴ (models 440-3, 440-5, and 440-7; they have a hand grip and cost 50 to 85 USD). These antennas have a BNC connector so you will need a BNC-to-SMA cable, or adapters. We have also had good experience with easy-to-build DIY antennas described in articles by Kent Britain⁵.

⁴<http://www.arrowantennas.com>

⁵<https://www.wa5vjb.com/yagi-pdf/cheapyagi.pdf> and https://www.wa5vjb.com/references/More_cheap_Yagis_2004%20WA5VJB.pdf. For ATLAS tags operating in the 434 MHz license-free band, choose a design for 435 MHz.

Chapter 13

Setting Up Vildehaye Base Stations and ATLAS/Vildehaye Beacons

This chapter explains how to set up Vildehaye base stations and beacons. Vildehaye base stations can identify transmissions from tags, to determine that they are in proximity to the base station, they can be used to home in on tags that transmit Vildehaye identification packets, and they can be used to configure tags through the radio. Beacons that transmit ATLAS codes and/or Vildehaye packets have a very similar structure, so they are also covered here.

There are several ways to set up beacons and base stations. We refer to these setups in the text as *types*. Each use case is best served by a particular type of base station or beacon.

We start by describing the building blocks of base stations and beacons and then move on to describe how the different types of base stations and beacons are put together.

13.1 Launchpad Radios

Beacons and Vildehaye base stations need a radio that is compatible with the radio in our tags (from same series of chips). Evaluation boards made by Texas Instruments (the manufacturer of the chips that power our tags) are the most appropriate and inexpensive radios. These boards are called *Launchpads*, and they come in several flavors, for different frequency bands and with two different generations of RF microcontrollers.

LAUNCHXL-CC1350-4 This version is the best for systems operating on 434MHz. It operates on both 434MHz and 2.4GHz, comes with built-in antennas for both bands, and with convenient connectors (SMA connectors) that allows connection of external antennas, filters, and amplifiers. The built-in antenna for 434MHz has low performance and should only be used when the intended communication range is short (meters or tens of meters).

LAUNCHXL-CC1310 This version is designed for both 868MHz and 915MHz. (It does work on 434MHz, but it is not certified for operation on 434MHz, and its performance on this band is very poor; use CC1350-4 on 434MHz). The built-in antenna is reasonable (but still inferior to external antennas).

Figure 13.1: A LAUNCHXL-CC1350-4 Launchpad.

LAUNCHXL-CC1350 This version comes in two variants, a EU variant for use on 868MHz and 2.4GHz, and a US version for 915MHz and 2.4GHz. The built-in antenna for 868/915 are not as good as on the CC1310 launchpad.

LAUNCHXL-CC1352P-4 A LaunchPad based on the CC1352 RF microcontroller, which has more memory than the CC13X0. This variant (the -4 one) is for 434MHz. It can also transmit and receive on 2.4GHz. The additional memory should allow more features in the future, but it has not been fully tested for Vildehaye base stations.

There are also launchpads for 2.4GHz only which are not currently relevant to ATLAS and Vildehaye so we do not cover them.

13.2 Programming Launchpads

To serve as base stations or beacons, Launchpads must be programmed with Vildehaye firmware. This is a two step process.

The first step, which only needs to be performed once (even if the Launchpad is programmed several times with different Vildehaye firmware), erases the demonstration firmware that is programmed into the Launchpad in the factory.

To erase (blank) the Launchpad, you need to install a free software program called *Texas Instruments Smart RF Programmer 2*. Connect the Launchpad using the provided USB cable and run the following command

```
"\Program Files (x86)\Texas Instruments\SmartRF Tools\Flash Programmer 2\bin\  
→ srfprog.exe" -t lsdix(0) -e all
```


Figure 13.2: Launchpad serial ports in the Windows' Device Manager.

Once the Launchpad has been erased, you can program it with Vildehaye base station firmware, using an ATLAS command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat vh-program basestation serialPort=App@Windows
```

The command will ask you to press two buttons on the Launchpad, the reset button (near the USB connector) and BTN-1 (on the left side, when the USB connector is at the top), and then to release the reset button and then BTN-1 (in that order). This sequence of button presses puts the processor into a mode called *bootloader mode*, in which it can accept firmware from the PC. You will need to press Enter (on the PC) after you press these buttons, which tells the software to try to communicate with the Launchpad and to try to program the firmware onto the processor. When programming ends, the software will tell you to press reset on the Launchpad once more, to cause the firmware to start running, and to press Enter on the PC to terminate the process.

To program a beacon, follow the instructions to program a tag below, but with the Launchpad connected, not a tag.

13.3 An Aside: Specifying Serial Ports

Vildehaye software running on the PC (Windows or Linux) communicates with tags and Launchpads using serial ports. This applies to both the `vh-program` command that programs tags and Launchpads and to the `vh-basestation` command that runs the Vildehaye base station software.

There are several ways to specify the serial port. One is to give the canonical name of the device. Under Windows, these names look like COM8 or COM33. For Launchpads, you can find the name of the serial port by connecting the Launchpad and opening the Windows device manager and looking under *Ports (COM and LPT)*. A Launchpad shows up as two serial port; the one that we need is described as the *Application/User UART*. In the screenshot below, it is COM33. This means that we could have given the command above using the argument `serialPort=COM33` instead of `serialPort=App@Windows`.

The notation App@Windows for the serial port refers to the serial port whose description in the Device Manager contains the text App; specifying the serial port as Application@Windows would have worked too.

Under Linux, the two serial ports of the Launchpad show up as /dev/ttyACM0 and /dev/ttyACM1 (or 1 and 2); it's not easy to tell which is which; you'll have to try. My experience is that the port we need is the one with the lower number.

When you program tags using a USB-to-serial adapter based on an FTDI chip, as we recommend below, you do not need to specify the serial port at all; the software can find it (specifying serialPort=FTD2XX tells the software explicitly that you are using such a bridge, but it's the default, so there is normally no need to specify this).

Under Linux, programming tags using an FTDI USB dongle requires paying attention to two more details. First, when you insert the dongle, the operating system associates with it a driver that allows it to be used as a standard serial port. This driver prevents the ATLAS software from communicating with the dongle, so it needs to be removed. You can do so (after inserting the dongle) using the command:

```
sudo rmmod ftdi_sio
```

You can also tell the operating system to do that automatically. Create a file /etc/udev/rules.d/33-tag.rules containing the following line (thanks to Frank van Maarseveen for figuring this out):

```
SUBSYSTEM=="usb", ATTRS{idVendor}=="0403", ATTRS{idProduct}=="6015", MODE="0660",  
  ↳ GROUP="plugdev" RUN+="/bin/sh -c 'echo $kernel:1.0 > /sys/bus/usb/drivers  
  ↳ /ftdi_sio/unbind'"
```

This will take effect the next time the system reboots, but you can force the change to take effect immediately using the command:

```
sudo udevadm control --reload-rules
```

Second, you will normally not have permissions to communicate with the dongle. You can acquire permissions by running the `vh-program` command under `sudo` or by using the udev rule above and adding your user account to the `plugdev` group.

13.4 Improving the RF Performance of the LaunchPad

A LaunchPad that uses its built-in antenna is easy to set up (does not need to be modified and no other components are needed). The built-in antenna is not particularly good so it has a short communication range. This is useful for configuring tags in the lab or in the field, for short-range data uploads, and for beacons that are only meant to verify that ATLAS or Vildehaye receivers do work.

An external antenna and possibly filters and an amplifier can improve performance. The RF signal of a LaunchPad can be routed either to the built-in antenna or to the coaxial connector. The boards come with the signal routed to the built-in antenna; to use the connector, the board must be modified, typically by moving a small capacitor from one location on the board to another. The manual of each Launchpad specifies the

Figure 13.3: Modifying a LAUNCHXL-CC1350-4 Launchpad to route the signal to the SMA connector.

modification required to route the signal to the connector. These components are small and moving them requires some expertise in soldering small components.

The two images shown in Figure 13.3 show such a modification on LAUNCHXL-CC1350-4. A small 330pF capacitor (size 0402) was removed from the path to the antenna and a slightly larger (0603) capacitor was soldered on the path to the connector.

Note: the Hebrew University may be able to supply Launchpads that have already undergone this modification, and that are already programmed with Vildehaye firmware.

Once the LaunchPad has been modified, you can attach an external antenna to the SMA connector.

You can improve receive performance even further using an antenna amplifier, but this does not allow the base station to transmit (the amplifiers that we use are unidirectional). To do so, connect a front-end unit to the LaunchPad (the one described in Section 12.5). Connect a low-noise amplifier between the antenna and the front-end unit, near the antenna. Plug the DC connector of the front-end unit onto the header pins marked 5V and GND on the left side of the Launchpad (when the USB connector is at the top), with the black wire connected to the GND pin and the red wire to the 5V pin. *This should only be used in receive-only base stations!*

13.5 Power Options for Launchpads

When the Launchpad is connected to a PC (including a Raspberry Pi), the PC provides power to the Launchpad. A USB phone charger can also power LaunchPad; this includes AC (mains) chargers, battery-based chargers, solar chargers, etc.

You can also power a Launchpad from another power source, say a battery; this is primarily useful for beacons. To do that, remove the 11 jumpers that connect two parts of the Launchpad. These jumpers are marked GND, 5V, 3V3, etc. This disconnects the chip that runs the Vildehaye firmware from the large chip near the USB connector, to save power.

Connect the battery to the pins marked GND and 3V3 at the bottom right side of the Launchpad. The Launchpad will work on any voltage between 1.8V and 3.8V. The Launchpad will not be able to provide power to an LNA from the GND and 5V pins on the left side of the Launchpad.

13.6 Jumpers for a Computer-Attached Base Station

In a CC1350 launchpad intended to be used as a base station that is attached to a computer running the ATLAS vh-basestation command, you must connect pins DIO27 and DIO28 with a jumper. In a CC1352P Launchpad, connect DIO16 and DIO17. You can use the jumper from the 5V connection, which is usually not required. This tells the Vildehaye base station software that it should expect a computer to control it rather than act as a standalone logging base station.

13.7 Setting Standalone Logging Base Stations

By adding a *logging board* to a Launchpad, or a group of modules that you can easily buy, you can turn it into a logging base station that can work without a computer. Such a base station can log packets from tags that it hears, can synchronize the clock of tags, and can log sensor data from tags configured to upload data via their radio. The base station knows the time using a GNSS (GPS) receiver contained on the logging board. The base station also logs air pressure, temperature, and humidity (at the base station) and GNSS location fixes. The air-pressure measurements can be used to calibrate measurements from tags to obtain altitude information, assuming that the altitude of the base station is known. The GNSS location fixes can be used to validate the location of the base station, or to support mobile base stations. Logging is done into micro-SD cards.

The firmware currently supports both regular micro-SD cards (capacity up to 2GB) and high-capacity cards, which are marked HC or SDHC (2 to 32GB). There are also larger-capacity cards, SDXC and SDUC, which we have not tested and which might not work.

To set up a logging base station with a logging board, program the base station and then disconnect all the numbers that connect the programming section of the Launchpad to the target (RF microcontroller) section, as shown in Figure 13.4. You can leave the jumpers hanging on one pin so as not to lose them; we have done so to the two extreme jumpers in the picture.

Next, plug in the logging board with the GNSS receiver pointing toward the antenna connectors of the Launchpad, as shown Figure 13.5. If you need to separate the two boards later, use a flat screwdriver to carefully lift the connector. Do not pull on the boards themselves since this can disconnect the connector from the logging board.

Now power the base station by either plugging a micro-USB power supply (from an AC adapter or from a battery; a USB port on a computer will also work) into the micro-USB socket *on the logging board*, as shown in Figure 13.5.

You can also set up a logging base station using easily available external modules, as shown in Figure 13.6. The modules are connected to the LaunchPad using wires that are either soldered directly to the LaunchPad's headers, or soldered to female headers

Figure 13.4: Removing the jumpers that connect the target from the programming section of a Launchpad.

Figure 13.5: A Launchpad with a logging board BoosterPack.

Figure 13.6: A LaunchPad connected to four external modules that allow it to act as a logging base station.

connectors that are plugged into the LaunchPad’s male headers, or using wires with female header connectors.

The modules that you need to connect to the LaunchPad to set up the base station are:

- A u-blox GNSS (GPS) module. The SparkFun SAM-M8Q module with a chip antenna (SparkFun part number GPS-15210, \$40) is an excellent choice. The ZOE-M8Q seems like a good choice if you want to use an external GPS antenna; we have not tested it but it should work. If you use a module with a built-in antenna, make sure it points up to the sky. The module connects to the LaunchPad using 4 wires. They connect the pads marked 3V3 and GND to pins with the same markings on the LaunchPad, and the pads marked RX and TX (UART receive and transmit) to pins DIO26 and DIO25 on the CC1350 LaunchPad.
- A BME280 module allows the base station to record air pressure. The SparkFun SEN-15440 (\$15) is a good choice. It connects to the LaunchPad with 4 wires, 3V3, GND, SCL, and SDA (the last two form a bus called I2C). You can solder them to the LaunchPad, but you can also use the 4-wire connectors on the SparkFun module. These connectors are called *Qwiic* or *Stemma QT* connectors and it is easy to buy compatible cables. If you use the Qwiic connectors, you can either solder a Qwiic cable to the LaunchPad, or use a Qwiic breakout board like the one shown in the figure. Either way, SCL connects to DIO4 and SDA to DIO5 on the CC1350 LaunchPad.
- A 128x32-pixels OLED display with a SSD1306 driver chip. These are available from Adafruit (product ID 4440, \$12.50) and Sparkfun (LCD-17153, \$10) with

a Qwiic connector, or on ebay. You again need to connect GND, 3Vo (compatible with 3V3), SCL, and SDA.

- A micro-SD breakout boards, such as the SparkFun BOB-00544 (\$4.75) shown in the figure. On the CC1350 LaunchPad, connect VCC to 3V3, GND, DO to DIO8, DI to DIO9, SCK to DIO10, CS to DIO11, and CD to DIO22.

You can power the LaunchPad using its USB connector, as shown in the figure, with the LaunchPad jumpers left connected. This is a good choice for a mains connected base station. When operating on batteries, this is not ideal because it this connector also powers the programming part of the LaunchPad, wasting some power. A more efficient scheme is to remove the LaunchPad's jumpers and to connect the output of a 3.3V regulator to the GND and 3V3 pins of the LaunchPad. The SparkFun Buck-Boost Converter (COM15208, \$10) is a good choice, with a 3–16V input voltage (but no USB connector), and so is the Adafruit MPM3610 3.3V converter board (product ID 4683, \$6), with a 4.5-20V input range. In either case, if you power these from a battery with a USB output, you can interface the battery and the converter board with a hacked USB cable or with a USB-C or micro-USB breakout board.

13.8 Using Standalone Logging Base Stations

The display contains four lines. There are several display modes. The default one that you see in the picture shows the status of the radio (Y for active, '-' for not active; the notation is similar for other functions), the time, the status of the base station's clock, whether it is sending acknowledgments to sensor data arriving from tags, whether there is an SD card inserted and active, and whether it received a GNSS/GPS fix.

In the picture, the time shows as 62 seconds; this is the time since the base station was powered, and the Clock status is '-', because the clock has not yet been synchronized. After a few minutes, the time display should change to a number in the billions (seconds since 1970) and the clock status should change to Y.

Once you insert a properly-formatted SD card, the SD-card status should change to Y and the radio status should also change to Y, because a properly-formatted SD card tells the base station on which radio frequency to listen and in what packet format (modulation, data rate, and so on). If you insert an SD card and the status changes to U, it means that the card has not been properly formatted. You can also turn the base station on with the card already inserted.

Before you remove a card to copy the data on it, press the button on the logging board (or the Launchpad button below it, marked BTN-2) until the SD card display changes back to - (a minus sign). Now eject the card physically. You do not need to power off the base station to remove the card, but do tell it (by pressing the button) that you want to eject it before you actually do.

You can change the display mode and turn it off by pressing the other Launchpad button, marked BTN-1. The display cycles between several modes, one of which is completely off (this mode saves a bit of power).

You can also power the base station by soldering wires to the holes marked GND and + on the bottom right of the logging board (when the display is upright). Any voltage

from 1.8V to 5.5V should work. This allows powering the base station with a pair or a triplet of AA or D batteries, lithium-polymer and lithium-ion batteries (but the logger does not protect them from discharging too much).

To format an SD card or to read its contents, insert the card into a reader connected to a Windows computer and run a command shell (`cmd.exe`) as administrator (the commands will not work otherwise). To format a card, issue the command such as:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat sdc card size=8 format all radioSetup=DATA_433_92  
→ basestation=972002000013
```

The `size` argument is always required when using the `sdc card` command; it verifies that you are formatting the correct card. Here I used `size=8` because the card's capacity is 8 GB. Give a number that corresponds to your card's capacity. The `radioSetup` option tells the base station how to configure its radio. The base station number is used to label tag reception reports and sensor measurements from the base station's own sensors. You can use a number using the format of tags, not only the smaller numbers that are normally used to denote ATLAS base stations.

Formatting a large card for the first time takes a long time, about one minute per GB, because the software fills the card with binary ones, to make it easier for base stations to log data. However, when you format a card that has already been formatted and you drop the `all` option, the software only overwrites old data with binary ones, so if the card was not very full, formatting completes much faster.

To retrieve the data, give the command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat sdc card size=8 dump
```

This produces an SQLite file called `vildehaye.sqlite` containing all the data on the card (or it adds to the file if it exists). Chapter 17 explains how to process this file.

Chapter 14

Managing Tagging Metadata

Metadata about the use of ATLAS tags should be uploaded to Movebank, a repository of animal tracking data. ATLAS and Kamadata can retrieve the metadata and can use it to associate tags with animals and with studies.

14.1 Movebank Essentials

Movebank organizes data in studies. A study records tracking and sensing data on a number of individual animals. They can be all of the same species, or of multiple species.

A study in a Movebank study consists of several types of data. ATLAS uses all of the except for events, the data type that contains position and sensor data. These are stored in ATLAS databases. The types of data are:

1. Tags. You can specify the tag's ID (identifying name or number), manufacturer's name and tag model, and other details if appropriate, such as the tag's mass, the type of sensors it has (GPS, radio transmitter, acceleration, and so on), and more.
2. Individual animals under study. You can specify the taxon (species), sex, ring ID, and other details if known.
3. Deployments, which describe a period in which a particular tag is attached to a particular animal. The deployment specifies the animal ID and the tag's ID, the starting date and time of the deployment, and possibly many other details, if known. These details include the ending time of the deployment, the places where the tag was attached and removed and the identity of the persons who attached and removed the tag, etc.
4. Permissions to read and modify study data. Under the sharing menu of the study you can specify which Movebank users can view and download the data, and which Movebank users can modify and upload data.
5. Sensing events, which include GPS localizations, accelerometer data, etc.

The Movebank web site¹ allows researchers to register as Movebank users, and it allows users (and to some extent anonymous users) to view, edit, and upload data. Users can also upload data using spreadsheet files. Movebank also provides interfaces to the data from other software, which ATLAS and Kamadata uses to retrieve data from Movebank (they do not currently upload any data to Movebank).

14.2 How to Describe ATLAS Deployments in Movebank

Users of ATLAS systems should register as Movebank users.

The administrator of the ATLAS system should also register as a user, different from her or his personal Movebank user. This will allow transfer of the administrator user along with the permissions of the user to subsequent administrators of the ATLAS system. We suggest the name `atlas_systemname` for this account (e.g., `atlas_hula` for the administrator of the ATLAS hula system).

Users should open Movebank studies to represent their ATLAS studies. The following rules ensure that ATLAS and Kamadata can use the data in a Movebank study. The rules constrain certain fields in Movebank records. You can fill the other fields as you see fit.

- The name of the study must have the structure `ATLAS systemname studyname`, where `systemname` is the name of the ATLAS system (e.g., `hula`), and `studyname` is whatever name you see fit for the study. In the ATLAS hula system we use study names that specify a species, such as `ATLAS hula Tyto alba`, but for the software, only the first two words in the name are significant.
- Tags should have manufacturer name `ATLAS` and the Tag ID should be the number of the ATLAS tag.
- You should upload tags to Movebank *before* you go out to the field. The real time display in Kamadata can restrict tags to a specific Movebank study, which allows you to focus on your tags and to ignore tags that are part of other studies. This display presents all the tags in a study, whether deployed or not. This allows you to test that tags are working and being localized before you deploy them.
- Once you deploy tags, you should upload them to Movebank. The query mechanisms of ATLAS and Kamadata filter out localizations from before the deployment time and date of a tag, so the output you will obtain only include movement of the animal, not of researchers carrying tags on the way to deploy them.

¹<https://www.movebank.org>

Chapter 15

Programming and Preparing Tags

ATLAS uses a system of miniature and sophisticated radio tags called Vildehaye. Tag consist of an assembled printed circuit board (PCB), like the one shown in Figure15.1, a battery, an antenna, sometimes an add-on board that connects to the PCB, and protective coating. The PCBs arrive from the manufacturer with a blank microprocessor (MCU) that contains no firmware (software) and no identity. This chapter explains how to transform a blank PCB into a functional tag.

Figure 15.1: The main components of a tag.

Before we do that, let us take a closer look at the main components of a tag, indicated in Figure 15.1. The large black component is a radio-frequency microprocessor (RF MCU). It runs the firmware and can transmit and receive radio packets. The radio signal is emitted by an antenna, usually just a piece of wire, which is not part of the PCB; it need to be soldered to a pad on the PCB. *Pads* are conductive surfaces on the PCB that you can solder wires to. They are normally gold plated; the gold plating prevents corrosion and is easy to solder to. The RF MCU is connected to the antenna pad through components that filter the signal and perform impedance matching. On this tag, there are just two components: a ceramic integrated passive component (IPC) and a tiny capacitor. On other tag variants there are sometime more components, inductors and capacitors, in this signal path. The negative terminal of the battery is connected to a *ground pad*; there are sometimes several ground pads. On most tag variants, at least one of them is marked by a the letter G. The positive terminal of the battery is connected to the pad marked with a plus sign (+), which is connected to the MCU's power supply pin, called VDD5¹When the tag transmits, most of the energy comes not directly from the battery, but from a *reservoir capacitor*. The capacitor is charged slowly by the battery between transmissions. Tags have a red indicator light (an LED), mostly to provide visual indication that they have started working. Tags are programmed through a 14-pin miniature connector. The same connector allows you to attach add-on boards to the tag. Not all tag variants

¹The pad marked by the letter R is connected to VDD5 through a 3300 Ohm resistor. It was intended to protect tiny batteries, but does not seem to be particularly helpful.

Figure 15.2: Vildehaye tags and add-on boards. The scale is the same in all the images.

are compatible with all add-on boards. This particular tag variant also contains an environmental sensor (air pressure, temperature, and humidity); most tag variants do not.

The range of current (September 2020) Vildehaye circuit boards for tags and add-on boards is shown in Figures 15.2 and 15.3. First-generation ATLAS tags, which are now obsolete, are described in [TagsEDERC2014]. Tags are marked with a version number. These numbers are essentially arbitrary; a higher version number does not indicate a better tag.

Version 2.6 tags offer full functionality and are the most widely used. The main dif-

Figure 15.3: A Vildehaye add-on board that can switch a load like a miniature motor on and off. The load should be connected to the pads marked '+' and 'S' on the bottom of the board (the two top right pads in the board on the right).

ference between Versions 2.6.1 and 2.6.3 is the inclusion of an environmental sensor on 2.6.3. The RF matching circuit is also a little different. These variants support add-on boards. They are designed for the 434 MHz band.

Versions 2.8 and 2.9 are smaller; they do not support sensor and memory add-on boards, because the communication channels required to communicate with sensors and memory chips are not routed to the connector. They are also designed for the 434 MHz band. They are designed so that the connector can be snapped off after programming, to make the tags even smaller. To snap off, score both sides along the marked line, to cleanly cut the PCB traces (printed wires) that connect the MCU to the tag, and then snap off at the line.

Version 2.9 has a Hall sensor that can sense a nearby magnet. When the tag senses a magnet, it stops transmitting and it disconnects the reservoir capacitor. The capacitor is a bit leaky, so in other tag versions, the capacitor slowly drain the battery even when the tag is inactive. Version 2.9 contains a transistor that can disconnect the capacitor and it does so when the tag is inactive. When you remove the magnet, the tag first slowly charges the capacitor and only then starts transmitting again. The charging period is about 10 seconds.

Version 2.10 works on the 915 and 868 MHz bands. The only component on its bottom, apart from the connector, is the reservoir capacitor. This allows it to function as a radio for a family of tags called Vesper. To use with a Vesper tag, the reservoir capacitor must be removed.

Version 3.0 tags use a separate radio transmitter chip, the AX5031, which is capable of phase modulation. See [**modulation**] for rationale and details. It also works on the 434 MHz band. This is a preliminary design that was not yet optimized for size.

The bottom row in Figure 15.1 shows two add-on boards. Both contain both an inertial sensor (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer), an environmental sensor (air pressure, temperature, and humidity) and a flash memory chip, either a 64 MB chip or an 8 MB chip. Some production runs include an inertial sensor with no magnetometer.

The board shown in Figure 15.3 can switch a load like a small motor or solenoid on and off. It was designed to activate motorized release mechanism for logging tags. The Vildehaye tag turns the motor on for a prescribed number of seconds upon receiving a command from a remote base station.

Figure 15.6: The FT_Prog utility.

The bridge board may need to be configured so that it can move the tag between programming mode and normal operation mode. This is done with a free utility called FT_Prog from FTDI, the manufacturer of the chip. Open the utility, scan for devices, and under *Hardware Specific CBUS Signals* make sure that C0 and C1 are marked GPIO. If they are not, select GPIO and program the chip. The screen should look roughly like the screenshot in Figure 15.6.

After you program the bridge using FT_Prog, unplug it and plug it back in to program tag.

The pin assignments of tag's connector are described in Section A.6 and the pin assignments of the programmer are described in Section A.7.

15.2 Defining Tags and Tag Templates

Vildehaye tags are highly configurable; they can transmit and receive data in a variety of formats using complex schedules that can change when certain triggering events

occur. Because many tags share identical or similar behaviors, we define these behaviors as templates. Templates and tags are usually defined in a configuration file called `vildehaye.txt`.

To define the behavior of a tag, we normally simply select a template. It is also possible to modify certain aspects of the template when defining a tag. Here is the definition of the template for a very simple tag, one that sends an ATLAS code every second and an identification packet once per minute. This template is appropriate for beacons.

```
VHTag, SIMPLE_BEACON_433_92
>,Property, period, 500
>,Property, blinkCounter, 10
>,Property, initialConfiguration, 0_BEACON
>,RadioSetupRef, ID_433_92
>,RadioSetupRef, ATLAS_433_92
>,AtlasCode, CODE, SRSHA1, #TAGID, 8192
>,Configuration, 0_BEACON
>,>,Property, slotCount, 120
>,>,SlotSchedule, ATLAS_433_92, 0, 2, 60, 10, CODE
>,>,SlotSchedule, ID_433_92, 1, 2, 1, 10,
```

The first line defines the name of the template, `SIMPLE_BEACON_433_92`. The second line defines the basic period of the tag, here 500 ms. The third line tells the tag to blink 10 times right after transmissions, but only 10 times. This helps determine that a tag is working after you connect batteries to it.

Templates defines one or more *configurations*, which are states that the tag can be in. Here we have only one configuration, called `0_slow`. In each configuration (state), the tag follows a particular schedule or transmitting and receiving.

Configurations define cycle schedules with a certain number of activity slots that are spaced equally in time, here with a 500 ms period. Our configuration use 120 slots. The `SlotSchedule` command defines how slots are used. The first argument is the name of a *radio setup*, which defines a transmission format and a frequency. Here we use two setups, the `ATLAS_433_92` setup, which defines ATLAS transmissions at 433.92 MHz, and `ID_433_92`, which defines a long-range data transmission at the same frequency. The next arguments in each `SlotSchedule` command are the index of the first slot that uses the setup (starting from 0), the distance in slots between slots that use the same setup (here 2 in both cases), the number of slots that are used (the tag will skip the rest or use them for some other setup), the transmit power (10 dBm=10 mW in all cases here), and a set of options to control how the slots are used.

In this configuration, the tag transmits an ATLAS code 60 times, once per second, in the even slots, and an identification packet once per minute (one time every 120 cycles that last 500 ms each).

To define a tag, we use the same `VHTag` command but with two arguments, a tag number and a template name. For example:

```
VHTag, 972002000095, ATLAS_ID_1S_433_92
```

When defining a tag, you can specify properties that override those defined in the template. For example, the following definition defines a tag that blinks 20 times, not 10:

```
VHTag, 972002000095, ATLAS_ID_1S_433_92
>,Property,blinkCounter,20
```

The next template is more complex. It defines two configurations, one in which the tag only transmits its identification 3 times (and listens for commands 2 times) every 2 minutes; this configuration is designed to save battery power between the tag is prepared and the time it is deployed. The other configuration sends the same ID packets every 2 minutes, but also sends an ATLAS code every second. The tag switches between the two configurations when it receives appropriate commands through the radio.

```
VHTag, ATLAS_ID_1S_433_92
>,Property, period, 500
>,Property, initialConfiguration, 0_SLOW
>,Property, blinkCounter, 10
>,RadioSetupRef, ATLAS_433_92
>,RadioSetupRef, ID_433_92
>,AtlasCode, CODE, SRSHA1, #TAGID, 8192
>,Configuration, 0_SLOW
>,>,Property, slotCount, 240
>,>,SlotSchedule, ATLAS_433_92, 255, 2, 1, 10, CODE
>,>,SlotSchedule, ID_433_92, 0, 2, 5, 10, ALLOW_RESPONSE
>,Configuration, 1_FAST
>,>,Property, slotCount, 240
>,>,SlotSchedule, ATLAS_433_92, 1, 2, 120, 10, CODE
>,>,SlotSchedule, ID_433_92, 0, 2, 5, 10, ALLOW_RESPONSE
>,Trigger
>,>, Property, type, WAKEUP
>,>, Property, index, 1
>,>, Property, fromConfiguration, 0_SLOW
>,>, Property, fromSetup, ID_433_92
>,>, Property, toConfiguration, 1_FAST
>,Trigger
>,>, Property, type, WAKEUP
>,>, Property, index, 0
>,>, Property, fromConfiguration, 1_FAST
>,>, Property, fromSetup, ID_433_92
>,>, Property, toConfiguration, 0_SLOW
```

15.3 Programming Tags

The ATLAS command `vh-program` downloads firmware into tags and configures them. The required firmware files are part of the ATLAS distribution. Programming a tag with this command requires four options:

```
system=name    for example, hula
dir=directory for example, c:\svn\atlas-configuration\hula
tag=id        for example, 972001000078
hex=filename  for example, vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6.hex
```

The `dir` argument is only required if the tag emits ATLAS codes. The directory specified by this argument should be a directory that contains configuration files checked out of

SVN. It should not refer to a directory such as `~\.atlas\hula` that contains configuration files that ATLAS cached. The program will read the definition of Vildehaye tags from a configuration file in this directory (normally from `vildehaye.txt`), and if the tag transmits ATLAS codes, the command will modify another file in the same directory, `vh-schedules.txt`. The modification adds or replaces the description of the ATLAS transmission schedule of the tag, for use by base stations.

The use of a directory that you checked from SVN allows you to define tags and to program them without committing configuration changes to SVN. This helps reduce the number of times that ATLAS base stations and servers restart. You should prepare tags using an SVN-checked-out set of configuration files, test the tags and their definition using these files, and only when you are done defining all the tags, commit the files back to SVN. You must commit both `vh-schedules.txt` and `vildehaye.txt`.

If you must run `vh-program` on a directory that you did not check out from SVN, give it the argument `override` to allow this. This is not normally advised, however, because you usually do need to update the SVN configuration files in order for base stations to operate normally.

If you use an ATLAS ad-hoc base station, you can give the same `dir=directory` option to the receiver command. This allows the receiver to detect the tag even if you have not yet committed `vh-schedules.txt` to SVN.

15.4 Additional Modes of the Programming Command

The `vh-program` command can take a few more options:

`list` shows the available firmware files and their build dates
`read` extracts and prints the configuration of a tag

The `vh-program` command has yet another mode that we cover later.

15.5 Finishing the Tags: Batteries, Antennas, and Coating

This section describes types of batteries, antenna wires, and coating materials that users have successfully used to produce tags, as well as some production procedures. Kenward's *A Manual for Wildlife Radio Tagging* [Kenward2nd], although somewhat old, is still worth consulting if you are starting to produce tags.

15.5.1 Batteries

Vildehaye tags operate at voltages of 1.8 to 3.8 V. They can be powered by a wide range of primary Lithium batteries, by a pair of Silver Oxide batteries, and even by a pair of alkaline AA or AAA batteries.

Lithium coin-cell primary (single-use) batteries are probably the most common type that is used with tags. Users have successfully used coin-cell batteries ranging from CR1025 (10 mm diameter, 2.5 mm thick, 0.7 g) all the way to CR2477 (10.5 g). The CR series

have Lithium Manganese Oxide (Li/MnO₂) chemistry. Some users have had reliability issues with CR1025, so perhaps using larger batteries is a safer option.

Pairs of 1.55 V Silver Oxide (Zn/Ag₂O) batteries work very well. They start at very small masses: type 337 weigh 0.13 g each, and have been successfully used in tags.

For larger tags, users often use Lithium Thionyl Chloride batteries, like the LS14500 from Saft² (17 g) or the TL-4902 (9.6 g) from Tadiran³.

The 64 MB flash chips that are used on some logging boards require at least 2.7 V, so they limit the range of batteries that can be used.

Tags do not have battery holders; batteries are attached to the tag with wires. Soldering the wire to the tag is easy. Soldering a wire to a battery is possible but requires skill, as described in the next section. Some lithium coin cells, like CR2032, are widely available with tabs, which makes it easier to prepare tags.

If you prepare tags for future activation, solder a wire to the positive terminal of the battery and a wire to the VDDS pad on the tag (marked +) and leave them outside the coating materials. To activate the tag, solder the two together and cover the joint with a bit of epoxy.

Figure 15.7: A Panasonic CR2032/F4N battery with soldering tabs; the F4N suffix indicates the existence and type of tabs.

15.5.2 Soldering Batteries

ATLAS users have used a specialized technique to reliably solder wires to miniature batteries. We learned about the technique from Julian Kapoor from Cornell and from Beat Naef-Daenzer from the Swiss Ornithological Institute. Their comments are reprinted below. Yoav Bartan prepared a video showing a variant of this technique [**SolderingBatteries**]. Watching it is highly recommended if you are about to try this technique out.

Julian Kapoor described the technique as follows:

The technique is outlined in detail in *A Manual for Wildlife Radio Tagging* by Kenward [**Kenward2nd**], and takes a little practice to get right, but works very well. The basic procedure is to make a small loop of wire (the loop should be ~1mm in diameter) to dip into phosphoric acid. A small dot of acid is then placed onto the center of the battery using the wire loop. Tin a wire to be used as a lead and lay it over the dot and then quickly brush a very lightly tinned soldering iron over the wire (I've experimented with a stabbing motion versus a wiping motion and find that wiping leaves less solder). Be aware that the acid could wick up the lead and onto the gasket of the battery, which would ruin it (using less acid helps avoid this). I then take the whole battery and dip it into distilled water to help remove the acid

²<https://www.saftbatteries.com>

³<http://www.tadiran.com/>

residue (scrubbing helps). Repeat for the other lead. As the wire on the negative lead can bend and bridge over to the positive lead easily I usually place some epoxy near the edge of the battery, let it harden, then place the lead over it and place more epoxy.

The phosphoric acid should be a 5% to 10% solution. Beat Naef-Daenzer added:

Soldering small cells using acid flux proved very reliable in my assembling transmitters for very small birds. Zinc-Air cells are likely to be especially delicate, but these appear not to suffer, either. The following may further facilitate soldering small cells:

- Sticking the battery on one of those very strong button-magnets creates an efficient heat sink.
- Using fine solder tips (those for working small surface-mount components) help avoiding excessive heat transfer.
- The smaller the cell, the finer the wire that should be used for connections.

With some experience it is possible to get perfect solder points in a part of a second. Wiping as Julian describes is excellent.

15.5.3 Antennas

Vildevhaye tags normally use a *monopole* antenna consisting of a single insulated wire that is soldered to the antenna pad on the tag. The antenna should be roughly $\lambda/4$ long, where λ is the wavelength, about 70 cm at 434 MHz. We have experimentally found that slightly shorter antennas, about 16.5 cm, appear to work a little better. Monopole antennas that are attached to such small tags have poor radiation efficiency (most of the RF energy is not radiated), but we have not found a better alternative.

Most tag variants have a ground pad next to the antenna pad or on the opposite side of the board. If you can attach another wire with the same length to this ground pad and form the two so that they are spread apart (with an angle of 60 to 180 degrees, say, the more the better), radiation efficiency should improve significantly. This type of antenna is called a *dipole*. This might be possible on fairly large collars, for example.

Most of the following information on antenna materials was contributed by Yoav Bartan.

Many ATLAS/Vildevhaye users have found that *49-strand gold-plated beading wire* works very well. This is a multi-strand stainless steel gold-plated wire with a nylon coating. Gold is an excellent conductor and is easy to solder. The wire is soft and flexible and the nylon coating protects it. To attach to a tag, strip the nylon coating from the end of the wire and solder. This wire is manufactured for hobby applications by several companies, including

Figure 15.8: Gold-plated beading wire.

Beadalon⁴, Accu-Flex⁵, and others, and is often available in hobby shops. The 0.018 or 0.019 inch-thick version is good for species that are not likely to chew on the antenna and the 0.024 inch variety for more aggressive species.

The stainless-steel silver plated versions should be fine and are less expensive, but we do not have much experience with them. These wires are also offered in versions that are not gold plated but rather painted; do not use them (not even the gold-color version). The 19-strand and 7-strand versions are less flexible.

For particularly aggressive species, users reinforce the antenna with heat-shrink tubing, sometimes in two layers (e.g., with 1.17 mm inner-diameter 3M MPF tubing, and then with heat-shrink tubing with glue).

Users also successfully use 2.1 mm thick bicycle shifter cable made from galvanized steel, which is easy to solder. The stainless steel variety is difficult to solder to the tag and hence less recommended.

Another type of wire that can be used is *nylon-coated single-strand stainless steel wire* manufactured for fishing applications, where it is referred to as a *leader*. It is made by Malin⁶ and comes in a wide range of thicknesses, starting from 0.01 inch. This type of wire is stiff and springy. The thinner versions kink fairly easily, but it appears impossible to tear or chew off. Steel is not a good electrical conductor, but it does work as an antenna. Steel is also difficult to solder. To solder this type of antenna to a tag, remove the plastic coating from the end of the wire, polish it to remove any remaining nylon and any corrosion, dip in a pickle solution, then coat with solder. *Pickling* is a chemical cleaning process that makes it possible to solder steel. Users have used 5% to 10% solution of phosphoric acid to pickle this wire; sulfuric acid is hazardous, so if you use it, take appropriate precautions.

15.5.4 Coating

Most of the following information on coating materials was contributed by Yoav Bartan.

After the battery and antenna have been soldered to the tag, it should be *sealed* to protect it from moisture, electrical shorts, and contaminants. Users have successfully used clear 3M 1601-C electrical insulating sealer, which comes in a spray can. It looks and feels like a lacquer when dry.

If the battery is placed on the top or bottom of the tag (as opposed to behind it), separate it from the tag with a piece of electrical tape, after the tag has been sealed.

Tags that must be as lightweight as possible can simply be covered with a few more coats of sealer should be applied.

Tags that should be more robust and can be a little heavier should be potted in epoxy resin. Some users use EPOKUKDO YD-114 resin with Kukdo DOCURE KH-816 curing

⁴<https://www.beadalon.com>

⁵<http://www.accuflexwire.com/>

⁶<https://malinco.com/>

Figure 15.9: The E79-400DM2005S module. The module comes with a metal shield. The second image from the right shows the electronics beneath the shield.

agent; both are manufactured by Kukdo. The epoxy can be mixed with glass bubbles at a volume ratio of 1:1.5 to 1:2 (more bubbles than epoxy) to reduce weight. Another type of epoxy that has been successfully used is 3M Epoxy Potting Compound DP270; it is more viscous and less suitable for mixing with glass bubbles. This material comes in both black and clear.

Techniques used by other tag makers should probably also work. Deng et al. seal injectable fish tags with Parylene-C, coat them with 3M Scotchcast Electrical Resin 5 using a mold, and then apply another layer of Parylene-C [InjectibleFish2015].

15.6 Using an Ebyte E79 Module as a Tag

A company called Ebyte (www.ebyte.com) manufactures a 20-by-32 mm module that contains a CC1352P RF microcontroller, shown in Figure 15.9. The module, marked E79-400DM2005S, can transmit and receive on the 434 MHz band and on the 2.4 GHz band. The module can transmit on 434 MHz at either 10 mW, like a CC1310 or CC1350, or, using a built-in power amplifier, at up to 100 mW. These are nominal values and the output in practice is lower, about 9 dBm and 16 dBm, respectively. The module requires an external antenna for 434 MHz but has a built-in antenna for 2.4 GHz.

The modules weigh 2.82 g. If you remove the metal shield, the mass drops to 1.75 g (the shield is designed to reduce harmful interference and should ideally be left on the module). They cost around \$10 on web sites such as ebay and aliexpress. They are also available for the 868 and 915 MHz bands.

The same company also makes slightly cheaper (around \$6) and slightly smaller modules based on the CC1310 (E70-433T14S2; 1.18 g or 0.78 g with the shield removed). These lack the 32 kHz crystal that regulates the ping frequency of tags, but if you add a crystal between two pads of the module, it can be programmed to function as an ATLAS/Vildehaye tag.

The modules can be used as a tag or as part of a Vildehaye base station.

When used as a tag, the module contains all the required components except for a battery, antenna, and a reservoir capacitor. The capacitor is required for small batteries but can probably be omitted when the module is used with large batteries or with batteries that include a capacitor, like some Tadiran lithium batteries. They do not have an indicator LED.

The modules are designed to be soldered to a larger circuit board so it is a bit challenging to program them. You need to solder wires between certain pads of the module and two other boards, a CC1352 LaunchPad that is used once to erase the memory of the module, and a Vildehaye adapter that is used to program the module. The following table shows which pads to connect to where.

CC1352 Function	E79 Pad	CC1310 Function	E70 Pad	Connect to:
GND	4,14,15,26,27,37	GND	1,2,3,9,10,15,23	LaunchPad GND
VCC	36	VCC	8	LaunchPad 3.3V
RESET_N	25	RESET_N	14	LaunchPad RST
JTAG_TMSC	16	JTAG_TMSC	19	LaunchPad TMS
JTAG_TCLK	17	JTAG_TCLK	18	LaunchPad TCK
GND	4,14,15,26,27,37	GND	1,2,3,9,10,15,23	Vildehaye Adapter GND
VCC	36	VCC	8	Vildehaye Adapter VCC
RESET_N	25	RESET_N	14	Vildehaye Adapter RST
DIO_12	10	DIO_1	21	Vildehaye Adapter RX
DIO_13	11	DIO_2	20	Vildehaye Adapter TX
DIO_15	13	DIO_6	12	Vildehaye Adapter SE
X32K_Q1	(on board)	X32K_Q1	4	32768Hz crystal
X32K_Q2	(on board)	X32K_Q2	5	32768Hz crystal
		DIO_0	22	optional LED

To erase the module, connect the LaunchPad wires to the programming side of the LaunchPad with all the programming jumpers removed from the LaunchPad. Connect the LaunchPad to a computer and run Texas Instruments' *Flash Programmer 2* from within *SmartRF Studio*. Erase the chip. This is a one time operation, once the module has been erased it can be programmed over and over again using the Vildehaye Adapter only.

Now connect the Vildehaye Adapter wires, connect the adapter to a computer using an FTDI dongle, and program the module just like any other tag model.

A wire antenna can be soldered to Pin 2 of the module. More elaborate antennas can be connected using the coax connector on the module. The connector type is called IPEX or U.FL and you can purchase coax jumpers with this connector on one side and an SMA or N connector on the other, to connect to an external antenna (e.g., for Beacons).

In normal operation as a tag, only the antenna and GND and VCC pads need to be wired.

The e79 module requires special firmware. The e70 module uses the firmware for V2.6 tags.

Chapter 16

Using Sensor Logging Boards

Some types of Vildehaye tags can be fitted with add-on boards. Two sensor logging add-on boards are shown on the bottom row of Figure 15.2. They contain an inertial sensor with a 3-axis accelerometer, a 3 axis gyroscope, and a 3-axis magnetometer, an environmental sensor that measures air pressure, temperature, and humidity, and a memory chip. (Some production runs produced boards in which the inertial sensor does not contain a magnetometer.)

The sensor logger connects to the tag through the same connector that is used to program tags. Sensor loggers have both male and female connectors so a tag+logger ensemble can be attached to the programming adapter board, as shown in Figure 16.1.

The connectors carry power and two types of data channels, an I2C bus and an SPI bus. The I2C bus is used to communicate with the sensors and the SPI bus is used to communicate with the memory chip.

The connectors snap together but you should not rely on them for mechanical strength.

Figure 16.1: A tag with an attached sensor board connected to the programming adapter.

You should use some other mechanism to hold the two boards together (heat-shrink tubing, glue, etc).

In the smaller Vildehaye tag designs, the I2C and SPI are not routed to the programming connector, so logger boards cannot be attached to these tags. Currently this includes versions 2.8 and 2.9. Version 2.6 is compatible with the logger boards.

One tag variant, Version 2.6.3, contains an on-board environmental sensor; it can log a small amount of environmental data onto the on-board memory.

16.1 Sensor Logging Boards and their Constraints

We currently have two sensor logging designs. Both are about 1 cm by 2 cm. They differ mostly in the memory chip that they contain.

Both use a Bosch Sensortec BMX160 accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer, and a Bosch Sensortec BME280 pressure, temperature, and humidity sensor. Early production runs used the BMI160 rather than the BMX160; it lacks the magnetometer.

Both boards contain a Macronix NOR flash chip. Flash chips come in two main variants, NOR and NAND. NOR is easier to use. NAND is more difficult to use (it may contain faulty areas and suffers from other complications) but is denser, in the sense that it contains more bits per square centimeter (and also per dollar). The larger board can also accommodate NAND chips (instead of the NOR chip) but the firmware currently does not support NAND flash.

The slightly larger board shown in Figure ?? contains a Macronix MX66L5123F, a 64 MB device. It is designed to work at voltages of 2.7 to 3.6 V, with 4 V being the absolute maximum supply voltage allowed.

The smaller board contains an 8 MB Macronix MX25R6435F. It is more tolerant to supply voltage variations, working from 1.65 to 3.6 V.

CC13XX Launchpads contain another flash chip from Macronix, the 1 MB MX25R8035F. We used it for firmware development but it is not otherwise important.

For comparison, the CC13XX RF microcontrollers work from 1.8 to 3.8 V, with an absolute maximum of 4.1 V. The BME280 and BMI160 both work from 1.71 to 3.6 V.

The main implication of this discussion is that the smaller logger boards are more tolerant of battery voltage variations and will work with any battery voltage that is good for the RF microcontroller and for the sensors (the range of 1.8 to 3.6 V). The larger board has more memory but the flash will not work if battery voltage sags significantly below 2.7 V. Therefore, the larger boards are best used with either physically large batteries or with Lithium chemistries that start around 3.6 V, not around 3.0 V.

16.2 Power Consumption and Battery Life Spans

We now describe the energy used by the sensors and flash memory, to help you estimate the life span of tags with different batteries and different sensor configurations.

Our reference will be a single ATLAS transmission, which consumes about 50mW while transmitting or about 0.4 mJ for a standard 8 ms transmission.

Running the accelerometer in the BMI160 consumes 180 μA (we use it in Normal Mode to allow long sampling periods, which requires using this mode; in principle, bursts of up to about 145 samples can use the Low Power Mode which consumes much less power). Assuming a battery voltage of 3 V, the accelerometer consumes the same amount of energy as an ATLAS transmission every 741 ms.

Running the accelerometer for 10 seconds accelerometer consumes about the same amount of energy as 13.5 ATLAS transmissions. Running it for 10 s every 120 increases the average power consumption of a tag that transmits an ATLAS transmission every second by only 11%.

We also need to consider the power required to store the sensor data and if it is downloaded remotely, the energy to transmit it.

Every accelerometer reading consumes a little over 7 bytes (three 2-byte values plus a header byte). Writing a page of 256 bytes takes about 1 ms and consumes about 60 mW. Therefore, the amount of energy required for one ATLAS transmission is the same as storing to flash about 1700 bytes or 243 accelerometer samples. In other words, storing the data from a 10 s, 25 Hz accelerometer burst requires the same amount of energy as one ATLAS transmission. If we sample for the same period but at 100 Hz, sampling takes the same amount of energy, but storing the data takes 4 times more energy.

The energy to transmit one packet of data is similar to the energy required to transmit an ATLAS transmission. These data transmissions usually carry 100 to 200 bytes of data. Even if every byte in the log is transmitted only once, it takes 10 times more energy to transmit the byte than to store it in flash. Still, the energy required to transmit a burst of 250 accelerometer measurements is comparable to 12 ATLAS transmissions.

However, in some situations the tag may transmit data bytes more than once, if it cannot hear an acknowledgment from a base station. This is mostly a problem in situations in which a base station is reachable but only barely. If base stations are too far, the tag stops transmitting data; if a base station is close enough and there is not too much interference, it will acknowledge most packets.

Storing and transmitting BME280 air-pressure measurements requires 4 bytes per sample. Most of the energy costs associated with this sensor are negligible when sensing at a rate of 1 Hz or lower.

Another important aspect to consider is the power consumed by sensors and memory when they are idle, not doing anything. The CC13XX consumes very little in sleep mode, about 3.6 μW (1 μA at 3.6 V). Sleeping for about 110 seconds consumes the same amount of energy as one ATLAS transmission. However, the reservoir capacitor that we place on most tags leaks about 20 times more energy than the CC13XX.

The 64 MB NOR flash chips leaks about 4 μA but can leak up to 40 μA . So in most cases it leaks a lot less than the capacitor, but it can leak twice as much as the capacitor in some cases (which the data sheet does not specify; perhaps high temperatures).

The BMI160 consumes 3 to 10 μA in sleep mode. The BME280 consumes almost nothing in sleep mode.

16.3 Clock Synchronization

Sensor data is time stamped with the tag's local real-time clock. Initially, the clock counts the number of seconds since the tag was powered, but it can also be set to some other value.

The clock can be set to the correct value (seconds since 1970) by a base station that knows the time. We recommend that most logging tags allow this (include `BEACON_CLOCK` in their configuration) and that a Vildehaye base station will operate in the area where tags are powered, to set their clock shortly after being powered up. An ad-hoc base station is sufficient, as long as it is connected to a computer that knows the correct time.

Tags in this configuration may adjust their clock while in the field, if their clock has drifted relative to the clock of a nearby base station that knows the time. These adjustments may cause small jumps (several seconds) in the time stamps of logged data.

Another mechanism to synchronize between on-tag time stamps and real time is described in Section 17.3 below.

16.4 Using Sensor Loggers: An Overview

To use a sensor logger, you need to perform the following tasks:

1. Prepare a sensor-logger board by erasing its flash-memory chip. Erasure takes a fairly long time (about 100 s on the 64 MB chips we currently use), which implies that it requires a significant amount of energy (about the same as transmitting ATLAS codes at 1 Hz for 2.7 hours), so we erase the memory when the logger board is connected to a computer, not using the tag's batteries. This also eliminates the risk that a bug will cause the tag to erase the log after it has been partially filled.
2. Program a tag using a firmware that supports logging (e.g, using `hex=vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6-logger.hex`) and using a template that includes sensing. We will explain how sensing is configured in the template.
3. Attach the tag to the logger board, complete the construction of the tag (coating, etc) and attach batteries. The tag will use the sensors periodically and will record the measurements to the flash-memory chip.
4. The tag's template can allow downloading of the sensor measurements through the tag's radio. Currently, data that is downloaded is not erased. Downloading is done through Vildehaye base stations.
5. If you can retrieve the tag and if the connectors (or at least one of them) is or can be exposed, you can also copy the sensor measurements to a file by connecting the tag, or at least the logger board, to a computer.
6. In principle, the logger board can then be erased and reused, if it is in physically good condition.

16.5 The Structure of the Log

Vildehaye tags write to the flash memory an ordered sequence of *data items*. The most important data items contain sensor measurements, usually a few, so that the contents of each data item consist of 100 to 224 bytes. Other data items specify the identity of the tag, how the sensors were configured, the random bits associated with ATLAS transmissions (each transmission carries one bit, and the sequence is useful; see below), and so on.

Sensor data items are time stamped. The time stamp has a whole-second resolution (if the sensor use used in a bursty periodic mode, the time stamp is of the beginning of the burst). The time stamp uses the tag's real-time clock, which should be set after batteries are attached to the tag, and which may drift over time.

Long bursts of measurements are fragmented, so that each fragment fits within one data item. Software can assemble the fragments back into a continuous burst, but only if all the fragments are present. If some fragments of a burst are missing, only the beginning of the burst is reconstructed. Missing fragments prevent the use of fragments that follow the missing one(s) because we cannot always know how many measurements the missing fragment(s) contain.

If a tag restarts (e.g., because you disconnected and reconnected the battery), it finds the last data item in the log and continues to write past it. Old data is not erased.

16.6 Remote Downloading of the Log

Vildehaye base stations can download data items from logging tags, if the tag's template allows this.

In a tethered base station, the base station software on the computer stores data items that the radio receives and in an SQLite file. The radio acknowledges data before it is transferred to the computer for storage, so if the program on the computer crashes or is stopped, some data items may be lost. Normally this is not a serious problem, since data items may be lost due to other reasons too (running out of space, low battery voltage, etc).

In a standalone base station, received data items are stored into a micro-SD card. Data is stored on this card in using the same log structure that tags use.

The tag remembers the position in the log before which all the data has been downloaded and acknowledged. This information is stored in volatile memory but is committed to flash once in a while. If a tag restarts, it finds this information in the log and continues to download from that point on. Because the download marker on flash may be a bit old, some data items may be downloaded more than once. The duplicates are detected and discarded when inserted into the database.

16.7 Preparing the Flash Controller

To format the memory chip and to read its content after a tag has been retrieved, you need an adapter that can control the flash of a logger board. This *flash controller* can

Figure 16.2: A Launchpad serving as a flash controller. The logging board is attached to the adapter, which is connected to specific LaunchPad pins.

be either a normal V2.6 tag connected to a programming dongle or a CC1350 Launchpad hooked up to a Vildehaye adapter board in a way that allows the CC1350 on the Launchpad to access the memory on an attached logger board. Either way, they need a special firmware that enables them to function as flash controllers.

We will start with the simpler option, of using a normal tag. Connect a Version 2.6 tag to a programmer and program it with the `not-a-tag` option and the flash-controller firmware ; you do need to specify a system name or a tag number.

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat vh-program not-a-tag hex=vildehaye-
  ↪ flashcontroller-cc13x0-v2-6.hex
```

If you decide instead to use a CC13X0 LaunchPad (not particularly recommended, but documented here for completeness), prepare it by making the following connections between the Launchpad and the programming adapter:

CC13X0 LaunchPad		Vildehaye Adapter
GND	↔	GND
3V3	↔	VDDS
DI08	↔	MISO
DI09	↔	MOSI
DI010	↔	SCK
DI011	↔	CS1

Programming the LaunchPad with appropriate flash-controller firmware is similar to programming a tag, but you need to specify the name of the serial port using the `serialPort=App@Windows` option on Windows and using `serialPort=/dev/ttyACM0` option on Linux; see Section 13.3.

16.8 Using the Flash Controller

The flash controller is used for two key actions: formatting a logger board and downloading the data from a used board. Formatting consists of erasing the flash chip and writing a small header on it, with a current time stamp. The time stamp can be used to distinguish between multiple uses of the same tag.

First, set up the flash controller. If you use a LaunchPad, insert a logger board into the flash controller. You can do this while the LaunchPad is connected to a computer via the USB cable. If you use a tag, attach the flash-controller-tag to the logger board and then attach the entire assembly to the programming adapter; the logger board should be on the bottom (connected directly to the adapter).

The Java program that communicates with the flash controller (invoked with atlas.bat flashcontroller) expects the flash controller to have just been freshly reset. If you use a tag connected to an programmer, just take it out of the USB port and re-insert to reset. If you use a LaunchPad, press its reset button to reset. When the flash controller is waiting for the Java program to communicate with it, its LED blinks slowly. After communication starts, the LED turns off. If the flash controller cannot detect a flash chip, it blinks quickly, indicating a problem.

Check first that the controller can access the memory, without erasing. We do this by running the flashcontroller command without giving any sub-command. If you use a Launchpad, use serialPort=App@Windows; if you use a tag, use serialPort=USB@Windows or don't use a serialPort option at all.

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat flashcontroller serialPort=...
...
14:56:47 [Thread-1] INFO tau.atlas.vildehaye.SerialPortRXTX - Found port for
  ↳ pattern App: COM66 (XDS110 Class Application/User UART (COM66))
14:56:47 [Thread-1] INFO tau.atlas.vildehaye.SerialConnection - setting up the
  ↳ serial port
14:56:47 [Thread-1] INFO tau.atlas.vildehaye.SerialPortRXTX - baud rate (pre-
  ↳ setup) is 9600
14:56:47 [Thread-1] INFO tau.atlas.vildehaye.SerialPortRXTX - baud rate (post-
  ↳ setup) is 115200
Trying to communicate with tag (waiting for keepalive)...
KEEPALIVE packet!
Got a response from tag, continuing
ACK for ID
manufacturer c2
memory type 20
density 1a
type 1 (1==NOR, etc)
flash size 67108864 B
sector size 4096 B
page 256 B
free addr 00000000
catalog ver 1
flash size = 67108864 first free flash address = 00000000 Check the size!
```

The size seems fine (about 64 MB) so we continue to erasing the flash and formatting it. Reset the Launchpad again and run the flashcontroller command with the format sub-command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat flashcontroller format serialPort=...
...
Trying to communicate with tag (waiting for keepalive)... Press Enter if
  ↳ requested
KEEPALIVE packet!
Got a response from tag, continuing
ACK for ID
manufacturer c2
memory type 20
density 1a
```

```

type 1 (1==NOR, etc)
flash size 67108864 B
sector size 4096 B
page 256 B
free addr 00000000
catalog ver 1
flash size = 67108864 first free flash address = 00000000
FORMATTING WILL ERASE ALL THE DATA ON THE BOARD!
Press enter to continue, control-C to abort. Press Enter
  This will take a while, about 2 seconds per MB...
Erasing... This takes a while, wait
ACK for CHIP_ERASE
time 107.59
ACK for ID
manufacturer c2
memory type 20
density 1a
type 1 (1==NOR, etc)
flash size 67108864 B
sector size 4096 B
page 256 B
free addr 00000000
catalog ver 1
flash size = 67108864 first free flash address = 00000000
Format!
CATAOG_ID CMD:
ACK for LOG
return code = 0 (0==success)
before addr = 00000000
after addr = 0000001c
logged 28 so far, log header
CATAOG_ID CMD:
ACK for LOG
return code = 0 (0==success)
before addr = 0000001c
after addr = 00000022
logged 34 so far, catalog id
ACK for COMMIT
return code = 0 (0==success)
before addr = 00000022
after addr = 00000100
committed!

```

Erasing the 64 MB NOR chip takes about 100 s (almost 2 minutes), so be patient. If you run the command again with no sub-commands, the first free address on flash should be 00000100 (this is in base 16 and it represents the decimal number 256); the first page contains the header of the log.

To download the data from an logger board, attach it to the flash controller and issue the dump sub-command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat flashcontroller dump serialPort=...
```

This reads all the data items from the log and stores them in an SQLite database with filename `vildehaye.sqlite`.

Assuming that you use a tag as a flash controller, dumping data is much faster with the `serialPort=USB@Windows` option than with no `serialPort` option. This is due to the high overhead of the serial library that we use in the no-option case.

16.9 Faster Dumping through a Raspberry Pi

Dumping the contents of a log through the flash controller is quite slow. A faster method uses a Raspberry Pi to copy the contents of the memory chip on a sensor-logging board into a file. The log is then extracted from the file in a `vildehaye.sqlite` file.

To use this method, connect 6 pins of the Raspberry Pi 40-pin connector to an adapter board as follows:

Raspberry Pi 40-Pin Connector		Vildehay Adapter
GND 6	↔	GND
3V3 1	↔	VDDS
SPI0 MISO 21	↔	MISO
SPI0 MOSI 19	↔	MOSI
SPI0 SCLK 23	↔	SCK
SPI0 CE0 24	↔	CS1

Now run the command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\linux-arm71\flashrom -p linux_spi:dev=/dev/spidev0.0 -r
↪ filename.bin
```

The command `flashrom` might be installed on your Raspberry Pi's operating system, but the built-in version that I tested did not support the specific flash chip on the sensor-logging board. The version inside `atlas-distribution` does.

The file that was created should contain a copy of the contents of the flash chip. Run an ATLAS command to extract the log from it::

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.sh sensorlog-image dump filename.bin
```

You can run this command on another computer, including on a Windows computer (you'll need to copy the file to it first, of course).

16.10 Using Tags with On-Board Sensors and No External Flash Memory

Tags version 2.6.3 include an air-pressure sensor. The tag can log sensor measurements into its built-in flash memory. The amount of memory available for logging in the

built-in memory is small, tens of kilobytes, but it may nevertheless be useful for certain applications.

To use, program the tag with firmware that supports sensor measurements and logging into the built-in memory, and add the `log` option that tells the software to format a log in the memory that remains after the firmware has been programmed into the chip.

```
... \atlas.bat vh-program system=... dir=... tag=... hex=vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2
  ↪ -6-altimeter.hex log
```

To download the data from the log, use the same command but with the `dump` option. The software will read the log from the end until it reaches a sector that starts with a header and will then dump the log records into an SQLite database.

```
... \atlas.bat vh-program dump
```

16.11 Tag Templates for Sensing and Logging

For our tests, we programmed tags with a template similar to the following one:

```
VHTag, LOGGER_433_92
>,Property, period, 250
>,Property, logger, true
>,Property, blinkCounter, 20
>,Property, initialConfiguration, 0_ATLAS
>,RadioSetupRef, DATA_433_92
>,RadioSetupRef, ATLAS_433_92
>,AtlasCode, CODE, SRSHA1, #TAGID, 8192
>,Configuration, 0_ATLAS
>,>,Property, slotCount, 120
>,>,SlotSchedule, ATLAS_433_92, 0, 4, 30, 10, CODE, RANDOM_SIGN
>,>,SlotSchedule, DATA_433_92, 119, 4, 1, 0, BEACON_CLOCK
>,Configuration, 1_ATLAS_DOWNLOAD
>,>,Property, slotCount, 4
>,>,SlotSchedule, ATLAS_433_92, 0, 4, 1, 10, CODE, RANDOM_SIGN
>,>,SlotSchedule, DATA_433_92, 1, 1, 3, 0, ALLOW_SESSION
>,Trigger
>,>,Property, type, NO_WAKEUP
>,>,Property, afterSeconds, 10
>,>,Property, afterHours, 0
>,>,Property, afterDays, 0
>,>,Property, toConfiguration, 0_ATLAS
>,SensorConfiguration,BATMON,2
>,SensorConfiguration,BMI160,300,10,25
>,SensorConfiguration,BME280,2
```

The logger uses two radio setups. One is for ATLAS and the other, DATA_433_92, is for downloading data (and for setting the clock). The DATA_433_92 setup transmits data at a high rate (500 kb/s) and only works at short ranges.

The tag uses two configuration. In the first, 0_ATLAS, the tag transmits an ATLAS code very second (every four 250 ms periods) and it transmits a beacon data packet, including its local time, every 30 s. The beacon also states whether the tag has data to

download. If a Vildehaye base station hears this data packet, it can respond with a clock adjustment and/or a command to switch to the last configuration of the tag, here 1_ATLAS_DOWNLOAD. In the download configuration the tag continues to transmit its ATLAS code every second, but it also transmits 3 data packets every second. If the base station acknowledges the data transfers, the tag sends more data. Otherwise, it repeats the same data. If the tag fails to receive acknowledgments for data for 10 s, it reverts to its first configuration. This saves power when the tag is out of range of the base station, or has nothing to send (so the base station has nothing to acknowledge).

Note that the transmit power of the data protocol is only 0 dBm (=1 mW). This is to reduce power consumption, under the assumption that the base station is nearby. This also reduces interference to other tags and base stations and to ATLAS.

The template also tells the tag what to sense and how often. It tells it to sense using the BATMON sensor that is built into the CC13XX microcontrollers every 2 seconds. This records the battery voltage and the temperature. It tells the tag to use the BME280 every 2 seconds too; this logs air-pressure measurements. Finally, it tell the tag to use the BMI160 inertial sensor for 10 s every 5 minutes at a rate of 25 Hz. *The duration field is specified in seconds, but is converted in the tag to a whole number of tag periods.* That is, the specification of 10 s here is converted to

$$\left\lfloor \frac{10 \text{ s}}{\text{period}} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{10000 \text{ ms}}{250 \text{ ms}} \right\rfloor = 40 .$$

If the integer part of the division is zero, the sensor will perform one measurement every interval, much like the BATMON and BME280 are used here.

Figure 16.3 shows the timeline of packets received from a tag configured using this template. Each dot represents a 10 s period in which a base station received at least one packet from the tag. In most of these periods, the base station received only one packet; this is consistent with the tag transmitting one packet every 30 s when it is in the 0_ATLAS configuration. Every 5 minutes, the tag transmits a burst of packets. These bursts happen when the tag accumulates enough data to initiate data upload; this happens every 5 minutes because most of the data that is accumulated comes from the acceleration sensor. In the periods between bursts we see about 10 dots, that correspond to one packet every 30 s; the graph does not indicate that the tag is transmitting a packet every 10 s, because only periods in which the base station received at least one packet are plotted.

Figure 16.4 shows air-pressure data logged by a tag and a simplistic conversion of the air pressure to altitude.

Figure 16.3: Timeline of packets received from a tag programming using the `LOGGER_433_92` template. The dots show the number of packets received by a base station in 10 s periods in which the base station received some packet from the tag.

Figure 16.4: Air pressure as sensed by a BME280 on a sensor-logging board. The tag was carried shortly after 15:00 up five floors using stairs and then back down. The graph on the left shows the compensated measurements that that the sensor produced and the graph on the right the transformation of the air pressure to altitude using the Barometric formula, using a nominal pressure for sea level (1013 hPa). The graph shows a climb of about 14 m (2.8 m per floor), which is about right. After the descent, the tag was stationary, but the sensor still shows some noise and drift.

Chapter 17

Processing Sensor Logs and Vildehaye Databases

This chapter explains how to process data stored in SQLite files that contain data downloaded from sensors and memory boards (the `flashcontroller dump` command), downloaded from memory cards in Vildehaye stand alone base stations, and from tethered base stations. The data is usually stored in a file called `vildehaye.sqlite`.

The command that extracts the data from the SQLite databases is `sensorlog-query`.

17.1 Extracting Sensor Data for Analysis

To extract sensor data from an SQLite database file that was created by the flash controller or by a Vildehaye base station, run the `atlas sensorlog-query` command:

```
..\atlas-distribution\atlas.bat sensorlog-query tag=972002000601
```

You can omit the `tag=` argument in files that contain log items from only one tag; the software will find that tag number. The command reads data from a file named `vildehaye.sqlite`. If file is named differently, use the option `input=jdbc:sqlite:filename.sqlite`. To list the tags whose data is stored in such a file, use the option `list`.

The `sensorlog-query` command reads all the data items of one tag from the database, in increasing log order, and extracts all the sensor data into binary files that can be easily read from Matlab and other analysis environments. The run above produced three output files:

```
tag-972002000601-BATMON.bin  
tag-972002000601-BME280.bin  
tag-972002000601-BMI160.bin
```

You can also specify a single sensor whose data you want extracted with the `sensor=name` option.

Scripts in `atlas-distribution\matlab` can read these files and produce simple MATLAB data structures (arrays or cell arrays) that contain the same data. The scripts are named `sensorsBME280.m` and so on.

But the format of these data files is not complicated. Data is usually stored in one of two formats. For simple periodic sensors like BME280 and BATMON, the file contains one matrix with a row for each measurement. The first column contains time stamps and the rest sensor. The file has a three-number header containing the sensor type (not strictly needed since it's also included in the file name) and the number of rows and columns in the matrix. The data itself is stored in row order (measurement after measurement). All the data, including the header, is stored as big-endian 64-bit floating point numbers.

The following Matlab script reads the BME280 data from such a file and plots it.

```
f = fopen('tag-972002000601-sensor-BME280.bin','r');
sensorId = fread(f, 1, 'double','b') % 'b' == big-endian
m = fread(f, 1, 'double','b')
n = fread(f, 1, 'double','b')
% fread reads in column order, but data is in row order
bme280 = fread(f, [n m], 'double','b');
bme280 = bme280'; % transpose back

% Filter bad records (fill the data with NaNs)

filter = find(bme280(:,1) < 1.5e9) % incorrect times
bme280(filter,2) = NaN;

filter = find(bme280(:,2) < 300) % out of range
bme280(filter,2) = NaN;

filter = find(bme280(:,2) > 1100) % out of range
bme280(filter,2) = NaN;

plot(bme280(:,1),bme280(:,2))
fclose(f);
```

Figure 17.1 shows the plot (units are hPa), along with a plot of the acceleration from the same tag. The tag was carried by a person for a few days.

Bursty sensors, like the BMI160, produce data files with distinct bursts. The data file still starts with a sensor-type number, followed by bursts of sensor data. Each burst starts with a header describing the starting time of the burst, the sampling rate, and the number of rows and columns in the data matrix. The matrix follows, in row order (measurement order). Again all the data is 64-bit floating point and big-Endian byte ordering.

Here is a Matlab code snippet that reads the bursts from a file. The graph above shows the maximal non-directional acceleration in every burst.

```
f = fopen('tag-972002000601-sensor-BMI160.bin','r');
sensorId = fread(f, 1, 'double','b') % 'b' == big-endian
while (~feof(f))
    t = fread(f, 1, 'double','b'); % time stamp
    r = fread(f, 1, 'double','b'); % sampling rate
    m = fread(f, 1, 'double','b'); % number of measurements
    n = fread(f, 1, 'double','b'); % dimension of each measurement
    if (t < 1.5e9) continue; end; % incorrect time stamp
```


Figure 17.1: The output from an air-pressure sensor (top) and an accelerometer (bottom).

Figure 17.2: A single acceleration burst from a walking person.

```

if (feof(f)) break; end; % past the end of the file
bmi160burst = fread(f, [n m], 'double','b');
bmi160burst = bmi160burst'; % row order, so transpose
...
end

```

Figure 17.2 shows what a single burst looks like when the tag is carried by a walking

Figure 17.3: Plots from sensors.

person.

Running `sensorlog-query` on files from base stations produces a different set of binary files:

```
tag-972002000001-BME280.bin
tag-972002000001-UBLOX.bin
```

The first contains environmental measurements (air pressure, temperature, and humidity) from the BME280 sensor. The second contains GNSS locations from the ublox receiver of a standalone base station.

The graphs shown in Figure 17.3 plot environmental data from a base station. Figure 17.4 shows the GPS locations of a logging base station, collected during two trips in a car, after conversion from longitude-latitude to a metric projection.

17.2 Adding Sensor Configuration to Partial Logs

The `sensorlog-query` command produces an output similar to the one below:

```
09:42:42 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - connecting to: jdbc:sqlite
↳ :6601.sqlite
09:42:43 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - connected to: jdbc:sqlite
↳ :6601.sqlite
...
09:42:43 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - found tag 972001006601
09:42:43 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - Single tag log, tag
↳ =972001006601
09:42:43 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.Query - Querying for the single tag in the
↳ log, tag 972001006601
```


Figure 17.4: GPS track of a logging base station.

```

scanning for tag=972001006601
LOG HEADER addr=00000000 length = 34
  creation time 2020-May-13-09-10-26
  sector/page/flash sizes = 4096/256/67108864
CATALOG_ID 1
SENSOR_CONFIG 52 tag 972001006601
Sensor config type=BME280 interval=1.000000 duration=0.000000 rate=0.000000
  ↪ options=0000
SENSOR_CONFIG 51 tag 972001006601
Sensor config type=BATMON interval=1.000000 duration=0.000000 rate=0.000000
  ↪ options=0000
SENSOR_CONFIG 53 tag 972001006601
Sensor config type=BMI160 interval=10.000000 duration=0.000000 rate=25.000000
  ↪ options=0000
BOOT_MARKER
TAG_ID 972001006601
SENSOR BMI160
SENSOR BMI160
...                a lot cut out
Closing database
09:57:23 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - Draining detection
  ↪ summaries
Sensor BATMON id 972001006601 has data? true (configured? true; counts = 0+17296)
Sensor BME280 id 972001006601 has data? true (configured? true; counts = 0+9224)
Sensor BMI160 id 972001006601 has data? true (configured? true; counts =
  ↪ 0+359772)
No data at all for sensor UBLOX
Sensor TXINV id 972001006601 has data? true (configured? false; counts = 4288+0)

```

We highlighted in bold the first the printouts that describe the first few log items that the program found in the log, and also the summaries of how much data from each sensor was extracted.

You can see that the beginning of the log contains sensor-configuration records. These

records reflect the sensor configuration in `vildehaye.txt`; they told the tag how to configure the sensor, and they are now telling `sensorlog-query` how to interpret sensor data in the log. At the end of the run, the software reports that `BATMON`, `BME280`, and `BMI160` were configured. The two counts are counts of log items found *before* the sensor configuration was determined and *after* it was determined. For these three sensors, all the data followed the configuration, so all the data was used.

You can also see that there was not GNSS data in the log, and that there is data from a pseudo-sensor called `TXINV` that was not configured (so all of its data precedes the sensor configuration, which is not present at all). This pseudo-sensor does not need a configuration, so in this case there is no problem.

In SQLite files containing data from base stations (as opposed to data downloaded directly from a sensors and memory board), the beginning of the log of a tag might be missing, and when it is missing, the sensor-configuration log items might also be missing. This can happen if the tag uploaded the beginning of the log to base station A and the rest to base station B, but we have data only from B (perhaps we did not retrieve data from A yet, or perhaps it was somehow lost). This is a problem for some sensor types. In such a case we might see at the end of the run of `sensorlog-query` something like:

```
atlas.bat sensorlog-query tag=972002000600 input=jdbc:sqlite:bs008.sqlite
...
10:20:29 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - Draining detection
  → summaries
Sensor BATMON id 972002000600 has data? false (configured? false; counts = 184+0)
Sensor BME280 id 972002000600 has data? false (configured? false; counts = 97+0)
Sensor BMI160 id 972002000600 has data? false (configured? false; counts = 682+0)
No data at all for sensor UBL0X
Sensor TXINV id 972002000600 has data? true (configured? false; counts = 92+0)
```

This is not good; no data will be output into the `.bin` files.

Fortunately, this is easy to correct using the `sensorlog-sensors-conf` command:

```
atlas.bat sensorlog-sensors-conf system=... dir=... tag=...
```

The command reads the sensor configuration of the specified tag from `vildehaye.txt` and adds sensor-configuration log items to the log stored in `vildehaye.sqlite` in the current directory. When we run `sensorlog-query` again, we get:

```
10:35:55 [main] INFO tau.atlas.logger.SQLiteLogger - Draining detection
  → summaries
Sensor BATMON id 972002000600 has data? true (configured? true; counts = 0+184)
Sensor BME280 id 972002000600 has data? true (configured? true; counts = 0+97)
Sensor BMI160 id 972002000600 has data? true (configured? true; counts = 0+682)
No data at all for sensor UBL0X
Sensor TXINV id 972002000600 has data? true (configured? false; counts = 92+0)
```

17.3 Transmission Inversions

Tags that log sensor data and transmit an ATLAS code that is marked `RANDOM_BEACON` in the tag's template record to the log the signs of the ATLAS codes. The tag can invert the

code (replace a +1 symbol with a -1 symbol), which is equivalent to transmitting a low frequency when it was supposed to transmit a high frequency and vice versa. When the transmission is marked with the `RANDOM_BEACON` option, the tag uses a pseudo-random choice for the inversion in each transmission. It records the choices and records them, with a second-accurate time stamp, to its log.

ATLAS base stations can usually determine whether a code was inverted or not; inversion results in a negative peak in the cross correlation function, whereas a transmission with no inversion results in a positive peak. This information is included in the information that the base stations send to the server and is stored in the `DETECTIONS` table in the database (represented by plus or minus sign for the transmission identifier):

```
mysql> select BS,TAG,TX,TIME,SNR from DETECTIONS where TAG=972002000600 order by
        ↪ TIME desc LIMIT 10;
```

```
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| BS      | TAG          | TX          | TIME          | SNR  |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | -972002000600 | 1602170060591 | 2.847 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | -972002000600 | 1602170059549 | 4.252 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | -972002000600 | 1602170058527 | 4.261 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | -972002000600 | 1602170057487 | 4.218 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | 972002000600  | 1602170056444 | 4.236 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | -972002000600 | 1602170055375 | 4.093 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | 972002000600  | 1602170054343 | 3.555 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | 972002000600  | 1602170053336 | 3.005 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | 972002000600  | 1602170052400 | 2.484 |
| 972002003 | 972002000600 | 972002000600  | 1602170051242 | 3.880 |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
```

```
10 rows in set (0.00 sec)
```

By correlating the sequence of inversions that the tag recorded with the sequences that the base stations produce we can correct for any offset and possibly drift that the clock on the tag has. We do not yet have code to do that automatically, but it is doable.

The `sensorlog-query` command stores these inversions in a binary file, like it stores other sensor data. This data currently does not have an on-log sensor configuration information.

17.4 Vildehaye Detections

Vildehaye databases from tethered base station can also contain summaries of detections of tags. These summaries are stored in the `DETECTIONS_VH` table, as shown in the next snippet:

```
C:\temp\atlas>sqlite3 vildehaye.sqlite
SQLite version 3.32.3 2020-06-18 14:00:33
Enter ".help" for usage hints.
sqlite> select BS,TAG,TIME,RSSI,SUMMARY_OF from DETECTIONS_VH;
972002000007|972002000953|1602081135085|-44.0|3|
972002000007|972002000953|1602081145085|-45.0|2|
972002000007|972002000953|1602081155085|-45.0|3|
```

```
972002000007|972002000953|1602081165083|-45.0|2|
972002000007|972002000953|1602081175082|-45.0|3|
972002000007|972002000953|1602081185081|-45.0|2|
972002000007|972002000953|1602081195080|-46.0|3|
...
```

The fields shown are the base station number (here 972002000007), the tag number (972002000953), the time (milliseconds since 1970), the maximum RSSI of packets in the summary, and the number of packets represented by the summary. The time is the average reception time. Currently, each summary is of packets received during a 10 s period.

The table also contains another field called PACKED that can contain the actual payload of a single packet (if it is not empty, the summary is of exactly one packet). The software normally does not store the payload; we can turn this on in the sources, mostly to debug the protocol.

Chapter 18

Monitoring for Faults and Performance Problems and Troubleshooting Them

ATLAS, Vildehaye, and Kamadata are complex systems that consist of both hardware and software. Components can experience faults. This chapter explains how to monitor the systems to detect faults, how to resolve some faults on your own, and how to report faults that you cannot resolve yourself.

18.1 Monitoring

You cannot fix a fault that you do not know about. Therefore, active ATLAS and Vildehaye systems should be monitored regularly. In particular, every system should have a person who is responsible for monitoring it, and the monitoring period should be explicitly defined (e.g., every day).

The system-wide real-time view of Kamadata provides a good way to perform basic monitoring that tells you which components are up and which are down. If the server is down or not reachable via the network, the program will display no information, indicating that the server needs attention. If you have several servers, you should try to connect to all of them to make sure they are all up. If the server is up, the program shows base station activity and detections, indicating which base stations are up and online and which are down or disconnected.

Beacons are important tools for monitoring. Every infrastructure base station should be able to hear at least one beacon. If you see detections of the beacons, you know that the base stations are not only up, but actually receiving. In particular, this means that their antennas have not been damaged, that their LNAs are receiving power, and so on; these things can do wrong. If you have beacons that only one base station can hear and it does not hear them, you may be unable to tell if the beacon is not operating (needs replacement batteries, its antenna has been damaged, etc.) or the base station is not working properly. If multiple base stations can normally hear the beacon, you can tell which component is not operating. This function of beacons is particularly important in systems in which there is sometimes very little activity of tags attached to animals.

The *performance view* of Kamadata provides quantitative information about the performance of basestations. By default it shows performance in the last day or two, but you can enlarge the time spans shown or page back in time. The *base station load* graph

Figure 18.1: Weird behavior in February 2017.

shows the computational load on base stations. More specifically, it shows the approximate fraction of tag transmissions that each base station missed because it was too busy processing other transmissions. It also shows periods in which the base station missed transmissions because it was down. This includes temporarily missing data from base stations that collected data but have not yet uploaded it to the server.

The *interference* graphs show RF interference on the channels that the ATLAS system is using, and sometimes on other channels, for reference. Some systems experience periods of high interference, which hurts their ability to detect and localize tags. This display tells you when the system experienced such periods.

18.2 Troubleshooting

Unattended ATLAS programs are designed to stop when they discover that something is wrong. When they are invoked by the `atlas-loop` script, the script launches the program again 10 seconds later. This allows the system to overcome minor faults automatically.

In some cases, this mechanism fails and the program does not restart and does not function normally. In these cases, you should log on to the computer running the program (usually using `ssh`) and perform the following steps:

1. Inspect the log to see if the program is running and whether it reported some failure. After you go to the logs' directory of the program, say `~/runs/receiver/logs`, the command `tail -f atlas.log` shows lines as they are added to the end of the log. If you monitor logs of programs that operate normally once or twice, you will know what to expect.
2. If the program does not appear to work normally, try to determine whether it has been running for a while (more than a few minutes). The other option is that the program cannot start normally, so it stops while trying to start up and the `atlas-loop` restarts it over and over again. This can happen, for example, if the base station program cannot communicate with the radio, or if the server program cannot communicate with the database. When this happens, you must correct the problem that causes the program to crash repeatedly. You can diagnose these repeated attempts to start in a few different ways:
 - You can inspect the beginning and end of the previous logs (`atlas-1.log` and `atlas-2.log`); the time stamps of log messages will show that the program

stopped shortly after starting. You can view the beginning with the utilities `head`, `more`, and `less`, and the end with `tail -200 | less`.

- You can monitor the process number of the running program with repeated invocations of `ps aux | grep java` for about a minute to see if the process restarts quickly.
3. If the program appears to be running (`ps aux | grep java` shows it as running) but is not making progress and not responding (e.g., a base station program is not reporting detection to a server, or a server does not respond to Kamadata), find out the process number of the program and kill it (`kill processnumber`). If it appears to keep running, use `kill -9 processnumber` to kill it; this always works.
 4. If the program gets stuck or crashes repeatedly and the log does not indicate why, you should run it interactively. To do this, find out the process number of the `atlas-loop` script, kill it first, and then kill the program. If you do not kill the `atlas-loop` script, it will keep running the program and this can prevent the interactive instance from running normally. By running interactively we mean to run an ATLAS base station by invoking `atlas.sh receiver`, etc. Some messages that are displayed in this mode are not written to the log. For example, in one case a base station was not able to connect to the radio. Running the program interactively revealed a message from the radio's driver that it's firmware reverted to factory settings and was incompatible with the driver. The message showed the command to correct this problem.
 5. Running programs interactively can also be helpful when a program is not stuck but restarts repeatedly.
 6. If you kill the `atlas-loop` script and correct some problem, make sure the program runs under `atlas-loop`. The easiest way to accomplish this is to invoke the command that starts the `atlas-loop` script in `/etc/rc.local`.

18.3 Reporting Problems

Please report problems to the ATLAS/Vildehaye users' mailing list on Google groups (atlas-vildehaye-users@googlegroups.com). You need to be a member of the group to post messages to it.

When you report a problem, try to include enough information to diagnose it. This usually include the pertinent parts of the log (or all of it), messages that appeared on the screen in interactive invocations, and so on.

18.4 Appendix B: Localization with Multiple Beacons

We show here simulations of an ATLAS system in which all base stations receive all the tags, but very few base stations receive the beacons. The examples show when ATLAS can and cannot localize tags in such situations.

Two base stations receive beacons, no localizations.

Two base stations receive beacons 3 and another receives beacon 1, no localizations.

Two base stations receive beacon 1 and two other base stations receive beacon 3; this allows the system to localize tags.

18.5 Prometheus and Grafana

Starting in April 2022, ATLAS includes support for a sophisticated and widely-used monitoring system called *Prometheus* (<https://prometheus.io/>). Data collected by Prometheus can be visualized by another widely-used system called *Grafana* (<https://grafana.com/>). Grafana allows users to create so-called dashboards that display a lot of quantitative information about a monitored system, to assess its performance, identify performance bottlenecks, and detect faults. Grafana can also generate *alerts* that inform system operators about faults via email, text messages, and so on.

These monitoring tools should be useful mostly to operators and administrators of ATLAS systems, not to users who tag animals and use the tracking data.

Keep in mind that the data is intended for monitoring only, not for collecting statistics about the system. Prometheus itself and the way that ATLAS uses it optimize computational efficiency, not complete accuracy.

Figure 18.2 shows how an ATLAS system can be connected to Prometheus and Grafana. The ATLAS server and receiver programs collect data called *metrics* about their own performance. For example, ATLAS servers count how many detections they receive from each base station, how many localizations they produce at real time, how long it takes to insert the data into the database, and so on.

These metrics are available for inspection and collection through a web interface. You can view it in your browser, but it is really meant to be automatically collected by Prometheus. Prometheus visits these web interfaces every few seconds in all the programs it monitors, both on the computer that runs Prometheus and on other computers in the network. It only visits computers it is explicitly configured to visit. It collects and stores all the metrics that it finds, usually for 15 days. The act of visiting a web interface, requesting metrics data, and storing it, is called *scraping*. Each piece of data that Prometheus scrapes is time stamped and given a name. Data with the same name over multiple scrapes (with increasing time stamps) form a *time series*. So Prometheus collects named time series from the programs that it monitors.

In a typical setup, Prometheus might run on a different computer than the ATLAS server (but it can run on the same computer) and it might scrape data only from the ATLAS server program; this connection is denoted in the figure with a bold green arrow. The data that the server provides contains metrics about the server's performance, but also about the performance of the base stations, like the number of detections and how much interference they are experiencing. So you do not have to scrape the base stations; but you could. Scraping the base stations direction allows you to determine their performance even if the server is not working. This is not usually useful, but it might be useful in some special circumstances. Prometheus can also scrape data from MySQL servers (this requires an add-on to MySQL), and it can also scrape information about computer hardware and operating systems; this is scraped from a program called *node exporter*. This allows you to monitor things like how full the disks are and how hot the computer gets. The temperature, for example, might be useful to monitor in base stations.

For Prometheus to be able to scrape an ATLAS program, the program must expose its metrics via a web interface. Servers do this automatically via their standard ATLAS port. So if you have an ATLAS server running on `atlas-server.university.edu` on port 6789, you can view the servers metrics by directing your browser to

Figure 18.2: Connections between components of an ATLAS system and Prometheus and Grafana.

Figure 18.3: The top part of a Grafana dashboard displaying the performance of an ATLAS system.

`https:atlas-server.university.edu:6789/metrics`

Prometheus can be configured to visit this address, but it will succeed only if the ATLAS server presents a trusted security certificate. The standard security certificate that most ATLAS servers used would not be trusted. We may fix this in the future, but there is another solution. You can add in the configuration of the server (and of base stations, if necessary) a property that tells the ATLAS program to also make its metrics available via a non-secure web interface on a particular port:

```
>,Server,primary,atlas-server.university.edu,6789,null,atlas_db
>,>,Property,httpPort,1234
>,>,...
```

Now you (and Prometheus) can access the metrics also through

`http:atlas-server.university.edu:1234/metrics`

Give it a try.

The data that Prometheus scrapes is accessible via a web interface that Prometheus itself exposes. To access this data in the example presented in Figure 18.2, the user would visit

`http:metrics-server.university.edu:9090`

(9090 is the default port that Prometheus uses). You can view metrics in tabular format using this web interface and you can ask Prometheus to present the data as graphs.

But Grafana provides better ways to visualize metrics data scraped and stored by Prometheus. Grafana also uses a web interface, normally on port 3000. So to use Grafana to visualize your Prometheus data, you would log in to Grafana, configure it to retrieve data from Prometheus, and then configure it to present the data you want in the form you want. Figures 18.3 and 18.4 show a Grafana dashboard presenting ATLAS performance. It shows at the top gauges that show the number of localizations and detections that a particular ATLAS system produces every second (averaged over a minute). A drop-down menu labeled SYSTEM at the top left allows you to choose the system for which

Figure 18.4: The rest of the Grafana dashboard from Figure 18.3.

system-level data would be presented in this dashboard. This particular Grafana dashboard gets its data from a Prometheus instance that scrapes three ATLAS servers, not one, so this drop-down menu allows you to choose the system you want to inspect. A drop-down menu at the top right allows you to choose the span of time for which data is displayed, here the last 6 hours. The dashboard also presents the detection and localization rates as graphs, as well as the number of detections per-base station (as reported by the server, in this case), the searching and tracking coverage of base stations, interference, database performance, the length of queues at base stations (amount of data waiting to be sent to the server), and the utilization of memory and CPU time at the servers.

In the dashboard shown in Figures 18.3 and 18.4 we can observe that the server was not working for a few hours, restarting around 5am. Several graphs show various effects when the server restarted. For example, we can see the base stations' queues draining

over a period of about half an hour, we can see the server's CPU load spiking as it was recomputing localizations for the hours in which it did not operate, and so on.

18.5.1 Metrics, Labels, and Queries

The names of individual time series in Prometheus consist of a *metric* name, such as `atlas_detections_total`, and of a set of key-value pairs. The keys are called *labels* (in other similar systems, like OpenTSDB, the keys are sometimes called *tags*). The metrics that ATLAS exposes always have three labels: `system`, `component`, and `where`.

The `system` label is self explanatory; it is the name of the ATLAS system. The `component` specifies the part of the system that the metric describes, like a particular base station, say `bs_972002006`, or `server_primary`. Metrics of base stations that are reported by a server are reported with a `component` value such as `bs_972002006_at_primary`. We normally configure Prometheus add a label called `basestation` to base station's metrics, with a value that is just the base station's name. The `where` label specifies additional aspects of the time series, such as distinguishing between detections in different channels (frequencies) or localizations computed in real time or in the hourly consistency enforcer.

Prometheus supports four types of metrics. We currently use only two, *counters* whose names always end with `total`, and *gauges*, whose name ends with a unit of measurements, like seconds or bytes.

The graphs that describe the performance of ATLAS systems often do not display raw time series but derived time series produced from the raw ones using expressions in Prometheus's query language. For example, the bottom right graph in Figure 18.4 shows raw time series, namely

```
process_resident_memory_bytes
```

but the bottom left graph shows a derived graph,

```
rate(process_cpu_seconds_total[1m])
```

The derived time series shows the rate of increase (derivative) in the total number of CPU seconds used, when the derivative is evaluated over a minute. Queries can select time series with specific labels to display. For example,

```
rate(atlas_detections_total{system="harod",where="ATLAS_CH_75"}[1m])
```

selects only time series from the Harod ATLAS system and only those labeled with a particular channel name.

18.5.2 Installation and Configuration

Installing Prometheus on Ubuntu Linux is easy,

```
sudo apt update
sudo apt install prometheus
```

Installing Grafana is a bit more complicated, because it is distributed from a non-standard repository. Follow the instructions in the Grafana documentation.

Prometheus is configured on Ubuntu to run continuously and to start automatically. Grafana needs a few more configuration steps to run continuously and automatically; again, follow the instructions. Prometheus needs to be restarted when you modify its configuration file.

```
sudo service prometheus restart
```

Prometheus must be configured to scrape your ATLAS system; this is done in a configuration file that is normally stored in `/etc/prometheus/prometheus.yml`. The `global` section in this file defines the default scrape interval, usually 10 or 15 seconds. The `scrape_configs` section of the file defines a set of *jobs* that collect data from various system. By default, Prometheus scrapes only itself and the computer that it runs on. You need to add a job to scrape your ATLAS system. Here is an example that scrapes three ATLAS systems.

```
scrape_configs:
  - job_name: 'prometheus'
    ...

  - job_name: atlas
    static_configs:
      # tau primary server
      - targets: ['atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il:1234']
      # hula primary server
      - targets: ['atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il:4321']
      # harod primary server
      - targets: ['132.66.43.247:1234']

metric_relabel_configs:
  - source_labels: [component]
    regex: bs_(\d+)_.
    target_label: basestation

  - source_labels: [component]
    regex: bs_(\d+)
    target_label: basestation

  - source_labels: [instance,system,component]
    regex: atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il:1234;;
    target_label: system
    replacement: tau

  - source_labels: [instance,system,component]
    regex: atlas-server.cs.tau.ac.il:1234;tau;
    target_label: component
    replacement: primary

    ...
```

The `static_configs` subsection tells Prometheus which computers and ports you want to scrape. The `metric_relabel_configs` subsection adds labels to some of the metrics, to allow Grafana to present these metrics with more meaningful legends. The relabeling extracts the base station number from metrics related to base station performance.

Other relabeling rules add the ATLAS system name and the server name to metrics that describe the memory and CPU usage.

Appendix A

Technical Documentation: Hardware

A.1 The Circuit-Board Manufacturing Process

We use a manufacturer called CircuitHub (<https://circuitHub.com/>) to produce circuit boards for ATLAS and Vildehaye. Every type of board is a *project* in the terminology

Project Name	Comments
sivan_toledo/atlas-tag-v2_6	Tag Version 2.6.1
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-434-ipc	Tag Version 2.6.3 with a pressure sensor
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-434-ipc-bmp384	Tag Version 2.6.4 with a BMP384 pressure sensor
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-tag-v2-8	Tag Version 2.8
ATLAS-Consignmnet/vildehaye-tag-v2-9	Tag Version 2.9
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-tag-v2-10	Tag Version 2.10
sivan_toledo/tag-cc1310-ax5031	Tag Version 3.0
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-tag-v2-9-800-900-MHz	Tag version 2.9, variant for 868 and 915 MHz, <i>never manufactured</i>
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-sensors-memory-bmx160	Sensors+memory board with BMX160, 64 MB
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-sensors-memory	Sensors+memory board with BMI160, 64 MB
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-sensors-memory-small	Sensors+memory board, 8 MB, <i>requires a board fix</i>
sivan_toledo/vildeyahe-adapter-2	Programming adapter
sivan_toledo/vildeyahe-extender	Vildehaye male-female stack, <i>never manufactured</i>
sivan_toledo/tag-stacking-breakout	Vildehaye male-female breakout, <i>few uses</i>
sivan_toledo/vildehaye-basestation-boosterpack	Boosterpack for Vildehaye base stations with CAM-M8Q GNSS receiver
sivan_toledo/filter-bias-limiters	Filter, bias-tee, and limiter for ATLAS base stations

Table A.1: Current ATLAS and Vildehaye CircuitHub projects. The URL for a project named user/proj in the table is <https://circuitHub.com/projects/user/proj>.

The screenshot shows a CircuitHub project page for 'sivan_toledo / atlas-tag-v2_6'. The page displays a list of parts with columns for Part, Quantity, Unit, and Line. The parts listed are:

Part	Quantity	Unit	Line
JOHANSON-LPF JOHANSON-LPF Johanson / 0400LP15A0122E RF FILTER LOW PASS 373MHZ 0805	110	\$0 5082	\$55 9020
22u C0603K Murata / GRM188R60J226MEA00 Multilayer Ceramic Capacitors MLCC - SMD/SMT 0603 22uF 6.3volts *Derate Voltage/Temp	250	\$0 0660	\$16 5000
330p C0201 Murata / GRM0335C1E331-1A01D	250	\$0 0098	\$2 4475

Below the parts list, there is a section for 'Assembled boards' with a slider set to 100 boards. A summary table shows a total of 100 boards at a unit price of \$25.19, for a total of \$2,519.01. An 'Order' button is visible at the bottom right.

Figure A.1: A CircuitHub Project.

of the website. All the projects are public, meaning that you can inspect them and order batches of boards from them. You need a CircuitHub account to order (but not to view the projects). You can also download the design files from the website, and you can fork (copy) the projects so that you can change the selection of parts or other manufacturing parameters (e.g, board thickness and color). The list of current projects is shown in Table A.1.

The main screen of a project looks like the screen shown in Figure A.1. In principle, you adjust the number of boards you want to order, perhaps shorten the manufacturing time (this causes a price increase), and order. The more units you order the lower the unit price. However, there are several pitfalls to watch for:

1. If some of the parts in the project are not available from any of the distributors that CircuitHub works with, the website will alert you of the *shortfall*, as shown in Figure A.2. In that case, you cannot place an order. The owner of the project can sometimes correct the problem. One option is to allow CircuitHub to use an alternate part, say a generic part like a capacitor by another manufacturer, or a CC1350 instead of a CC1310 (more expensive, but compatible). The second option is to find the part at some distributor's web site and to tell CircuitHub's web site how to find the part. If you fork the project, you become the owner of the forked project and you can do this yourself. Only do this if you are sure the alternate parts are indeed equivalent. Otherwise, ask the owner of the original project to correct the situation if possible.
2. Sometimes a part is available, but only in very large batches. In that case CircuitHub will alert you that the price is influenced in a significant way by a *minimum order quantity (MOQ)*; the distributor is causing CircuitHub to purchase hundreds or thousands of parts when only a small fraction will actually be used

Figure A.2: A CircuitHub Project with a shortfall of some parts. If you scroll down, you see which parts are not available.

Figure A.3: A CircuitHub Project with parts that have a large minimum order quantity (MOQ). If you place an order, CircuitHub will be forced to purchase 3000 parts when they only need a few; this increases the price of the order.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a CircuitHub project page. The URL is circuithub.com/projects/sivan_toledo/vildehaye-basestation-boosterpack/revisions/19162/parts. The page lists several components for a project. Two components are marked as 'Not placed'.

Part Name	Manufacturer	Part Number	Description	Quantity	Unit Price	Estimated Total
1000	Bourns	CR0603-FX-1001ELF	Res Thick Film 0603 1K Ohm 1% 1/10W ±100ppm°C Molded SMD Paper Tape on Plastic Reel	100	\$0.0044	\$0.4400
220	Panasonic	ERJ-3GEYJ221V	Resistor Thick Film 0603 220 Ohm 5% 1/10W 200ppm°C Molded SMD Punched Carrier T/R	100	\$0.0130	\$1.2980
100k	Vishay	CRCW0603100KFKEA	Res Thick Film 0603 100K Ohm 1% 1/10W ±100ppm°C Molded SMD Paper T/R	100	\$0.0139	\$1.3860
SD-CARD-MSD50	Molex	503182-1852	Conn Micro SD Card M 8 POS 1.09mm Solder RA SMD Embossed T/R 0.5A/Contact	9	\$2.1010	\$18.9090
BME280	Bosch Tools	BME280	Pressure, Temperature and Humidity Sensor Digital Output 1.8V 8-Pin LGA T/R	8	\$4.1030	\$32.8240
HEADERS-2-10	Not placed	Not placed	Not placed	0	\$0.0000	\$0.0000
IR-RECEIVER	Not placed	Not placed	Not placed	0	\$0.0000	\$0.0000

At the bottom of the page, there is a summary section for 'Assembled boards' showing 5 boards. A table below it shows:

Quantity	Unit price	Estimated total
5	\$109.39	\$546.93

An 'Order' button is visible, and the lead time is indicated as 'Ships on Nov 19 (32 business days)'.

Figure A.4: A CircuitHub Project with two parts that are marked as *do not place*. These parts will not be on the manufactured boards.

in the project. A situation like this is shown in Figure A.3. This is not as bad as a shortfall, but it usually makes sense to try to replace the part with the MOQ with another part that is available in smaller quantities, to reduce the cost of the build.

3. The project might be in an imperfect state, usually due to changes made to allow a previous order to go through. For example, the project might tell CircuitHub not to place some part on the board. Perhaps that part is non-essential (but useful for you) and was expensive or not available at the time of the previous build, so it was marked by the owner of the project as a *do not place* part. This situation is shown in Figure A.4. Other possibilities are parts that are functional but sub-optimal (because the most appropriate part was not available during the previous build), such as a reservoir capacitor with a smaller capacitance, or an unusual board thickness. Therefore, before you place an order, check that there are no *do not place* parts (or that they are marked that way for a good reason), that the board thickness is the one you want, and that the owner of the project is not aware of other problems (like sub-optimal replacements).

We have had quite a few problems with unavailable parts in the years that we have been using CircuitHub. The main reasons for this seem to be:

- Parts that became obsolete but were replaced by functionally identical parts. This happened with to the miniature 14-pin connectors that we use. The replacement parts are virtually identical to the old ones, but CircuitHub does not replace them automatically, so we have to do that with every project that we order again now (we replace once per project; then it can be ordered over and over again).

- Parts that are essentially generic, especially capacitors, but are the smallest available for a particular capacitance and voltage rating, like the reservoir capacitor and 0402 1 μ F capacitors. There are sometimes very few different parts that fit the specification, and sometimes none of them are available.
- Parts that are unique, especially when they are particularly tiny. This is the case with the Hall sensor that we use on Version 2.9 tags. It is tiny and available only from one manufacturer. The manufacturer offers a wide range of these sensors (different sensitivities, active high or active low, etc), so sometimes the variant that we use is unavailable. The remedy is either to wait until it is ready (and then maybe order a large batch) or to use another variant. A slightly different sensitivity is not a big issue; the tags will still function. Switching from an active-high part to an active low or vice versa requires a modified firmware; it's doable, but a hassle.

CircuitHub allows you to buy a large quantity of a particular part (or several) and to send it to them for use in your projects. This can address all three issues to some extent, but it requires an upfront purchase of many parts, and the ordering process becomes more involved.

A.2 Printed Circuit Boards

All current Vildehaye tags use 4-layer circuit boards. The top and bottom layers are used for signals. The layer next to the top layer it is (mostly) continuous ground. The layer just above the bottom is usually used for routing the positive supply nets.

We produce tags on both 0.4 mm-thick boards and on 0.6 mm boards. The thicker boards are obviously slightly heavier and do not appear to have any significant benefits.

So far, we have designed all the boards using a CAD program called Eagle.

A.3 RF Microcontroller

Vildehaye tags and base stations are based on the Texas Instruments CC1310 radio-frequency microcontroller in a 4-by-4 mm package. The chip comes in three different packages; we use the smallest one. Texas Instruments (TI) refers to this package as RSM.

The tags can also be manufactured with a CC1350 chip, if CC1310 are not available. The two chips are the same except that the CC1350 can also operate on 2.4 GHz; we do not use this feature. TI refers to this family of chips as CC13X0.

Both chips operate over a voltage range of 1.8 to 3.8 V. We normally ensure that all the other components that are used in tags and in add-on boards be able to operate over this entire voltage range.

TI released a family of more powerful RF microcontrollers, CC13X2 and CC26X2. They differ from the CC13X0 in two main ways: (1) they have a more powerful processor and much more memory, and (2) one variant has a built-in power amplifier, so it can transmit 100 mW, as opposed to a maximum of about 20 mW in all the other variants.

At the source-code level, these chips are largely compatible with the CC13X0 chips, so software written for CC13X0 can run with only few changes on CC13X2 chips.

However, the sub-1 GHz chips from this family currently only come in much larger 7-by-7 mm packages, so they are not particularly useful for small tags. The extra memory might be useful for base stations, and we do have firmware support for that.

A.4 Reservoir Capacitors

Tags use a large capacitor to allow them to draw a significant amount of current (tens of milliamps) when the radio is active, even with small batteries that cannot provide that much current. We refer to this capacitor as a *reservoir* capacitor.

The standard reservoir capacitor that we use is a 330 μF 6.3 V tantalum capacitor made by AVX, part number F950J337KBAAQ2. This capacitor is part of the F95 series. The K indicates the accuracy, 10%; a 20% accurate part is also available, F950J337MBAAQ2. The J in the part number indicates the rated voltage, 6.3 V. The B in the part number is a size code; it is equivalent or compatible with EIA imperial size 1411 and EIA metric size 3528-20. The capacitor is 3.50 ± 0.20 mm long, 2.80 ± 0.20 mm wide, and 1.80 ± 0.20 mm high.

This part is sometimes not available. We have successfully used two replacements on two particular models. The replacements are likely to fit other tag models, but this should be checked before manufacturing.

The most direct replacement the 330 μF 6 V tantalum capacitor T490B337M006ATE800 from Kemet's T490 series. It has the same length and width specifications but is higher by 0.1 mm. Both the lower voltage rating and the increased height are not serious issues. This was tested on Version 2.6.3 tags.

We also used a 220 μF 6.3 V 10% tantalum capacitor made by AVX, F930J227KBA, part of their F93 series. It is listed as EIA sizes 1210 and 3528-21 (imperial and metric) and has the same dimension specifications as the T490B337M006ATE800. The smaller capacitance can limit the length of bursts of tag activity; we do not have much experience tags with a 220 μF reservoir capacitor. We used this capacitor on Version 2.9 tags. Vishay Sprague TMCMB0J227MTRF is a similar part that also seems to be appropriate. So is T55B227M6R3C0035, also by Vishay.

A.5 RF Filter or Balun-Filter Combination

Most of the tags have been manufactured with a ceramic RF low-pass filter (an integrated passive component or IPC), Johanson Technology 0400LP15A0122E. It appears that Johanson 0500LP15A500E is also appropriate and has better attenuation of harmonics.

Some tags use a combined balun-filter IPC, Walsin Technologies RFBLN2520090YC3T10.

A.6 Vildehaye 14-Pin Connectors

Vildehaye tags use a stacking 14-pin low profile connector is that is used to program them and to communicate with add-on boards or motherboards. When two boards are stacked, the vertical separation is 1 mm.

The connectors are made by Molex and are part of the SlimStack series. Tags have a plug (male) connector, add-on boards have a receptacle on one side, to mate with the tag, and a plug on the other, to allow stacking and to allow connecting the entire stack to the adapter board. Adapter boards have a receptacle.

The current part numbers are:

502-430-1430 plug

502-426-1430 receptacle

The two digits represent a variant. The first tags used variant 10, which is now obsolete. Variant 10 is now obsolete and Molex states that it was replaced by 12, but 12 is usually not available. Variant 30 is identical to 12 but is packed differently, and is widely available. The two digits to the right, 14, are the number of the connections.

We selected these connectors to allow mating with Vesper tags, which are wildlife-tracking tags designed by Alex Schwartz for Yossi Yovel. The assignment of connections was also selected for compatibility with Vesper, and the two tag families can indeed inter-operate.

The assignment of connections is:

VDDS	2	1	NRESET
SPI_CS	4	3	I2C_SCL
SPI_SCK	6	5	I2C_SDA
SPI_MI	8	7	UART_TX
SPI_MOSI	10	9	UART_RX
BOOTLOADER	12	11	NC
GND	14	13	GND

VDDS is the supply input. NRESET is a reset signal, active low. BOOTLOADER is an active-low signal that tells the microcontroller to enter the serial-bootloader mode (it is monitored only during reset; TI refers to this signal as the bootloader trapdoor). Pin 11 is used as an SPI chip-select on Vesper tags, but Vildehaye tags do not use it.

A.7 Vildehaye Programmer Connections

The UMFT230XB-01 programmer has a socket with 10 contacts in two rows. The function of the contacts is labeled on the programmer board.

We route 6 connections to the 14-pin connector that the tag attaches to, as follows

UMFT230XB-01		Vildehaye 14-Pin
GND	↔	GND
3V3	↔	VDDS
TXD	↔	RXD
RXD	↔	TXD
CBUS0	↔	NRESET
CBUS1	↔	BOOTLOADER

Note that the UART transmit and receive signals are crossed; the tag receives what the bridge transmits and vice versa. The bridge supplies up to 50 mA at 3.3 V. This is enough for CC13X0 tags but may not be enough for more powerful future devices.

A.8 The Front-End Unit

The front-end unit that provides power to the LNA is described in a technical paper [[MelemedToledoFrontEnd](#)], but the units built are slightly different than the one described in the filter.

One important difference is the current limiter. The article specifies a TPS2553-1 with a 180k current-programming resistor. The -1 variants of the TPS2552 and TPS2553 turn off power (latch off) if the current limit is exceeded. This protects the LNA and the current limiter from overheating, but it requires powering off the unit and powering back on to restore power. This is not convenient in remote locations.

So in actual production, we used the TPS2553 (without the -1 suffix), that continues to supply power at the current limit. The TPS2552 is completely equivalent but is active low rather than active high.

It is also possible to use the older TPS2550 (active low) or TPS2551 (active high) if TPS2552/3 is not available, but they require a different current-limiting resistor. We recommend 75k to get a similar limit (it appears that the TPS2550/1 are not as good as TPS2552/3 at keeping a tight limit, so the limit is not exactly the same).

A.9 Antenna Performance and Experimentation

In 2015 we performed a series of experiments to evaluate the radiation efficiency of the antennas and certain aspects of propagation. We used a solution of salt and sugar with electromagnetic properties similar to those of muscle to simulate the presence of an animal body near the tag and antenna. The proportions and preparation method are given in [[doi:10.1002/bem.2250080105](#)]. We did not use the jelling agent (Hydroxyethyl cellulose) suggested in that paper because the solution was stored in bottles, and we did not use the bactericide because we only used the solution for a short period. (Thanks to Kent Britain for pointing us to this paper.)

The experiment was conducted at a distance of 2.46 km with a line of sight to the tags. Tags at a height of 2 m above ground, strapped to a bottle with the salt-sugar solution,

were easily detected. At 50 cm high, signal strength was reduced by 10 dB when the tag's antenna was horizontal and by 15 dB when it was vertical. At 20 cm high, tags with vertical antennas suffered another loss of at least 13 dB (compared to 50 cm) and were barely detectable, and with horizontal antenna a loss of another 6.5 dB.

The liquid in the bottle seems to improve radiation by about 5 dB relative to tags in free air.

When two tags were strapped to the same bottle on either side, radiation was reduced by about 10 dB, presumably because one tag absorbed much of the radiation of the other. This was done to simulate a tag on a female bat and a tag on a pup clinging to her.

All of these experiments were performed with a Yagi antenna on the receiving side. The experiments were conducted by Sivan Toledo, Itamar Melamed, and Yotam Orchan.

A.10 Obsolete Hardware

The first ATLAS tags were based on MSP430 processors and the CC1101 transceiver. Figure A.5 shows most of the variants that we produced. These tags are described in a technical paper [TagsEDERC2014]. Tags version 1.1 and the CC430-based tag were assembled by hand and used relatively large passive components, mostly size 0603. The CC430 series of chips contain both an MSP430 microcontroller and a CC1101 in one plastic package, but because the package is large, the tags were not any smaller, so we abandoned the CC430. Version 1.2 is very similar to 1.1, but was manufactured by CircuitHub. In Version 2.10 we switched to smaller passive, mostly size 0402. The other three versions shown in the figure all use 0201 passives whenever possible, the same tiny size that we use now on CC13X0 tags.

The different variants of the CC430+CC1101 tags reflect attempts to find convenient ways to attach batteries, including retainers (as in Version 1.7) and pads for use with silver epoxy. These attempts were not successful and we switched to soldering batteries.

Another aspect of all the MSP+CC1101 ATLAS tags is the use of pads that mate with a TagConnect cable. These TagConnect cable connected the tag to an MSP430 programmer (usually a low-cost LaunchPad). In the first version of the CC13X0 tags used a similar mechanism, but with a 10-pin cable, but we then switched to the 14-pin miniature connector.

Another piece of now-obsolete hardware is the first version of the filter, limiter, and bias tee. The design is described in a technical paper [UHFFrontEnd].

Figure A.5: Obsolete tags.

Appendix B

Technical Documentation: Software

B.1 Overall Structure of the Sources

ATLAS, Kamadata, and Vildehaye consist of several projects, listed in Tables B.1, B.2, and B.3, respectively. The sources and binaries are managed using Subversion on <https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects>. The Vildehaye firmware projects and the ATLAS native-code (C) project are part of one workspace, which I normally name `native`, maintained using Code Composer Studio (Texas Instruments' IDE, which is based on Eclipse). The other projects, which consist of Java source-code projects and configuration-files projects, are part of another workspace, which I name `atlas` that is maintained using Eclipse.

In general, the IDEs (Eclipse and Code Composer Studio) perform some (often most) of the tasks in the build process of the projects. The remaining tasks are performed by `build.bat` scripts that are part of some of the projects. Some projects also have `build.sh` scripts that are used to build the software under Linux. These scripts normally build everything when invoked with no arguments. Some of the scripts can perform partial builds specified by a command line argument.

The projects that make up ATLAS are listed in Table B.1. The `atlas-java` and `atlas-native` projects contain the Java and C sources for ATLAS.

In the **`atlas-java`** project, Eclipse is responsible for compiling the Java sources. The resulting class files are stored in the `bin` directory of the project. The code uses a fairly large number of external libraries; most of them are stored in the `jars` directory of the `atlas-distribution` project. The `atlas-java` project generates two Kamadata plugins; the code in these plugins depends on Kamadata, so the `atlas-java` project depends on the `kamadata` project. The project contains a `build.bat` script that generates `atlas.jar` and copies it to the `jars` directories of `atlas-distribution` and `kamadata`. There is also a `build.sh` for building `atlas.jar` on Linux, but it is not always up to date.

The **`sivantoledo`** project has a very similar structure. Eclipse compiles the Java source files and `build.bat` creates the `sivantoledo.jar` file and copies it to `atlas-distribution/jars` and `kamadata/jars`.

In the **`atlas-native`** project, the `build.bat` script is responsible for compiling and linking libraries (dll files) for Windows and for copying them to the `windows` directory of `atlas-distribution`. The `build.sh` script is responsible for compiling and linking li-

Project Name	Comments
atlas-java	Java sources
atlas-native	native (C) libraries that are called from Java code
atlas-distribution	mirrors the ATLAS software installations
packages	binary distributions
atlas-configuration	system configurations
atlas-documentation	this manual and other documentation
atlas-react	JavaScript React web app
certificates	scripts to build SSL/TLS certificates
sivantoledo	Java code that is not specific to ATLAS or Kamadata
ftd2xx_java	Custom build of an external library (slightly updated)
atlas-deps-native	Windows external libraries that the native libraries depend on

Table B.1: ATLAS projects. All of these except `sivantoledo` are stored on the Subversion server under `atlas`.

libraries for Linux and for copying them to the `linux*` directories of `atlas-distribution` (there is a separate library for each architecture). See Section B.4 for instructions on building the libraries on Linux and Section B.5 for Windows. The `atlas-deps-native` project contains Windows binaries for the external libraries that ATLAS's native libraries depend on, with build instructions in case you need to build these binaries from the sources.

The **atlas-distribution** project contains a mirror of the entire ATLAS distribution. You can normally run ATLAS directly from this project for testing.

The **packages** project contains the packed ATLAS distribution files, `atlas-distribution.tgz` and `atlas-distribution-experimental.tgz`, as well as the files that users download to obtain and update ATLAS, `update.sh` and `getit.zip`. The script `pack.sh` is used to create the distribution files; it updates `atlas-distribution` from Subversion, increments the version number (in `atlas-distribution/version.txt`) and time stamps the distribution (in `atlas-distribution/date.txt`), commits the version number and time stamp, creates the distribution file, and commits it to Subversion. Users download and unpack the distribution from Subversion using the HTTP protocol (not using the Subversion protocol) using the `update.sh` and `update.bat` scripts.

The **atlas-configuration** project contains both global configuration files for ATLAS and the configuration files for each ATLAS system. ATLAS users are given permission to update the configuration files of their systems.

The **atlas-documentation** project contains the source files for this manual.

The **atlas-react** project contains the sources of the ATLAS web app, accessible as <https://www.cs.tau.ac.il/~stoledo/atlas/>. It is written in JavaScript using a framework called React. The build system relies on `node.js` and its package and build management system, `npm`.

Project Name	Comments
kamadata	Java sources; also contains binary distributions
kamadata-basics	Java sources for Kamadata plugins
kamadata-movebank	Java sources for a Kamadata plugin to visualize Movebank studies
sivantoledo	Java code that is not specific to ATLAS or Kamadata
jxmapviewer2	Java sources for a slightly modified external map-visualization library that Kamadata uses

Table B.2: Kamadata projects.

We use a Java library called **ftd2xx_java** to communicate with the FTDI USB-to-serial bridge through an proprietary interface called the D2XX direct driver. This interface does not require installing an operating system driver and it does not rely on determining which operating-system serial port represents the bridge (a numbered COM port in Windows). The Java library is essentially an open-source wrapper for a native library. The available open-source version was too old and was not able to communicate with the bridge properly. I upgraded it to be compatible with the latest versions of the native library. The modified sources are managed on our Subversion server.

Kamadata is a pure Java program. It uses a similar but slightly simplified project structure. The sources of the main program are maintained in the **kamadata** project. The project also contains a `build.bat` script that builds the `kamadata.jar` file, a `pack.sh` script that builds the binary distribution files of Kamadata (`kamadata.tgz` and `kamadata-experimental.tgz`), the distribution files themselves, and the files that users download to install and update Kamadata, `update.sh` and `get-kamadata.zip`. In ATLAS, these functions are currently split into three different projects. Kamadata also relies on classes in `sivantoledo.jar`, which is built in the project **sivantoledo**.

Kamadata is a modular program. Some of its functionality is not built into the main program but into plugins. These plugins are jar files with a particular structure that allows Kamadata to use their code. Two plugins are built in the **kamadata-basics** and **kamadata-movebank** projects; `build.bat` scripts in these projects create jar plugin files and copy them to `kamadata/jars`. The `atlas.jar` file that is produced by the `atlas-java` project is also a Kamadata plugin.

The map viewer in Kamadata comes from an open-source project called `jxmapviewer2`. I modified it slightly to make it easier to use in Kamadata. The modified sources are available in the **jxmapviewer2** project. The main (probably only) modification from the original is a replacement of the logging infrastructure with the one that ATLAS uses.

Firmware for Vildehaye tags, base stations, and flash controllers is built by several projects with names that start with **vildehaye-tag**, **vildehaye-basestation**, and **vildehaye-flashcontroller**. These projects contain only configuration files; the actual sources are part of other projects, listed in the top part of Table B.3. The script `build.bat` in the **vildehaye-common** project copies the binary firmware files to `atlas-distribution/firmware`. Section B.6 explains the structure of these projects in more details.

Project Name	Comments
tags-msp430	obsolete; C sources for 1st-generation tags
vildehaye-common	Vildehaye C source code
vildehaye-common-cc13x0	TI-RTOS configuration
vildehaye-common-cc13x2	TI-RTOS configuration
vildehaye-sc-lvs-cc13x0-4x4	Sensor Controller code for tags
vildehaye-sc-lvs-hallsensor-cc13x0-4x4	Sensor Controller code for tags with a Hall sensor
vildehaye-sc-uart-cc13x0-7x7	Sensor Controller code for base stations (2nd UART)
vildehaye-basestation-cc13x0-launchpad	base station using a CC1350 or CC1310 LaunchPad evaluation board
vildehaye-flashcontroller-v2-6	flash controller using a V2.6 series tag
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-launchpad	tag, CC1350 or CC1310 LaunchPad
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6	tag, V2.6 and V2.8 series
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6-logger	tag, V2.6 with memory+sensors board
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6-altimeter	tag, V2.6.3 for logging the on-board BME280 pressure sensor
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6-bmp3xx	tag, V2.6.4 for logging the on-board BMP384 pressure sensor
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-9-hallsensor	tag, V2.9 series with Hall sensor
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-ax5031	tag with AX5031 PSK transmitter
vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-vesper	tag that mates with a Vesper board

Table B.3: Vildehaye firmware projects. They are all stored on the Subversion server under atlas. Only the projects listed below the double line produce actual firmware; the others contain source-code components that are used by the firmware projects.

B.2 Debugging the Java Code

ATLAS programs use a fairly complex initialization sequence, so debugging them is sometimes not straightforward. To debug the ATLAS Java code, always debug the program `tau.atlas.ui.Dispatcher`. This is the program that the ATLAS scripts run. You can specify to the debugger the command-line arguments and you need to provide at least one VM argument. In Eclipse, these settings are accessible via the *Run Configurations* screen. The required VM argument tells ATLAS where to find its native libraries:

```
-Djava.library.path=/files/atlas/atlas-distribution/windows
```

Adjust to the location of `atlas-distribution` on your computer and if you run under Linux, point to the directory containing the libraries. If you run ATLAS in a directory other than the one containing the sources (that is, other than the directory containing the `atlas-java` project), you need to specify another VM argument, which tells ATLAS where to find some resources that are normally included in the `atlas.jar` file:

```
-Dtau.atlas.resources=/files/atlas/atlas-java
```

Figure B.1 shows an appropriate debugging configuration for Eclipse.

Figure B.1: An Eclipse debugging configuration for ATLAS.

If you want to debug an ATLAS program that runs continuously like the receiver and server commands, add another VM argument:

```
-Dtau.atlas.configuration.script=/files/atlas/atlas-distribution/atlas-loop.bat
```

This tells ATLAS that it was started from a script whose name contains `-loop`; this causes ATLAS to check periodically for new configuration files and to abort if new files are found. If you omit this VM argument, the programs will run but they will not check for new configuration files.

B.3 Diagnosing Memory Leaks and Other Runtime Issues

To diagnose memory leaks (ATLAS programs that use more and more memory as they run and eventually run out of memory) you can use a few utilities that come with the Java Development Kit (JDK). These utilities can tell you what a running Java program is doing. Start with `jps`:

```
C:\files\atlas\atlas-tests>jps
25520 Jps
2868 Dispatcher
16508
```

This tells us that there are currently three Java programs running. The second one, running in process number 2868, is running the main method in the class `Dispatcher`; this is an ATLAS program. Now we use the `jmap` utility to determine the statistics of objects that this program currently uses:

```
C:\files\atlas\atlas-tests>jmap -histo:live,file=histo.txt 2868
```

The resulting file begins like this:

num	#instances	#bytes	class name (module)
1:	2932181	93162696	[B (java.base@14.0.1)
2:	1053448	75848256	tau.atlas.messages.DetectionMessage
3:	1400647	44820704	java.util.HashMap\$Node (java.base@14.0.1)
4:	1118593	26846232	java.lang.Long (java.base@14.0.1)
5:	318664	17846680	[[B (java.base@14.0.1)
6:	143415	15962568	[Ljava.util.HashMap\$Node; (java.base@14.0.1)
7:	327405	7857720	java.util.LinkedList\$Node (java.base@14.0.1)
8:	318651	7647624	com.mysql.jdbc.ByteArrayRow
9:	141642	6798816	java.util.HashMap (java.base@14.0.1)
10:	94793	5308408	tau.atlas.server.DetSet
11:	5785	1807120	[Ljava.lang.Object; (java.base@14.0.1)
12:	93722	1499552	java.util.HashMap\$Values (java.base@14.0.1)
13:	59839	1436136	java.lang.String (java.base@14.0.1)
14:	33825	1353000	java.util.TreeMap\$Entry (java.base@14.0.1)
15:	3252	1073848	[I (java.base@14.0.1)
16:	11392	911360	tau.atlas.server.TOALocalizationData
...			

This tells us that the type that is using the largest amount of memory is arrays of boolean variables, followed by ATLSA DetectionMessage objects. If there is a memory leak (in this example there was not) the type of objects that fill up most of the memory can help determine the cause of the leak.

The `jstack` utility tells us what different threads are doing and how much compute time they have used:

```
C:\files\atlas\atlas-tests>jstack 2868 > threads.txt
```

Here is what the resulting file contains:

```
022-04-16 07:53:01
```

```
Full thread dump OpenJDK 64-Bit Server VM (14.0.1+7 mixed mode, sharing):
```

```
Threads class SMR info:
```

```
_java_thread_list=0x0000024a2c66be50, length=18, elements={
0x0000024a765e2000, 0x0000024a7f247800, 0x0000024a7f248000, 0x0000024a7f262000,
0x0000024a7f265000, 0x0000024a7f266800, 0x0000024a7f26e000, 0x0000024a7f26f000,
0x0000024a7f272000, 0x0000024a7f3c0000, 0x0000024a7f3eb800, 0x0000024a2bc86000,
0x0000024a2da1e000, 0x0000024a2bec2000, 0x0000024a2bda3000, 0x0000024a2c760800,
0x0000024a2da42800, 0x0000024a2e871000
}
```

```
"main" #1 prio=5 os_prio=0 cpu=434015.63ms elapsed=1047.44s tid=0
  ↪ x0000024a765e2000 nid=0x203c runnable [0x0000004b197fd000]
  java.lang.Thread.State: RUNNABLE
    at org.apache.commons.math3.linear.Array2DRowRealMatrix.copyOut(
  ↪ Array2DRowRealMatrix.java:528)
```

```
...
```

```

    at tau.atlas.localization.LocalizationServer$Localization.localize(
↪ LocalizationServer.java:296)
    at tau.atlas.localization.LocalizationServer.take(LocalizationServer.java
↪ :924)
    at tau.atlas.localization.LocalizationServer.take(LocalizationServer.java
↪ :1)
    at tau.atlas.dataflow.Giver.give(Giver.java:38)
    ...
    at tau.atlas.ui.Dispatcher.invoke(Dispatcher.java:110)
    at tau.atlas.ui.Dispatcher.main(Dispatcher.java:196)

"Reference Handler" #2 daemon prio=10 os_prio=2 cpu=15.63ms elapsed=1047.38s tid
↪ =0x00000024a7f247800 nid=0x2c24 waiting on condition [0x0000004b19eff000]
java.lang.Thread.State: RUNNABLE
    at java.lang.ref.Reference.waitForReferencePendingList(java.base@14.0.1/
↪ Native Method)
    at java.lang.ref.Reference.processPendingReferences(java.base@14.0.1/
↪ Reference.java:241)
    at java.lang.ref.Reference$ReferenceHandler.run(java.base@14.0.1/
↪ Reference.java:213)

"Finalizer" #3 daemon prio=8 os_prio=1 cpu=0.00ms elapsed=1047.37s tid=0
↪ x00000024a7f248000 nid=0x6868 in Object.wait() [0x0000004b19fff000]
java.lang.Thread.State: WAITING (on object monitor)
    at java.lang.Object.wait(java.base@14.0.1/Native Method)
    - waiting on <no object reference available>
    at java.lang.ref.ReferenceQueue.remove(java.base@14.0.1/ReferenceQueue.
↪ java:155)
    - locked <0x0000000583e00dc0> (a java.lang.ref.ReferenceQueue$Lock)
    at java.lang.ref.ReferenceQueue.remove(java.base@14.0.1/ReferenceQueue.
↪ java:176)
    at java.lang.ref.Finalizer$FinalizerThread.run(java.base@14.0.1/Finalizer
↪ .java:170)

...

"GC Thread#0" os_prio=2 cpu=6125.00ms elapsed=1047.39s tid=0x00000024a7667a800 nid
↪ =0x5e24 runnable

...
```

We can see what the main thread is doing, we can see that it has been using a lot of computer time, more than 434 s, and that most of the other threads are service threads that have not used much computer time. The garbage-collection threads did use significant computer time; when there is a memory leak, they sometimes use huge amounts of time, another indication that there is a problem.

B.4 Building Native Libraries on Linux

```
sudo apt install subversion to check out and commit code and binaries
```

```
sudo apt install librtlsdr-dev
sudo apt install libfftw3-dev
sudo apt install libuhd-dev
sudo apt install nvidia-cuda-toolkit for the GPU library
```

To build the CUDA signal-processing library, you will also need to download a source-code library called CUB from <https://nvlabs.github.io/cub>. It comes as a ZIP archive that only needs unpacking; no further installation is required. We currently use CUB version 1.8.0.

The SVN server that we use runs an old software version that prevents files from being compressed when they are being transferred. To use a current SVN client with this server, change the file `~/.subversion/servers` so that in the `[global]` section you have a line that reads:

```
[global]
...
http-compression = no
```

(you can also set this option only for ATLAS's SVN server; see the file for instructions.)

Check out the projects. You can use Eclipse, or the command line interface:

```
svn co --username username https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/atlas-distribution
↪ //you will be prompted for the password
svn co --username username https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/packages
svn co --username username https://svn.cs.tau.ac.il/stoledo/projects/atlas/atlas-native
```

Now you can build the libraries, either all of them (the first line, no arguments), or just specific ones (the following lines)

```
./build.sh build all libraries
./build.sh dsp or just this one
./build.sh radio-uhd or this one
./build.sh radio-rtlsdr etc
```

B.5 Building Native Libraries on Windows

To build the native libraries on Windows, install Visual Studio Community Edition. The instructions and scripts are for Visual Studio 2019. The community edition is free for individuals, academic use, and open source projects. The installer will offer to install optional feature; install *C++ CMake tools for Windows* and *C++ CMake tools for Linux*, which help build some libraries that the ATLAS libraries depend on. Other than that, you will need mainly the C

Check out the `atlas-native` and `atlas-deps-native` projects from SVN. I use Code Composer Studio (a version of Eclipse) to do that. The ATLAS native libraries in `atlas-native` rely on a few other native libraries that are included (and optionally built) in `atlas-deps-native`; I did not find an easy way to install the dependencies as on Linux.

The build script in `atlas-native` builds the native libraries and copies them to `atlas-distribution`. Once you build new libraries, you can commit the binaries in `atlas-`

distribution and then pack the ATLAS distributable files on a Linux computer. The build script in `atlas-native` has variables that point to `atlas-deps-native` and to `atlas-distribution`. You may need to change them to fit your directory structure. Similarly, the script invokes a script that comes with Visual Studio and sets up environment variables that the compiler depends on; you may also need to change the path to that script, if you use another version of Visual Studio or if it installed in a non-standard location. The commands to build the libraries are essentially the same as on Linux:

```
build.bat          build all libraries
build.bat dsp      or just this one
build.bat radio-uhd  or this one
build.bat radio-rtlsdr etc
```

If you want to build the libraries that ATLAS depends on from the sources (you do not need to), you can use the build script in `atlas-deps-native` to do that. The project includes zip files with the sources for the four libraries, all from github or sourceforge. You can download up-to-date libraries if you like; the URLs are given in `build.bat`. You need to unpack three of the libraries, `rtl-sdr`, `pthread4w`, and perhaps `libusb`. The script will build the first two if you give it the arguments `rtlsdr` and `pthread` (or if you run it with no arguments). The third, `libusb`, contains a Visual Studio *solution* that you can open with Visual Studio to build the library. In Visual Studio, choose the x64 Release settings and build. You can then copy the output files so ATLAS can use them using `build.bat libusb`. However, we encountered problems with the binaries built this way; the official binary distribution does not cause these problems, so we normally use it.

The fourth library, FFTW, is a bit more complicated to build, but not by much. Create a new Visual Studio project for a dynamic library. Then exist Visual Studio, unpack the contents of the zip file into it, and open the solution again. In the solution view, click the icon with the tooltip *Switch View* and use it to switch to the *Folder View* mode. This causes Visual Studio to discover all the sources that you added, including the input files to the CMake build system, and to configure the project. In the Solution Explorer subwindow, click the icon with the tooltip *Switch View* icon again and use it to switch to the *CMake Targets View*, then right-click the project name in the Solution Explorer subwindow and select *CMake Settings*. You can reach the same screen from the menus Project and then CMake Target Settings. In the CMake Settings subwindow, set the *Configuration type* to either Release and in the *Toolset* field select x64 or x86. Now, in the CMake Settings subwindow, click the link *Save and generate CMake cache to load variables*. When the process finishes, click the link a second time (sometimes this is needed, but it never hurts). Now enable the following options (some may already be selected):

```
BUILD_SHARED_LIBS
DISABLE_FORTTRAN
ENABLE_FLOAT
ENABLE_SSE
ENABLE_SSE2
ENABLE_THREADS
WITH_COMBINED_THREADS
```

You can disable these options:

```
BUILD_TESTS
ENABLE_OPENMP
ENABLE_AVX
ENABLE_AVX2
```

Now select from the menu Build and Rebuild All and Visual Studio should build the library. Finally, invoke `build.bat fftw` to copy the library to the target location.

(We used to build FFTW with support for AVX and AVX2, which are families of vector instructions; it turns out that the processors of some laptops do not support AVX and/or AVX2, and this caused ATLAS to fail on them, so we removed the support for them; this may degrade performance on processors with support for these instructions.)

B.6 Building the Vildehaye Firmware

Firmware for Vildehaye tags and base stations is built using *Code Composer Studio* (CCS), a free IDE based on Eclipse that is developed by Texas Instruments. You will need to download from and install CCS. The installation procedure asks you which processors and hardware debuggers you would like the IDE to support. You need to install support for the CC13XX processors, which are part of TI's SimpleLink line of RF processors and which are based on the ARM architecture, and for the XDS110 debugger, which is part of CC13XX LaunchPads.

The sources for the firmware are managed using Subversion, so once you install CCS, add Subversion support (Subclipse from the Eclipse Marketplace) and check out the Vildehaye firmware projects listed in Table B.3 (or just those you need to build).

The ARM compiler and the driver for the LaunchPad debugger is installed by CCS, but to build the firmware you also need the software development kit (SDK) for the CC13X0. If you build firmware for CC13X2 devices, you will also need the SDK for CC13X2 and CC26X2; it is separate from the SDK for CC13X0. You can download the SDKs from TI.

Finally, you also need to download and install *Sensor Controller Studio*, another free software from TI, which builds the firmware for a low-power processor called a *sensor controller* that is part of all the CC13XX chips. It is programmed in a subset of C.

The code for Vildehaye firmware is split among several projects with different functions:

- The actual C source code that runs on the main ARM processor of the CC13XX chips is all stored in `vildehaye-common`.
- The configuration of the operating system, called TI-RTOS, is stored in the `release.cfg` file in the projects `vildehaye-common-cc13x0` and `vildehaye-common-cc13x2`.
- Sensor-controller code is stored in projects with a `vildehaye-sc` prefix. The actual code and settings are stored in files with an `scp` suffix. You need to open them with Sensor Controller Studio and generate the code. This produces a number of C files that become part of the ARM firmware and that contain both the sensor-controller binary and code to interface between the two processors. Sensor-controller code is specific to both the family of processors (CC13X0 or CC13X2) and to the physical package, which we refer to by its size (e.g., 4x4 or 7x7).

- The projects that actually build the firmware files have names like `vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6`. The second word, here `tag`, indicates the function of the firmware (`tag`, `base station`, or `flash controller`). The `cc13x0` indicates the SDK that the firmware uses (`cc13x0` or `cc13x2`). The next part of the project's name indicates the hardware that the firmware is designed to run on, here `v2-6` refers to tags from the Version 2.6 series. There is sometimes another part in the project name, such as `logger`, that indicates that this firmware supports an optional feature, here logging sensor data.

The firmware projects (`vildehaye-tag-cc13x0-v2-6` etc) contain *linked folder* that contain the C code (a link to `vildehaye-common`) and the sensor-controller code (e.g., a link to `vildehaye-sc-lvs-cc13x0-4x4`). These project also have a dependency on an operating-system configuration project (e.g., `vildehaye-common-cc13x0`). Finally, the firmware projects also contain a single header file, `config.h`, that configures the project. This file is included in virtually all the C files in `atlas-common`, so all of them can depend on the firmware's configuration. The configuration has two aspects. First, `config.h` includes a header or two from `atlas-common` that specify the configuration of a particular hardware board. These files have names like `board_vildehaye_v2_6.h`, etc; these files specify which pin of the CC13XX is connected on the board to which external component (e.g., an LED or a serial communication channel).

To build the firmware, simple select *Build Project* from the *Project* menu in CCS, or click on the hammer icon. The firmware file, in hex format, is stored in the Debug or Release directories. The script `atlas.bat` in `vildehaye-common` (not in each of the firmware projects) copies the hex files to `atlas-distribution\firmware`.

B.7 Hourly Consistency Enforcement

When ATLAS server use an ATLAS database whose `hourlyConsistency` property is true (the default), the server recompute localizations whenever new detections arrive. Administrators can also invoke this mechanism explicitly using the `invalidate` command to trigger a recomputation of localizations in the database.

The recomputation is done in batches of one hour on all the tags in the system. The mechanism is implemented in the `HourlyConsistencyEnforcer` class and it uses the `HOURLY_INVALIDATIONS` table in the database.

The table has three columns (fields): `hour`, a unix time specifying an hour in which localizations must be recomputed, `invalidation`, unix time that describes the time that the last detection for that hour was stored in the database (or the end of the invalid hour if the record was created explicitly, not as a result of the arrival of new detections), and `state`, which describes the state of the recomputation.

When the server creates the `HourlyConsistencyEnforcer` object, the constructor checks if the table includes a record with `hour` less than or equal to zero. If there is no such record, it assumes that the entire table is invalid and populates it with a marker record with `hour=0` and with a normal invalidation record for every hour from the time of the first detection in the database to the hour of the last detection. This in effect triggers recomputation of all the localizations in the database. Beware of accidentally deleting the marker record.

The constructor also creates a timer that runs a method called `enforce` at least every minute. This method tries to find invalidation records and if it finds one, attempts to recompute the localization for that hour.

The enforcer searches for the non-marker record with the oldest `INVALIDATION` time. It only consider invalidation times older than 2 minutes. If it finds an invalidation record, it updates its `STATE` to 1, marking it as an active record. The `STATE` of all the other records is 0, inactive.

If an invalidation record is found, the enforcer tries to compute the localization in that hour. It creates a `LocalizationServer` to compute the localization, a few associated objects, and connects them to a `detections-query` object that the constructor initialized. It performs no filtering (reads detections for all tags within a specified time period).

The options or properties that control how the localizations are computed are the properties of the `ATLAS` database that created the enforcer. Note that these options could be different from the options of the server under which the enforcer runs.

There are two ways that the enforcer can perform the recomputation, depending on the property `localizeBulkDedup` of the `ATLAS` database. If the property is false (the default is true), the enforcer uses a simple way: it connects the output of the `LocalizationServer` to the `ATLAS` database. It then starts the `detections` query with a time period that starts 2 minutes before the hour and ends 5 minutes after the hour and connects the output. This causes the query to feed the `detections grouper`, which emits localization problems within the hour (it filters by time), which are processed by the `LocalizationServer`. The emitted localization are fed back to the database object, which writes them to the database.

The other way stores the computed localizations in an auxiliary table and copies them to the `LOCALIZATIONS` table in bulk. The code starts by deleting everything from the `TEMP_LOCALIZATIONS` table. It then constructs an object that takes localizations from the `LocalizationServer` and stores them in this temporary table. It then runs the `detections` query. When the recomputation ends (with localizations in the temporary table), the code deletes all the localizations for that hour from the main `LOCALIZATIONS` table, copies all the records from the temporary table to the main table, and commits. It then writes a log record with statistics about the recomputation (`retrieved X detections computed Y localizations for hour...`).

Next, the code updates the two hourly-summaries tables, `HOURLY_TAG_BS_SUMMARIES` and `HOURLY_TAG_SUMMARIES`.

Finally, the code deletes the invalidation record, but only if the state is still 1. If the state returned to zero, the code will recompute the hour again.

Detections that are inserted into the database are also passed on to the `updateHourlyInvalidation` method of the enforcer. The method maintains a map that tells it the last time a detection for a particular hour was processed. When a detection arrives, the method checks if it in the map. If so, it retrieves the last time stamp from the map. If not, it checks whether the `HOURLY_INVALIDATIONS` table contains a record for that hour; if so, the time stamp in the record is used, and the method also remembers the state of the recomputation process for the hour.

If there is no previous time stamp or the hour is active (being recomputed) or the last time stamp is more than 2 minutes old, the method updates the map with the current

tie and also updates the HOURLY_INVALIDATIONS table with a new time stamp (now) and an inactive (0) state. This causes the hour to be eventually recomputed.

The 2-minute grace period reduces the rate of writes to HOURLY_INVALIDATIONS from one per detection (possibly many per second) to one every 2 minutes.

Detections that are inserted into the database are also passed on to an Invalidator object whose job is to update the HOURLY_INVALIDATION table.

Here are examples of definitions of a server and its database with the enforcement and localization options in bold.

```
>,Database,huji2_db,jdbc:mysql:132.64.17.55/hula
>,>,Property,localizeBulkDedup,true
>,>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true

>,Server,huji2,132.64.17.55,6789,primary,huji2_db
>,>,Property,id,972001094
>,>,Property,backup,false
>,>,Property,localize,true
>,>,Property,recentActivity,true
>,>,Property,hourlyConsistency,true
>,>,Property,localization.extendedResults,true
```

If you define the relevant properties as properties of the ATLAS system, the parent of the server and database definitions, both the server and the database will inherit these properties.

B.8

Figure B.2: Data flow graph of query processing in the HourlyConsistencyEnforcer.

Figure B.3: Data flow graph of query processing in the Query class (ATLAS query command).

Figure B.4: Data flow graph of query processing in the NewServer class (ATLAS server command).